

**DEVELOPMENT OF A SERVICE-LEARNING CURRICULUM FOR
ENHANCING EMPLOYABILITY AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP SKILLS OF
UNDERGRADUATES OF PUBLIC UNIVERSITIES IN SOUTHWESTERN
NIGERIA**

BY

**Ololade Serifat OMOSUNLADE
B.Ed., M. Ed. (Ibadan)
Matric. No. :150656**

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CERTIFICATION

I certify that this work was carried out by Ololade Serifat OMOSUNLADE in the Department of Arts and Social Sciences Education, University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Nigeria under my supervision.

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Supervisor
Tolulope Victoria Gbadamosi
B.Ed, M.Ed, Ph.D (Ibadan)
Arts and Social Sciences Education Department,
University of Ibadan, Nigeria

DEDICATION

This thesis is dedicated to the Almighty Allah, my family, friends, and all those who have supported me throughout this journey.

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ABSTRACT

Employability and Entrepreneurship Skills (EESs), core 21st century skills, were infused into the curriculum of universities in Nigeria to address inadequate practical skills existing in the curriculum. Reports have shown that many undergraduates of public universities in southwestern Nigeria are deficient in EESs. Previous studies on EESs concentrated more on employers' perceptions of graduates' employability and evaluation of entrepreneurship curriculum than on development of a Service Learning (SL) curriculum. This study, therefore, developed a service-learning curriculum to enhance EESs among undergraduates of public universities in southwestern Nigeria.

Kolb's Experiential Learning, Schultz Human Capital theories, and Kerr's Model of Curriculum Design provided the framework. It employed a mixed-method design, implementing a multistage sampling procedure. Four public universities (two federal-University of Lagos, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife and two state- Lagos State University and Osun State University) were randomly selected for need assessment. Then, University of Ibadan was purposively selected for the curriculum try-out. For the need assessment, four faculties (education, arts, science and social science) common to the sampled universities were purposively selected, while four departments (one from each faculty) were randomly selected. The purposive sampling technique was employed to select 300 level students offering GES 301(Entrepreneurship), while random sampling technique was utilised to select 1,076 undergraduates (269 per university). For the curriculum try-out, University of Ibadan was purposively selected being the oldest in southwestern Nigeria, while 168 students (42 per faculty) offering GES 301 were randomly selected. The instruments used were Service-learning Curriculum for EESs Need Assessment ($r=0.93$), Awareness of Employability Skills($r=0.82$), Awareness of Entrepreneurship Skills ($r=0.83$) questionnaires; SL Curriculum for Employability Skills Validation Rating ($r=0.81$), SL Curriculum for Entrepreneurship Skills Validation Rating ($r=0.85$), SL Curriculum Observers Rating ($r=0.84$), SL Curriculum for EESs Participants' Perception ($r=0.80$) scales. Key informant interviews were held with 20 stakeholders (human resource managers, entrepreneurs, SL experts and curriculum experts). The quantitative data were analysed using descriptive statistics, while qualitative data were analysed using content-analysis.

The mean age of the undergraduates was 20.56 ± 2.06 and 63.0% were female. The majority (60.0%) of the validators were Ph.D. holders. Undergraduates were aware of employability ($\bar{x} = 3.17$) and entrepreneurship ($\bar{x} = 3.59$) skills. However, stakeholders had a negative view of graduates' possession of EESs which justified the need for a SL curriculum. Stakeholders had positive perception of the content adequacy, suitability, and relevance of the developed SL curriculum to enhance EESs among undergraduates ($\bar{x} = 3.68$) against the threshold of 2.50. Undergraduates had positive perception of the extent to which the objectives of the SL curriculum promote EESs ($\bar{x} = 3.28$) at the threshold of 2.50 The undergraduates recommended making a SL curriculum available to increase their understanding of social responsibility, change job-seeking expectations, and gain valuable skills for becoming productive employees or employers who can give back to society.

The service-learning curriculum developed enhanced undergraduates' employability and entrepreneurship skills in public institutions in southwestern Nigeria. This curriculum is recommended for adoption by universities.

Keywords: Employability skills, Entrepreneurship skills, Service-learning curriculum, University undergraduates, Southwestern Nigeria.

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Study

Nigeria, like many other countries, recognizes education as a key instrument for achieving national development across social, economic, and political sectors. For educational goals to be fully attained, the curriculum must be designed and delivered effectively to sharpen individuals' minds and help transform society to become globally competitive. However, Nigeria, as a developing nation, faces challenges such as inadequate human capital development, high unemployment, and issues with educational reforms. As a result, graduates often emerge with a focus on abstract and theoretical knowledge, lacking practical employability and entrepreneurship skills necessary for the 21st-century economy. While higher education plays a crucial role in economic development, simply learning in school does not guarantee a person's ability to create jobs. Therefore, this underscores the need for academics to advocate for improvements in the higher education system.

Adeleye (2019) and Sangoleye (2018) submitted that though undergraduates and graduates were positively disposed to self-employment through the introduction of entrepreneurship education curriculum, but not every graduate can be an entrepreneur. Therefore, there should be a curriculum which will balance the exposure of Higher Education students to both entrepreneurship and employability skills which will invariably improve the supply of labour and contribute to the nation's economic growth. However, for any meaningful national growth, the development of the education sector must not be taken for granted because it is an essential yardstick in determining the overall development of other sectors in the economy.

As pointed in the National Policy on Education of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (2014), section 5, sub- section 81, the goals higher education should achieve are:

- i. Strengthen national growth through promoting workforce development.
- ii. Meet the needs and interests of all Nigerians by offering accessible, affordable, and high-quality learning options in both formal and informal education.
- iii. Provide students with access to lifelong learning opportunities and high-quality career counselling so they are equipped with the knowledge and skills needed for independence and the workforce.
- iv. Reduce skill shortages by producing skilled workers who align with market demands.
- v. Promote and foster entrepreneurship, scholarship, and community service.
- vi. Create and solidify national unity,
- vii. Encourage dialogue and understanding between nations (FRN, 2014)

Considering items, i - vii above, they focused more on how higher education students can acquire both employability and entrepreneurship skills which will invariably lead to development of the economy. Employability has been described by Pitan (2016) as graduates possessing a set of skills and competencies that enable them to compete and secure job opportunities. Employability was also discussed by Yorke and Knight (2006) and Idaka (2013), both of whom focused on graduate employability. Idaka (2013) defined employability as being "work-ready," which is the possession of skills, knowledge, attitude, and commercial understanding that enables graduates to be successful in their chosen careers and gain employment. Researchers such as Barot (2015); Chang (2015); Croci (2016); and Sangoleye (2018) highlighted the fact that entrepreneurship skills would bring innovation to the job market since it is an artistic discipline that examines entrepreneurship's management process, which includes creativity, autonomy, capacity for flexibility, risk taking, strategic thinking, customer service, and financial analysis.

Hence, it is believed that acquisition of these skills will aid sustainability of businesses and promote economic growth. Additionally, according to researchers like Evans (2012) and Jackson (2012) have stated that there is still a disconnect between what businesses expect and what higher education offers (Jackson, 2012). Therefore, to have

an impact on graduates' profession going forward; educationalists, policymakers, and government parastatals need to pay more attention to a variety of generic, transferable and core skills to make its impact on graduates seeking employment and self-employment opportunities more effective (McLarty, 2005). According to Ajeyalemi (2018), soft skills and knowledge required for the workplace are less emphasized in Nigerian education than they should be. According to him, the higher education curriculum places little emphasis on the development of fundamental 21st-century skills like critical and analytical thinking, problem-solving, collaboration, adaptability, communication, taking calculated risks, work ethics, and information ethics, among others.

The failure of tertiary education to provide students with practical skills has resulted in resource waste of both human and natural resources because young people and graduates lack connections and there is a mismatch between what the industry requires of them and the knowledge they have acquired in tertiary institutions (Nwangwu, 2007; Onuoha, 2011). However, according to Afonja and Oyekunle (2020), the Nigerian government added entrepreneurship education to the university curricula in 2006 through the National Universities Commission (NUC) to instil entrepreneurship skills, knowledge, and attitudes in university students as well as to encourage entrepreneurial innovations and job creation. This initiative was started to promote self-employment among university freshmen and lessen their reliance on the public and commercial sectors for employment (Tomlinson, 2017).

The current entrepreneurship education curriculum covers pertinent entrepreneurship concepts, the history of entrepreneurship, unit operations and time management, creativity, and innovation, overcoming barriers to job creation, opportunities for entrepreneurship, and feasibility studies of starting a new business, but it does not cover the essential 21st century skills that UNESCO recommended to promote employability and entrepreneurship skills in 2020. Sangoleye (2018) continued by stating that the goals of the entrepreneurship curriculum are to provide pragmatic education to help young people become independent and self-employed, to give them the necessary training to be creative and innovative, to educate them on risk management and risk taking, to prevent rural-urban migration, and to instil a spirit of perseverance.

Therefore, it is anticipated that the entrepreneurship education curriculum should be able to provide undergraduates with the pertinent skills needed to enhance the quality of the graduate labour supply in Nigeria provided it is properly implemented and successful in reaching its purpose. However, it can be observed from the figure 1.1 that for over a decade after the introduction of this entrepreneurship education, the problem of unemployment is still being scratched on the surface. The mystery of unemployment appears to have worsened. In year 2007, unemployment rate was 5.3%, 2008 was 5.8%, and gradually, it kept increasing to 33.3% as at year 2021 Q1. However, the problem of unemployment has various factors in which problem of labour supply is among, which will be the focus of this study since the acquisition of these skills will improve the quality of labour supply in the economy.

Fig 1.1: Youth Unemployment Rate in Nigeria (2007- 2021 Q1)

Source: Trading Economics/ National Bureau of Statistics (2021)

Evidence from the unemployment increment over the years made Nwadioku (2019) assert that to conquer the supply of labour side of these problems, the twenty-first century curriculum should be carefully scrutinised. It should be embedded with certain critical attributes such as being interdisciplinary, project-based, research-driven, collaborative, incorporation of higher order thinking skills, multiple intelligences, information technology, authentic assessments and most importantly, incorporate experiential learning of which service-learning is a good fit. It is also worth noting that Pitan and Adedeji, (2012), Adebakin, Ajadi, and Subair, (2014), Pitan, (2016) Sangoleye, (2018) have carried out a lot of studies on employability skills and entrepreneurship skills but studies have not delved into how a service-learning curriculum can enhance both employability skills and entrepreneurship skills in Nigeria Also the ideals ingrained in the entrepreneurship education program, should go a long way in changing graduates from job hunters to job creators, according to prior studies.

Sangoleye (2018) found that the learning materials used to implement the curriculum for entrepreneurship education were insufficient and misused. He also discovered that the most common teaching strategies utilized to apply the entrepreneurship education curriculum were writing, presenting company ideas, and feasibility studies, which has impeded students from getting practical experience (Skilbeck and Connell, 2004). He observed that the existing entrepreneurship curriculum has certain deficiencies in its delivery. The lecture method is the major teaching method used in delivering the curriculum. Also, the delivery rarely goes beyond notes, assignments, tests and examination leaving out any form of experiential learning. Also, this entrepreneurship curriculum does not expose students to research driven and hands-on activities such as involvement in professional development projects, service engagements, environmental projects, community projects etc. which are present in service-learning (Steiner, and Watson, 2006).

Therefore, the prompt for this study is to address these deficiencies, because Nigeria higher education should have gone beyond only classroom teaching and learning since university graduates critical need to demonstrate self-independence, get professional skills, get involved in research driven activities to solve diverse problems,

acquire relevant soft skills, and implement solutions (Bamber and Hankin, 2011). However, teaching engagement like service-learning can effectively empower students by providing them with authentic experiences that encourage critical-thinking, teamwork, innovation, networking, problem-solving, strategic thinking, work ethics, emotional intelligence, and the application of knowledge to the overall development (Bligh, 2010). Hence, this study will capture 21st century skills which are some of the deficiencies in the existing entrepreneurship curriculum. Some of these skills listed by UNESCO (2020) include conflict resolution, self-management, information technology, media literacy, collaboration, communication, work and social media ethics, critical-thinking, problem solving, capacity for life-long learning, emotional intelligence, networking, marketing, and leadership.

Hence, the peculiarity of service-learning to this study over and above other plethora of approaches is that it can be used to articulate a curriculum that holistically integrates social and academic standards due to experiential educational opportunities available in promoting a connected, purposeful, and positive school experience (Bender, 2005). In addition, service-learning has a lot of potential as a teaching and learning technique for raising academic engagement and performance, according to Bligh (2010). He clarified that taking part in high-quality service-learning can lead to improved skill and knowledge acquisition as well as improved problem-solving abilities. Additionally, the utilization of service-learning as a crucial engagement approach will help students develop their competencies implicitly and take charge of their own learning. Elmhurst University (2021) also emphasized the significance of service-learning, saying that it fosters the habit of doing good deeds for others, deepens students' engagement in their local communities, equips them with useful skills, and helps them pursue their career and personal interests.

It is to be noted that some of these benefits includes connecting student learning from the classroom with real-world experiences in the community and instilling the habit of doing good deeds for others. Researchers such as Akpan and Etor, (2013), Oliver, (2015), Pitan, and Sangoleye, (2016) confirmed that the rise in student enrolment and graduate turnover in Nigerian higher education institutions over the past three decades is a major contributor to the problem of graduate unemployment. They argued that

graduates' unemployment is not primarily caused by a lack of employment opportunities, but rather by a lack of employability and entrepreneurial abilities, as the labour market now wants graduates with practical soft skills experience. In a similar spirit, Newton (2015) and Pitan (2016) argued that graduates must now demonstrate the abilities and qualities necessary to compete and work with others in a variety of fields. They stated that graduates should possess valuable skills and attributes required to cooperate with each other in a dynamic knowledge economy.

According to earlier research cited by Popoola (2017) and Dugguh (2018), universities in Nigeria are preparing students for jobs that are no longer in demand. They claimed that this is due to the lack of an academic culture that fosters creativity, cutting-edge research, engages in technology transfer, and the inability to recognize societal problems and conduct research to solve them, as well as the graduates' inadequate preparation to effectively address current problems that affect their communities and to face future challenges. Dugguh and Gbadamosi (2018) also noted that after years of using traditional teaching methods in Nigerian educational institutions, teachers have realized the necessity to fix the flaws in the students' out-of-date instruction. Consequently, service-learning as a course will successfully equip students to handle the challenges of 21st-century jobs. The solution, according to studies by Deba, Jabor, Buntat, and Musta'mal (2014), requires the adoption of a method of education and the training of students to critically think and successfully address societal difficulties like unemployment, hunger, poverty, and redundancy, among others.

Additionally, Gbadamosi (2014) supported the idea that service-learning develops as a tool to improve students' learning, re-establish their connections to their communities, balance learning and living, and mend the rift between learning and society. To effectively produce students who can face the difficulties of the next generation, service-learning as experiential learning should gradually take root in the Nigerian tertiary education system. More explicitly, as Dewey (1938) pointed out, education can only be effective and valuable when it is pragmatic. As a result, education should include purposeful practical learning based on real-world application of lessons conducted through a phenomenon known as experiential learning, which is based on learning by experience (Olagoke-Oladokun, Mokhtar, Gbadamosi and Dugguh, 2020). As

a result, the goal of this educational intervention is to facilitate service-learning as an effective teaching engagement in a curriculum document to enhance students' learning when they engage in the action and activities involved in the acquisition of skills and knowledge.

Meanwhile, studies by Lees (2002) and Pitan (2016) confirmed their findings that the existing university curriculum does not produce graduates with the professional and lifelong learning skills required to succeed in a competitive and changing job market. According to Rufai, Bakar, and Rashid (2015), higher education institutions have been chastised for providing training that is irrelevant to the social and economic needs of their countries, resulting in the production of unemployable graduates. Boeteng and Ofori-Sarpong (2002), Akerele (2004) and Abiodun (2010), also revealed information technology, financial analysis, and resources management, among others. Also, graduates should be able to relate these attributes to experience in terms of competencies and skills. It could be deduced that employers of labour force are not only interested in those with higher education degrees but also practical skills appropriate for job fulfilment.

The study of Kolb (1984) also deserved some commendation because it can be deduced from his cycle that service-learning is a form of experiential learning which enables students to apply the knowledge acquired in the classroom towards the development of their personal, social, and immediate environment. It can further be inferred that service-learning is not merely an add-on experience requiring students to do something good for the community; rather, it is a form of experiential learning (Kolb, 1984). Hence, when an undergraduate undergoes this type of curriculum, such students would be adequately informed on how to handle real life scenarios which will enhance their employability and entrepreneurship skills. Therefore, this study is to encourage the cognitive growth of students to think outside the box, become employable graduates and job creators, through the introduction of service-learning curriculum into higher education which will make students pragmatically respond to improving their hard and soft skills required for self-development, access to quality life, self-reliance and being gainfully employed if so wish (Bender, 2005).

Since the goal of every graduate is to either be employed or be an employer of labour at the end of their education programme, it makes sense to place service-learning

in the core of our higher institutions because it will aid how students learn by doing which will reinforce mastery and acquisition of relevant skills (Bender, 2005). The importance of service-learning to this study is specifically the unsatisfactory state of the existing entrepreneurship curriculum which does not engage features of experiential learning and out-of-class activities to promote the acquisition of valuable skills needed in the global job market. Gbadamosi (2019) further revealed that service-learning is used to increase effectiveness of students in the classroom. It addresses students' complaints on the abstract nature of concepts by providing them with opportunities to deal with real world issues in their communities through service projects and experiences (Abiodun, 2010).

Gbadamosi (2019) also stated that service-learning helps students in career exploration, acquisition of career skills and development of positive work attitude and orientation. It is therefore important, that to improve the quality of labour supply in the economy, and not encounter the same challenge as the entrepreneurship education curriculum did, there should be a framework established for developing a service-learning curriculum aimed at accommodating and promoting both employability and entrepreneurship skills (Berasategi, Alonso and Roman, 2016). Thus, it may be necessary to promote experiential learning using service-learning to aid the acquisition of these valuable skills. This hereby implies that whenever we need to see changes in the society, a curriculum must aid such changes and bring it into effect through curriculum development (Bringle and Hatcher, 2000). Hence, in developing a service-learning curriculum, the steps involve conceptualization of the service-learning components of the course, speculating the scope of service-learning projects to be associated with the course subject matters, developing the course subject matter by using a curriculum design model and applying for a service-learning course designation.

Curriculum refers to the subject matter, while curriculum development is the process of creating lessons that help students learn that subject matter (Buchanan, Baldwin, and Rudisill, 2002). Alsubaie (2016) defines curriculum development as a process of meeting students' needs, which leads to improvements in their learning. Babalola (2019) describes it as a framework or model for conceptualizing curriculum components. This process involves determining what students need to learn, analyzing

the best methodology to present that content, developing learning materials using appropriate methods, and then evaluating and revising those materials. Although time-consuming, it significantly enhances learning (Heffernan, 2001).

Huang and Yang (2004) critique current curricula and curriculum development in educational settings, suggesting they often amount to little more than checklists influenced by politics and the textbook market. For example, students must take specific tests in certain years, courses must align with these tests, and state laws may prescribe certain topics and treatments (Kenworthy-U'Ren, 2008).

On the other hand, good teachers develop their syllabi, to teach what they believe their students need to learn, about the subject at hand, at their stage of development (Pitan and Adedeji, 2012) and may well adjust that from semester to semester as new developments emerge, and as they refine their teaching styles (Kolawole, 2015). In the same vein, universities, develop degree programmes, that dictate a menu of required and elective courses, needed to earn a particular degree. Curriculum design is a systematic engagement of academic instructions, methodologies, and experiences aimed at preparing individuals to be productive members of society. It is logical, relatable, and sequential (Tomlinson, 2017). Curriculum design begins by clearly defining the teaching goals of the course, outlining what needs to be taught, for how long, and in what sequence. Teachers then act as course facilitators, guiding students through the learning process. Ideally, the curriculum format is logical and includes all the appropriate material (Steiner and Watson, 2006).

The first implementation of any new curriculum requires close observation and necessary modifications (Nwankwo, 2003). Without existing curriculum models, one would start by considering the features of a curriculum, including defining its scope. Thus, thinking about how to market the course, the types of students who will take it, the required number of teachers, and subject specializations are essential to curriculum development and models (Akinbode and Oyelude, 2020). A curriculum model serves as the backbone of a curriculum, providing the framework, while curriculum design involves building on the chosen model or even creating a new one and planning the curriculum in greater detail.

A curriculum model embraces the key components of the curriculum. A search on curriculum models such as Tyler, Taba, Wheeler, Skilbeck, Walker reveals how these models would help to shape the design of a curriculum (Huang and Yang, 2004). In the same vein, how will the students be assessed and by who and innumerable other issues is also a critical issue to consider (Yuan and Huang, 2000).

Thus, failure to acknowledge this, students' academic progress would be slow, disorganised and probably there would be deficits in one's plan (Yorke and Knight, 2006). Curriculum models will help you plan your course by using the key curriculum components such as aims, Subject Matter, methods, assessment, and evaluation, as a framework to enable sequential and ordered planning (Silva, 2008). The choice of design will help you decide which parts of the curriculum have greater significance, for example, if a situational analysis is important to consider before planning then a dynamic curriculum model would be more appropriate to your needs, this type of model is highly flexible and open to change and respond to ongoing concerns that emerge (Silva, 2008). If 'evaluation' is one of the most important components in the course, then choose a cyclic model, which ensures ongoing evaluation of the course and incorporation of changes before the next iteration. If your course is straightforward go for a linear model. Curriculum models help course planners to develop a course that is most suited to the school/college etc (Sharifi, McCombs and Kattelus, 2003)

Therefore, curriculum model is a conceptual framework and tool that guides curriculum experts in the curriculum design process. Kolawole, Amosun and Babalola (2014) also described curriculum models as a framework on which a particular curriculum can be based to facilitate its development, implementation, evaluation, and innovation. It is of no doubt that every model has their focus, basic assumptions and structure as propagated by their proponents (McLarty, 2005). Basically, curriculum models are done through graphic representation and in different structures showing the interaction of the model components. According to Mysore (2003) there are several authors, there are various curriculum development models that have been proposed over the years, and while there are similarities among them, there are also significant differences. This provides a logical template to follow.

Tyler's model emphasizes defining objectives, selecting Subject Matter, and organizing Subject Matter in a logical and meaningful way. It is also called the simple linear and rational curriculum models (Kolb, 2007). Tyler's model, helps to identify the key features of a curriculum. Tyler's model for curriculum planning is known as a 'rational' curriculum model because it is simple to follow and identifies the key stages that need to be considered. This type of model tends to operate in a linear manner with aims and objectives, course Subject Matter, teaching methods and assessment and evaluation processes (Mattern, 2016). The objective model is very similar to Tyler's model, but the distinguishing feature is the evaluation process, in the objective model (Okolie, Igwe and Eneje, 2019a). This model assumes that the primary purpose of education is to transmit a fixed body of knowledge from teacher to student. It is more teacher-centered and focuses on mastery of specific Subject Matter. It emphasizes student-centered learning and the need to consider the learner's interests and experiences when developing curriculum. This model emphasizes the importance of identifying the learners' needs and interests, and then designing a curriculum to meet those needs (Franklin, 2021).

The cyclical models are helpful to adopt when the developers wish to include an evaluation feedback loop into the next iteration of the course (Abiodun, 2010). It follows a more 'ongoing' continuous process, they are more responsive to change as you go along and are less rigid than rational models. Whereas a spiral model adopts a cyclical format which still includes the key characteristics of rational models and movement from a low level to a higher level. Cyclical models follow a more 'ongoing' continuous process, they are more responsive to change as people go along and are less rigid than rational models (Heffernan, 2001). The spiral element of Bruner's model implies that the course Subject Matter may contain similar parameters and topics, but that course Subject Matter will increase in level of difficulty (Gbadamosi, 2018). The cyclical models, like Wheeler's model has additional feedback loop via 'evaluation' back into re-design. The Wheeler's model emphasizes the importance of student participation in the curriculum development process. It emphasizes the need for dialogue and feedback between students and teachers and the importance of incorporating students' experiences and perspectives into the curriculum.

Oliva's model emphasizes the need to consider the context in which the curriculum will be taught (Hessels and Naudé, 2019). This model focuses on analyzing the existing curriculum, identifying areas for improvement, and then developing a new curriculum that is more relevant and effective in the specific context. Walker and Dimmock's model emphasize the need to consider the larger social and cultural context in which the curriculum will be taught (Fry, Ketteridge and Marshall, 2009). It emphasizes the importance of addressing issues of social justice and equity in curriculum development. The constructivist model is based on the principles of constructivism, which emphasize the importance of active learning and student-centered instruction. It includes four main steps: construction of knowledge, construction of meaning, construction of understanding, and construction of action (Joy and Kolb, 2009). The dynamic models are more open models and are valuable in taking situational analyses and where the curriculum is situated, into account (Keating, Rishel and Byles, 2005). Overall, the main similarity between these models is the focus on developing a curriculum that meets the needs of learners. The main differences lie in the emphasis on different factors, such as teacher-centered vs. student-centered learning, the importance of context, and the need to address broader social issues (Bamber and Hankin, 2011).

For this study, the Kerr's curriculum model will be used in the design phase because Kerr (1968) emphasised on how the objective means that the students will encounter behavioural change after learning; these changes included perception, affection, and skills. Also, Kerr's model, focused on experiential learning, Kerr's learning experience also depicted the interactive effect between the learners and various environmental elements. However, Skilbeck (1984) and Kolawole (2015) do propose that initiation of a needs assessment analysis is crucial as the entry point for curriculum development this study will also conduct a need assessment in order to assess where undergraduates are in terms of the skills they possess prior to the introduction of this study and to also investigate their awareness of service-learning.

Nonetheless, due to the problem of inefficient supply of labour, lack of experiential learning which has posed serious and variety of implications on graduates employability and entrepreneurship, some previous studies have focused research on enhancing university graduate employability in Nigeria (Pitan, 2016); using service-

learning to enhance employability skills in graduate business capstones (Wickam, 2018); why higher education institutions have problems with teaching generic skills (Okolie, Igwe, Nwosu, Eneje, Mlanga, 2019); evaluation of the entrepreneurship education curriculum (Sangoleye, 2018); attitude of students towards entrepreneurship (Adeleye, 2019); skills mismatch among graduates and labour market requirements (Pitan and Adedeji, 2012); perception of employers on graduates' employability (Damoah, Peprah and Brefo, 2021) among others. However, none of these studies focused on developing a service-learning curriculum to promote experiential learning in Nigeria. Hence, this study will develop (design, validate, trial test, and give report of the outcome) of the effectiveness of a service-learning curriculum to enhance undergraduates' employability and entrepreneurship skills.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The goal of Nigerian graduates is to secure a decent job or become an employer of labour after university education. However, to attain this goal, graduates need to be able to exhibit relevant employability and entrepreneurship skills. Although, entrepreneurship education has been introduced into university curriculum as a compulsory course through the General Education Studies (GES) programme to equip graduates with these skills, yet employers reveal that graduates lack relevant 21st century skills (conflict resolution, self-management, strategic-thinking, problem-solving, decision-making, ICT literacy among others) needed and demanded in the global workplace.

However, scholars like Pitan (2016), Sangoleye (2018) and Gbadamosi (2022) have carried out several studies on perception of employers on graduates' employability, attitude of students towards entrepreneurship, skills mismatch among graduates, evaluation of university entrepreneurship among others. Still, efforts have not been focused on how universities can actively engage and predispose graduates to the acquisition of 21st-century employability and entrepreneurship skills through active engagements in blended (classroom and out-of-class) activities and experiential learning. Therefore, the focus of this study is to develop a service-learning curriculum (design, validate, trial test, and give a report of the outcome) to predispose undergraduates to the

acquisition of 21st-century employability and entrepreneurship skills needed in the competitive global market.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The study set out to:

1. Investigate the level of undergraduates' awareness of employability skills
2. Examine the level of undergraduates' awareness of entrepreneurship skills.
3. Ascertain the extent to which stakeholders (human resource managers and entrepreneurs) opinions on graduates' possession of employability skills justify the need for a service-learning curriculum.
4. Investigate the extent to which the formulated objectives in the service-learning curriculum dedicated to Employability and Entrepreneurship (EES) foster the acquisition of vital skills among undergraduates.
5. Examine the perception of stakeholders on the Subject Matter of the service-learning curriculum to enhance EES.
6. Aggregate the perception of undergraduates on the extent to which the objectives of the service-learning curriculum promote EES
7. Ascertain observers' assessment of the effectiveness of the service-learning curriculum in fostering Employability and Entrepreneurship Skills (EES) among undergraduate students.
8. Examine the perception of undergraduates on their learning outcomes in the service-learning curriculum after trial testing

1.4 Research Questions

This study provides answers to the following research questions.

1. What is the level of undergraduates' awareness of employability skills?
2. What is the level of undergraduates' awareness of entrepreneurship skills?

3. To what extent would the opinion of stakeholders (human resource managers and entrepreneurs) on graduates' possession of employability skills justify the need for a service-learning curriculum?
4. To what extent do the formulated objectives in the service-learning curriculum dedicated to Employability and Entrepreneurship (EES) foster the acquisition of vital skills among undergraduates?
5. What is the perception of stakeholders on the Subject Matter of the service-learning curriculum to enhance EES?
6. What is the perception of undergraduates on the extent to which the objectives of the service-learning curriculum promote EES?
7. What assessments do observers make regarding the effectiveness of the service-learning curriculum in fostering Employability and Entrepreneurship Skills (EES) among undergraduate students?
8. What is the perception of undergraduates on their learning outcomes in the service-learning curriculum after trial testing?

1.5 Scope of the Study

The research utilized a four-phase (need assessment, design, validate, and trial-test) to achieve the stages involved in developing a service-learning curriculum for undergraduates in southwestern Nigeria Universities. The study covered undergraduates and some stakeholders (human resource managers, entrepreneurs, service-learning experts, and curriculum experts).

1.6 Significance and Importance of the Study

This study is expected to be of great value to undergraduates because it would expose them to necessary areas associated with the development of employability and entrepreneurship skills. It would equip students with real practical experience that would aid acquisition of valuable skills. It would provide undergraduates with hard, soft, and transferable skills needed in addressing the issues of quality supply of labour and poor attitude to entrepreneurship. This study would open ways through which various stakeholders in the job market such as human resources managers, entrepreneurs, students, and employers could actively participate as contributors in both the development and implementation phases of a service-learning curriculum to bring out the

best in the 21st century graduates through exposure to variant skills and experiential learning. In addition, this study is expected to enlighten educators better on the benefits of a service-learning curriculum. Its benefits would be extended to the instructor, prospective employers, the university, and the community at large. This study hopes to be considered significant because it involved various partakers in the global job market such as human resource personnel, entrepreneurs and employers who had first-hand information on employability and entrepreneurship skills which was very useful in the curriculum development and implementation process. This study is expected to contribute to the fields of curriculum development and service-learning, providing a valuable resource for both students and researchers in future references.

1.7 Operational Definitions of Terms

The following terms were defined operationally:

Service-learning Curriculum: In this study, a service-learning curriculum is the totality of a planned educational course to equip undergraduates with employability and entrepreneurship skills to improve the quality of labour supply.

Undergraduates: This refers to tertiary institution students studying for their first degree in the university.

Efficacy: In this study, effectiveness of the curriculum was assessed at the point of trial testing and reflection.

21st Century Skills: In this study, these are the skills required of people to participate constructively in the world of work as well as to be active and engaged members of their communities and societies.

Employability Skills: In this study, this refers to the 21st-century soft skills required of a student upon graduation to get employment opportunities. These skills include critical-thinking, communication, problem-solving, collaboration, networking, leadership, information technology and emotional intelligence.

Entrepreneurship Skills: In this study, these are the 21st century skills set students are exposed to as rudiment knowledge of being a business owner or job creator. Such include, self-management, business management, strategic thinking, financial analysis, innovation among others.

Stakeholders: In this study, the stakeholders included, human resource managers, entrepreneurs, undergraduates, service-learning experts, and curriculum experts.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

Pertinent research was appraised under the subheadings of theoretical framework, review of concepts, empirical review and appraisal of literature review.

2.1 Theoretical Framework

2.1.1 Experiential Learning Theory

In year 1984, David Kolb, an American Educator formally published a 4-stage Action Learning Cycle which today forms the foundations of experiential learning. Experiential learning is a method of learning through direct experience, and it often leads to deep, long-lasting understanding and personal growth (Kolb and Kolb, 2011a). For example, students participating in outdoor education programmes or wilderness expeditions may develop a greater appreciation for nature and their own abilities, while team-building exercises in a corporate setting can lead to improved communication and collaboration among employees (Kolb and Kolb, 2009a). Experiential approaches have important benefits for learning and memory, especially for creative, inductive people who like exploring and more random inquiry. It is to be noted that even structured learners benefit by broadening their cognitive range and practicing more flexible thinking methods (Kolb and Kolb, 2011b). This is because there have been several instances of meaningful moments being created through experiential learning.

Figure 2.1: Kolb's Cycle of Experiential Learning

Source: Oyekanmi ((2021)

Additionally, some people report a sense of personal breakthrough or epiphany during certain kinds of therapy, self-help and personal growth workshops, retreats or immersion programmes which include experiential learning components (Kolb and Kolb, 2006a). Such moments can be impactful and long-lasting, which can lead to significant changes in a person's life. It is to be noted that personal experiences often prompt people to think about what happened, what they did and whether they can improve the next time something like this occurs (Kolb and Kolb, 2009a). Learners are more likely to learn from their mistakes, because if they get things right, they mostly do not stop to congratulate themselves on how brilliant they are. Hence, experiential learning can be an impactful experience as it will also invoke learners' emotions and feelings along with thinking, and even involving moving their bodies in certain ways (Kolb, 2007). For instance, learning new dance moves or conducting a skill you have never done before. In short, experiential learning methods promote wholistic learning, involving the whole person (Kolb and Kolb, 2011b).

The additional element of emotion makes experiential learning more memorable, and this can occasionally be traumatic for the learner (Kuh, 2008). It is relevant to this study. Experimental learning is all about grooming one's career's path by applying theoretical knowledge in practical situations (Kolb, 2007). John Dewey enumerated five aspects or approaches to the cycle of how people learn from experience: leap to a solution, changing the perplexity into a problem/question, using consecutive ideas to guide observation, mental elaboration of an idea, and testing the idea by overt or imaginative action. Many contemporary pedagogues made their curricula far too child-centered in Dewey's eyes, and he was alarmed that they claimed to be his followers (Kolb and Kolb, 2011a). He believed too many teachers minimized the importance of Subject Matter. Dewey's writings today are being ignored, while pedagogues think they are following his lead. Experiential learning is what is known as "learning by doing" and not just ingesting all the textbook knowledge there is (Kolb and Kolb, 2011c).

It is the exposure to real world tasks which are open to errors that are the best way to achieve this (Kolb, 2007). Mistakes are a necessary factor in this as learning from pushes growth from within. Experiential learning promotes intelligence and competitiveness in a student that textbook knowledge cannot. It makes the peer develop a

hard shell to real world experiences, even before being sent into the warzone, that instills in them the ability to work under any environment later in their lives/careers (Kolb and Kolb, 2011c). One may be surprised that it is stated in such cognitive terms, and that an idea is allowed to be tested in step 5 using imagination. Many teachers today push what they think is experiential learning but miss the mark. Perhaps, they read the term and think they automatically know what it means (hands-on! learning by doing) without having to bother to learn pedagogy beyond those few phrases (Kolb and Kolb, 2011b). One should not confuse motion with learning. Experiential learning should not be used as an excuse to teach less Subject Matter, but that is often what happens due to the teacher's thinking this pedagogy gives them the free pass (Kuh, 2008).

However, nearly all universities and institutional establishments nowadays require some sort of experiential education to occur along with academics (Okolie, Nwosu and Eneje, 2019c). The institute itself facilitates these opportunities through internships and placements as the academic terms progress. It is important to do one's research and decide on a university which avails opportunities of industry level exposure, such as visits and tours and seminars and guest lectures (Manring, 2012). Experiential Learning is learning by doing. The learner first collects facts, theories, and other forms of information from various sources, applies this information to real-life scenarios and analyses the effect. When concepts are learnt in this way, they become unforgettable. Experiential learning is also known as hands-on Learning (Abiodun, 2010). Thus, making students experience the concepts by doing them within the teaching-learning process is its aim (Mattern, 2016). E.g.: As a teacher, one is explaining the concept of conversion of energy in say grade four. After teaching the concept, you make students do an activity wherein they make an electric generator.

2.1.2 Human Capital Theory

Human capital theory is a concept used in human resource management that suggests that employees are assets to the organization and should be treated as such (Rowe, 2019). It emphasizes that investing in employees and their development can lead to higher productivity, better job satisfaction, and greater organizational success. The theory suggests that the quality and quantity of a company's human resources are directly

linked to its overall performance (Mattern, 2016). The theory proposes that when employers invest in their employees, they are creating a valuable resource that can be used to maximize profits. For example, if a business invests in employee training and development, they are giving their employees the skills and knowledge to effectively perform their jobs (Felicetti et al., 2013). This can lead to increased productivity and efficiency, which can then result in higher profits for the company.

Another example of human capital theory in practice is when an organization invests in employee engagement activities. These activities can include team building, communication training, and leadership development (Barot, 2015). By investing in these activities, the organization is creating an atmosphere where employees feel valued and motivated to do their best. This can lead to increased job satisfaction and performance, which can then result in higher profits for the company. Human capital theory is also applicable to the recruitment process, service-learning, experiential activities, and several others (Bender, 2005). When an organization invests in its recruitment process, it can attract the best talent for the job, ensuring that the organization is hiring the most qualified and capable people. This can then lead to higher employee retention, which can result in greater organizational success. Overall, human capital theory emphasizes the importance of investing in employees and their development (Pitan, 2016).

It suggests that investing in employees leads to increased productivity, job satisfaction, and organizational success (Jackson, 2012). The relationship and relevance of the two theories is positive because, undergoing experiential learning will yield positive labour market returns, better experience, and acquisition of relevant skills (Mattern, 2016). Human capital theory contends that education has a part to play in increasing the productivity of individuals. Hence, getting experiential education will also help in acquiring marketable skills and abilities relevant to job performance, and thus the more highly experienced people are, the more successful they will be in the workplace in terms of both income and opportunities (Akinbode and Oyelude, 2020). Therefore, the prompt for this study is to achieve an innovative experiential teaching that can aid the acquisition of these valuable skills needed for improvement in the quality of labour supply in the 21st century (Bamber and Hankin, 2011). The theory is relevant to this

study as helps to drive students' acquisition of competencies to make them functional in the world of jobs.

2.1.3 John Kerr's Model of Curriculum Design

John Kerr's curriculum model is highly interactive. Indicating the complexity of curricula and how planners need to understand the impact of each of the curricula components on each other (Berasategi, Alonso, and Roman, 2016). i.e. Changes to the - 'Objectives' – 'knowledge' – 'evaluation' or 'school learning environment' will, invariably, affect the others (Alsubaie, 2016). This could be viewed as a strength and weakness. For example, curriculum implementers may be reluctant to change one component because this may warrant a constant cycle of evaluation and change. That said, the existence of constant change renders the curriculum to be open and responsive when there is a need for immediate change.

Figure 2.2: A simplified version of Kerr's model of curriculum design

Source: Urebyu (1985)

2.2 Reviewal of Concepts

2.2.1 Concept of Service-learning

Service-learning is an educational approach that combines community service with academic learning (Bringle and Hatcher, 2000). Students engage in meaningful service projects that address real-world problems while also incorporating academic Subject Matter, reflection, and critical thinking (Carvalho and Yeoman, 2018). The benefits of service-learning in education include. The key to do service-learning is frequent practices in one's community in which one builds new habits and transforms oneself with family members, teachers, and classmates as these help on to bring on transferrable skills wherever one goes. It is to be noted that many community issues can be tackled with various types of service-learning activities (Care and Anderson, 2016). Service-learning experiences can be life-changing, helping one develop new skills, gain valuable experiences, and give back to the community. However, with any significant undertaking, it is crucial to exit the service-learning experience with grace and gratitude (Clevenger and Ozbek, 2013). These are just a few examples of service-learning activities one can take on.

Hence, service-learning is not about giving back, but developing oneself as a community member, developing intellectual, cultural, or social DNA's (habits) through service and learning, to benefit or change oneself and hence the community at large (Folgueiras, Luna, and Puig, 2013). One's role could be that one has spouse, parent, child, teacher, friend, lawyer, doctor, neighbour. Hence, there are service-learning opportunities any time wherever you are. Overall, service-learning can have a positive impact on both students and their communities, providing opportunities for students to learn and grow while also making a meaningful contribution to society. There is no recommended template for service community service. It is a fact that higher institutions are looking for students who do things without getting "credit for it" (Furco, 2001). This is because they enjoy being with, doing and helping people as well as gaining few ideas about the challenges and plausible solutions to their problems. Hence, it is said that such activities are better included in the school curriculum to get those people who are willing to get involved in experiential learning (Heffernan, 2001).

Service-learning is on the verge of producing global citizenship who are cultivating a non-judgmental attitude towards different races, religions, countries, and regions while learning and practising some foreign cultural norms (Folgueiras, Luna and Puig, 2013). Universities have an enormous amount of work to do as well. At least high schools have the benefit of being small and intimate with students on how to service the community. For instance, imagine all the people who could flourish and excel if they were just given a way to actively engage with material and exercise their natural curiosity and ambition (Salimbene, Buono, LaFarge and Nurick, 2005). It is no longer news that there is such a discrepancy between what the workforce needs and how higher institutions are responding (Sharifi, McCombs and Kattelus, 2003). This is because the world of jobs is shifting the paradigm in that one can take the same material and apply it to skill-based career training so that all and sundry can benefit. For instance, several math concepts can be taught in projects that require planning or building, like tiling or painting.

In the same vein, students relish problem-solving opportunities, and it just takes a little more planning on the part of school to offer opportunities for students to train for jobs they can do while attending higher education (Kezar, 2002). It is to be noted that businesses will often work with schools if asked to come up with ideas on how to prepare students for jobs when they graduate from the higher institutions. In addition, people underestimate how to tap in and turned on a student who can be if they show them how the information is applied (Furco, 2001). Scholars have affirmed that there are a few different methods one can use to evaluate service-learning experience of students, and the best one depends on the planned goals and objectives (Franklin, 2021).

2.2.2 Importance of Service-Learning

The following are importance of service-learning.

Civic Engagement: Service-learning allows students to become involved and invested in their communities. Working with community partners teaches students about their community's needs and assets, as well as how to collaborate to effect positive change (Tomlinson, 2017).

Academic Enhancement: Service-learning can help students grasp academic subjects better and give them the opportunity to apply what they've learned in real-world

circumstances (Yorke and Knight, 2006). Hands-on learning can help students improve their critical thinking, problem-solving, and communication abilities.

Personal Growth: Service-learning can help students grow personally by giving them the opportunity to build empathy, leadership, and a feeling of social responsibility (Abiodun, 2010). Students may also have a better awareness of their own talents and shortcomings, as well as how they may help their community (Ambrose, Bridges, DiPietro, Lovett, and Norman, 2010).

Career Preparation: Service-learning can give students valuable experience and skills that will help them improve their resumes and prepare them for future employment (Bender, Daniels, Lazarus, Naude, and Sattar, 2006). Through their community activity, students may also get insight into potential career routes and make professional relationships (Barot, 2015).

Figure 2.3: Four steps involved in Service-Learning

Source: Quest International in Wayne-Westland Community School Service-Learning Curriculum Guide (2006-2007)

2.2.3 Concept and Importance of the 21st Century Skills

Skill is a special ability in a task or ability acquired by training (Care and Anderson, 2016). It is the knowledge and ability that enables one to do something well. In this challenging world, having skills is an added advantage when it comes to searching for and getting jobs. The 21st century skills include creativity, adaptability, communication, teamwork, leadership, good knowledge about computer languages, knowing different languages, multi-tasking, Self-confidence among others (Abiodun, 2010). It is to be noted that people could have either one skill or multiple skills as there are a lot of advantages to it. According to (Binkley, Erstad, Herman, Raizen, Ripley, Miller-Ricci, and Rumble, 2012), 21st century skills increase confidence to do work related to our skills; less training is required to further improve your acquired skill in the workplace; increase employment opportunities; help in growing careers, drive multiple streams of income, and make people interesting as individuals. In the twentieth century, children learnt home economics, including how to cook, fix clothing, and handle their finances. Thus, cooking and financial management have given way to soft skills such as social interaction, teamwork, and so on.

According to UNESCO (2020), there are listed skills such as self-management, conflict resolution, capacity for lifelong learning, among others. The 21st century has led to the establishment of the new world order which requires new skills for existence like critical thinking, collaboration, problem-solving, and data analysis (Kivunja, 2014b). To empower the future generations with these skills the teachers will have to reinvent and upskill themselves (Pitan, 2017). Further, the new world order hinges on technology, which is the greatest enabler, hence the teachers need to be equipped with all these skills such as coaching, mentoring and motivating the others, identifying the strengths of team members, and giving and receiving constructive feedback. Damoah, Peprah and Brefo (2021) stated in the era of industrialization, it was important for workers to be able to accumulate knowledge and repetitive actions, to follow instructions. But modern conditions require completely different skills. Now, people have all the chances to step into the new day with the skills that will be useful in it. Campus Compact (2013) remarked that to get a job nowadays, there need to take in consideration those main skills.

2.2.4 Traditional Methods of Teaching in Higher Education

Teachers tend to teach using the methods their teachers used to teach them (Akinbode, and Oyelude, 2020). This is because innovation in teaching methods has been slow in coming, and many people find university teacher preparatory programmes to be severely lacking in fixing this problem in higher education depend largely on memorization and instruction (Bender, 2005). The traditional teaching methods in higher education are generally teacher-directed, one where learners are taught in a manner that is conducive to sitting and listening. Today, scholars in education systems prefer student-centred methods while modern teaching methods focus on understanding and exploration. As Kivunja (2014) stated that teachers who participate professional learning communities are likely to deploy various strategies in the teaching and learning in higher education. It is an avenue in which teachers from each subject meet to decide what was going to be taught on each day, when the tests will be going on, and even how each lesson would be taught (Damoah, Peprah and Brefo. 2021).

Sometimes, in one school, the PLC would assign each member to write lessons and then share idea. Doing so, people learn different techniques and activities. It has been tagged teachers' involvement in curriculum implementation (Ambrose, Bridges, DiPietro, Lovett, and Norman, 2010). Though, every school is different, and also every student. Thus, making every school and student do the same thing does not work in terms of service-learning and associated engagements.

Table 2.1: Differences between traditional and service-learning

Traditional Learning	Service-Learning
Theory	Theory and Experience
Other People's Knowledge	Personal Knowledge
Spectator	Participant
Individual Learning	Cooperative Learning
Separation of Instructor and Learner	The Line Between Teacher and Learner is Blurred
Answer	Questions and Answer
Assurance of Outcomes	Heterogeneous Outcomes
Avoiding Ignorance	Ignorance a Resource
Objectivist Epistemology	Connected Epistemology

Source: Stacey, Rice, and Langer (2001) adapted Howard (1993).

2.2.5 Integrating, Implementing and Institutionalising Service-Learning into Higher Education Curriculum

Education does not only mean learning something useful for career, but it is also about learning something useful for personality development (Bamber and Hankin, 2011). The meaning of education in this purely technic-oriented world is where there is not much importance given to etiquette. People act in a decent manner, but people do not empathize anymore with peers or any human (Bender, 2005).

A well-structured curriculum is properly planned and designed. This is because the actual curriculum should reflect the 'intended curriculum' (Bringle and Hatcher, 2000). The curriculum should state its purpose, and what its main aims are. Thus, it is expected that setting learning outcomes should help to clarify the curriculum Subject Matter and how students will learn about subjects and skills (Boateng and Ofori-Sarpong, 2002). In the same vein, the assessment strategy should be valid, reliable and test what was stated at the outset. There should also be evidence of how the curriculum is to be evaluated and reformed as needed. The whole purpose of the design or model of curriculum chosen is to plan a curriculum (Alsubaie, 2016). Thus, using any of these models will steer the curriculum planning group to structure the curriculum in a particular way for which it should be. This is because, if a curriculum is well-designed, then its development and implementation should follow as a matter of course (Babalola, Amosun, and Kolawole, 2014). A good design will make it easier to plan for success.

The importance of curriculum implementation is the significant improvement of pedagogy, only because such implementation would help students learn more effectively while curriculum evaluation involves planning, developing and using some sort of evaluative method to see if the curriculum, as designed and implemented, is achieving what was intended (Babalola, 2019). Thus, integrating service-learning into the curriculum requires a successful and advance planned among the tripartite arrangement. By implication, professionals develop materials and courses to enable this process some of which could be textbooks, tests, lectures, community engagement and industrial relation. Integrating service-learning into higher education curriculum could take any of the three below.

Vertical integration: Same-subject lessons from one grade level to the next are coordinated and, in theory, seamless and scaffolded (Huang and Yang, 2004). It is not uncommon for middle school teachers to teach the same subject for three different grade levels; 6, 7, and 8. It is also not uncommon for textbook companies to align their textbooks for these grades so that the page numbers for various lessons are in sync across the grade levels (Yuan and Huang, 2000). If, for example, there is a lesson on possessive pronoun usage, that lesson will be the same page number in the 6th, 7th, and 8th grade textbooks. It makes planning that much easier.

Horizontal Integration: This is when different subjects of the same grade are coordinated (Kivunja, 2014b). For example, if the English teacher reads a Shakespearean Play while the Social Studies teacher is teaching a unit on Elizabethan England, that is horizontal integration. Typically, English and Social Studies are easy to integrate, and math and science are easy to integrate (Kolb and Kolb, 2009b). Entire-grade-level integration among all subjects is one of those things that administrators like to talk about happening over the summer and, by the second week of school, the teachers have given up on it, because it is not worth it.

2.2.6 Service-Learning Curriculum Models

Pure service-learning, undergraduate community-based action research, service internship, capstone courses, problem-based service-learning, and discipline-based service-learning, are the curriculum models according to Heffernan (2001).

Pure Service-Learning

This is the typical arrangement between the community, school, and industry for addressing difficulties and challenges in a collaborative manner.

Undergraduate Community-Based Action Research

Community action is frequently required to eliminate established interests, mainly governmental interests, that are anti-community. Prepare, implement, and lead are the three pillars of a community-based action plan. Community action research focuses on addressing real-world problems and difficulties, as well as developing practical answers and recommendations for change (Yorke and Knight, 2006). In contrast, community action research often involves collaboration between researchers, practitioners, and members of the community, with the objective of enabling the community to address and solve problems (Skilbeck and Connell 2004). Community action research, on the other hand, is generally undertaken by researchers or practitioners from outside the community and focuses on concerns or problems that affect a larger community or society. The community action research focuses a major emphasis on participation; however the extent of participation and roles of different stakeholders differ.

In community action research, however, engagement is often more extensive and includes members of the community as well. When an indigenous group is isolated, survival-critical modifications in behavior or technology are required to help the community overcome those challenges (Tomlinson, 2017). These are examples of community-based innovations. Traditional action research is often characterized by a cyclical process of planning, acting, observing, and reflecting. The researcher (or research team) finds a problem or issue that needs to be addressed and then devises a strategy to handle it. This could entail applying modifications in a particular practice, program, or policy, and then observing the results of these changes. The researcher then reflects on the results of their actions and considers what they have learned from the process (Skilbeck and Connell 2004). They may make further changes, refine their approach, or decide to implement a new strategy based on their findings. The process is often iterative, with multiple cycles of planning, acting, observing, and reflecting (Mysore, 2003).

One major benefit that comes from local research is that it addresses issues like poverty, economic challenges, gender equity, education, living conditions, and housing (Nwankwo, 2012). Local solutions lead to more awareness among officials about what is really happening in their communities instead of assumptions based on demographics or

stereotypes. Also, engaging residents in decision-making processes give them skills because they are given opportunities for empowerment through problem-solving or leadership positions like volunteering or participating on committees or boards (Olagoke-Oladokun, Mokhtar, Gbadamosi and Dugguh, 2020). It also encourages involvement with institutions like schools and social service agencies which can offer long-term benefits like career development opportunities (Onuoha, and Okam, 2011).

Service Internship

A service internship is a formal program that an employer offers to potential workers. Service interns work for a corporation either part-time or full-time for a set length of time. Service internships are particularly popular with undergraduate or graduate students who work for one to four months and want to get practical work or research experience while simultaneously giving value to the community (Salimbene, Buono, LaFarge, and Nurick, 2005). It gives a student both on-the-job experiences to add to their resume and a sense of what it would be like to work in a given industry on a daily basis (Passarelli, and Kolb, 2012). Because service internship is the first professional exposure, it has various advantages, including the opportunity to work under the supervision of specialists; it works as a bridge between the theory learned and the practice that exists (Pitan, 2016). It is a springboard into the professional world; it teaches workplace ethics; it is the best way for newcomers to grow their network; and it helps to discover one's interests, allowing one to choose the correct career route. It is also profitable. According to Sharifi, McCombs, Kattelus (2003) and Abiodun (2010), changes in undergraduate major after a service internship are often in the 20%-33% range. Service interns typically work with the organization for a set period of time ranging from three to twelve months. It is expected that service internship should inculcate practical skills, workplace experience, teamwork, better understanding of the industry etc (Akinyemi, Aimm, Igot and Ikuenomore, 2012). Many profiles involve interaction with the vendors, clients, competitors, branding professionals etc.

In addition to it, service interns get an opportunity to represent brand in varied forums like exhibitions, trade fairs, seminars, workshops, dealers/distributors meet etc. which gives them fee of the real-world business (Ambrose, Bridges, DiPietro, Lovett and

Norman, 2010). Several companies offer paid internships as well, wherein interns get minimum wages to meet their daily expenditure. This helps service intern by not burdening him or her with overheads like transport, room rent etc. On the other hand, this also ensures seriousness amongst the service interns towards the assigned task or responsibility (Bamber and Hankin, 2011).

It is to be noted that several companies generally assign one mentor to the service interns who join them. This becomes the responsibility of the mentor to guide, train, educate and upskill the students to equip them with requisite tools that will further help them to achieve the set target/goal. Once trained, the students are assigned dedicated tasks and open workplace with a set target which gives them exposure of real time work hurdles and broadens their knowledge as they overcome all the challenges faced. Service internship also inculcates the spirit of ‘working in a team’ (Bender, 2005). A service internship helps people to know the practical implementation of the tasks that need to be followed according to their job portfolio (Berasategi, Alonso, and Roman, 2016). It allows people to understand their weaknesses and strengths in managing the work and confidence in executing their work correctly. It also increases their chances of getting a job as they have got the experience of practical knowledge in their field of employment.

Capstone Courses

Capstone ideas have been around for some 4000 years now. By implication, every time some bright young engineer, architect, politician, or high priest comes around with a “new idea” for capstones, the masons grin, turn their heads and smile while they cash ever-larger paychecks (Bringle and Hatcher, 2000). It is a final year course (often a project) which essentially completes the degree and demonstrates capability across the subject rather than just a single module (Bender, Daniels, Lazarus, Naude and Sattar,2006). Capstone courses is the true higher institution class experience. In general, capstone courses are supposed to do one of two things: demonstrate that one has mastered his or her undergraduate Subject Matter; provide one with an academic experience that ‘caps-off’ one’s education. For example, it is common for chemical engineering students to be put into a small group and required to design a plant as a team, then do detailed design of parts as individuals, utilizing skills from all years of the course and working in

a non-exam situation (Alsubaie, 2016). By implication, this means that one must learn to use a dictionary, paper or online.

Thus, one can improve one's vocabulary by looking for words and keeping a list of new words to learn, which one then review from time to time until one can cross them off list. Boateng and Ofori-Sarpong (2002) remarked that students are immersed in a higher institution experience where they can work on their 'capstone' in a class setting where they focus their time on this project. It is essential for teamwork building, writing, and research. The idea here is to provide a unique higher institution experience that ultimately prepares one for the world of jobs (Bringle and Hatcher, 2000). The reality is that this is higher education tasks which are research and seminar. Capstone allows one to research and discover something that affects one in everyday lives (Berasategi, Alonso and Roman, 2016). The Capstone course is ideally a course that is conducted at the end of the curriculum. It provides the students with the opportunity to use the knowledge they have gained through the course and assess it by trying the knowledge in a project or specific assignments.

For example, at the end of a multi-facet business specialization, there would be capstone that would require students to formulate a business strategy and address all the key business areas covered in the specialization through a project or business simulation setup (Care and Anderson, 2016). This is something students are personally interested in, so they must spend the time on it. It is something that has a distinct phased structure of planning, execution, evaluation. It could also be at the beginning, middle or the end. The goal is that the student will have a project that they researched and solved individually (much like a bachelor's or master's capstone/thesis (Bringle and Hatcher, 2000). This will allow the student to distinguish themselves from just completing projects. The student can then demonstrate their knowledge synthesis and integration skills for the project which will provide them with a response to the common interview question "tell me a project that you recently worked on" (Berasategi, Alonso and Roman, 2016). The student can discuss how they approached the problem, solved it, could have made it better, and likely have ample information about the related packages and software used since they will be debugging, writing code, and parameter tuning by themselves.

Problem Based Service-Learning

Problem-based service-learning does have definite advantages, particularly if the goal of learning is to approach and solve similar problems (Evans, Gbadamosi, Wells, and Scott, 2012). There are skills that cannot be sharpened for practical use, by simply lecturing. For instance, information acquisition and filtration, for instance. However, designing problem-based service-learning interventions can be hard, and there is probably not a rigorous method that is applied strictly to assess the efficiency of these interventions. The designer or developer needs to have a deep, rational, and clear understanding of the skills the learners must apply and must be able to appropriately rescale and re-represent the problem for classroom use (Damoah, Peprah and Brefo, 2021). The facilitator who is delivering the intervention needs to be competent enough to probe students with appropriate questions (avoiding leading questions) to steer them to a ‘discovery’ in the true sense. Both these responsibilities are hard to carry out, which is why most problem-based service-learning implementations do not reach their goal (Clevenger and Ozbek, 2013).

Problem-based service-learning is basically a learning methodology followed by an active students’ group which revolves around strategies like learning by doing and self-paced learning (Deakin, Goldspink and Foster, 2013). It involves many students, but others may feel disengaged because of not being able to perform this type of exercise for a variety of reasons. Problem-based service-learning is fundamental to problem-solving (at least as when taught strategically), which is a core skill required for the 21st Century (every version of those skills seen includes problem-solving, critical thinking, analysis skills, and creativity (Dagenais, Hawley and Lund, 2003). Additionally, experiential learning shares a lot of the same philosophical ideas with problem-based service-learning and it will likely prove to be critical to 21st century skills, especially when applied in the context of a problem-solving methodology (Crocì, 2016).

Figure 2.4 Service-learning Curriculum models

Source: Heffernan (2001)

2.2.7 Need for Service-Learning Curriculum to Enhance Students' Employability and Entrepreneurship Skills

Service-learning is a credit-bearing educational opportunity in which students participate in an organized service project that addresses identified on- and off-campus community issues. Furthermore, it serves an important role in bridging academic studies and volunteer community service in mutually reinforcing ways, thereby improving students' employability and entrepreneurship abilities. Its significance and necessity cannot be overstated. This is due to the importance of higher education in the economic development of a country. This means that through effective teaching and learning, higher education graduates are expected to gain appropriate information and skills for employment and job creation. Service-learning is thus an educational pathway that aids in the consolidation of learning through reflective self-examination (Dunlap, 2006; Petkus, 2000) and provides students with autonomy and responsibility. It also fosters a sense of competence, self-efficacy, improved social relationships, and sound interconnections (Billig, 2010), and it provides students with a sense of wellbeing at work.

Service-learning additionally offers an educative methodology that engages students and communities in a mutual interdisciplinary development process and facilitates access to knowledge (Tiger and Parker, 2011; Kenworthy, Ren and Peterson, 2005; Mpofu, 2007; AlRashid and Walker, 2004; Conway, Amel, and Gerwien, 2009). It builds social capital (Laura, 2014), combats poverty (Ebrahim, 2012), instills fairness in pupils (Heffernan, 2001), promotes social justice (Wang and Rodgers, 2006), and makes students more altruistic (Hegarty and Angelidis, 2015).

Because it employs a teaching learning process centered on justice and social commitment, the adoption of service-learning by educational institutions is one strategy to establish a fairer and more sustainable society (Gaete, 2011). As a result, Gaete considers service-learning to be a cuttingedge transformational tool. It has influence over people, changing their attitudes, actions, and behaviors, and it is a human resource. When it is integrated thematically into the courses, it becomes a tool for societal sustainability and focuses individuals on their issues (Cheese and Hills, 2016; Dmochowski et al, 2016). According to Bringle and Hatcher (1995), institutions should expand service-learning through direct curriculum building. These authors believe that there are numerous ways to implement it, including community involvement, personal advocacy

for an issue, political engagement and activism, and experience in related pedagogies (Bringle and Hatcher, 1995: 112). However, they stated that service-learning might include topics with greater sensitivity and susceptibility to ethics and service practice, using social work as an example. It should be mentioned that service-learning cannot be confined to a discipline because it is reflective, interactive, collaborative, and humanitarian learning, emphasizing the relevance of ethics in the process.

The development of planning is important for the institutionalization of the philosophy of service-learning due to some factors such as common vocabulary, academic integrity, stronger backing and confidence, institutionalization (Bringle and Hatcher, 1995: 113), and the service-learning should be established within the characteristics of the institution's culture (Heffernan, 2001). As a result, it should be adequately prepared and integrated into the courses because it improves the altruism and pedagogy indexes (Hoffernan, 2001). It also improves and makes life more enjoyable for students' and organizations' performance and for taking responsibility for good citizenship (Dunlap, 2006; Petkus, 2000) since, as an experience learning process, service-learning encourages acts such as course planning, design, organization, implementation, and evaluation (Petkus, 2000). Service-learning should also be used as a tool for preuniversity teaching, which would include rewriting study programs and redefining educational institutions' missions (Appelbaum *et al*, 2017).

Despite the initial effort required to use this methodology, it promotes the sustainability of human life by creating a more sensitive society to communal goods, while the macro threshold for every person. As a result, sustainability challenges should be formally included into academic curricula, as they must occur within companies and in every moment of individuals' lives (Rusinko, 2010; Dmochowski *et al*, 2016)

2.2.8 Developing a Service-Learning Curriculum for Experiential Learning in Higher Education

Service-learning is a pedagogical conciliation method that fosters collaboration, mutual respect, interpersonal relationships, and attempts to build a bridge between universities, students, and the community (Petracchi *et al*, 2010). It addresses education from an experiential standpoint and provides a platform that bridges across numerous

fields, courses, and degrees of education by several universities globally (Yorio and Ye, 2012). It enables the reconciliation of school practices with community work and improves citizens' abilities and civic obligations (Andrews, 2007). It embodies diverse branches of personal and social enrichment, such as civic responsibility, social cohesion, community development, and a sense of happiness throughout the learning and teaching processes, as well as being an active molecule within the community. It uses human intelligence to combine relational, emotional, intellectual, spiritual, interpersonal, and intrapersonal intelligence. In this light, it is a viable option for humanizing higher education and society in general. This humanization process can help to materialize a new culture in which businesses become more connected to individuals and society. It may also encourage businesses to become more active in social programs, as well as to assume and implement entrepreneurial and social responsibility.

2.2.9 Benefits and Challenges of Implementing a Service-Learning Curriculum

Nonetheless, the most dominant challenge for all students in completing their service-learning projects experiences are enormous. However, the following are some of the challenges. The demands for implementing a service-learning curriculum range from spiraling costs due to over administration and an "arms race" to provide the most non-essential services to the community population (Buchanan, Baldwin and Rudisill, 2002). There is the challenge of administrative decisions to cut costs. Higher education has a fundamentally flawed business model! The most common problems faced by college students are ragging, adapting to university environment, problem of adjustment in starting all over again, making new friends. There is misinformation about the advantages of a university education and service-learning (Care and Anderson, 2016). There is lack of honesty about what university learning means; students pretend to study while instructors pretend to reward them for performance that usually does not exist. There is overemphasis on professional training; underemphasis on real education. Carvalho and Yeoman (2018) stated that preparing students for a career that is ahead seems a terrible disservice. Clevenger and Ozbek (2013) noted that there has been teaching supply chain for over 20 years to both graduate and undergraduate business students and the biggest problem of all higher education is that they have the wrong customer. Several universities

believe that the customer is the student, but the students are the product - the customer is the employer that hires the students (Cooper, Orrell and Bowden, 2010).

2.2.10 Acceptability and Effectiveness of a Curriculum

Dagenais, Hawley, and Lund (2003) stated that although it is important to assess the effectiveness of programs, courses, and teaching methods to ensure that goals are being achieved, but it is very difficult to evaluate the impact of fundamental changes in a whole curriculum. Casamassimo (1990) explained that the major reason for assessing the effectiveness of a curriculum is to find out how you are doing in doing what you do. He believed that the proponents of change need to be reassured that the right decision was made. The effectiveness of a new curriculum should be measured against a standard which is usually the old curriculum. To run an ideal educational trial, incoming classes can be randomly surveyed using questionnaires because they are widely used as curriculum assessment tools since they provide a lot of information rapidly, at a small cost, and with minimal staff involvement (Dagenais, Hawley, and Lund, 2003).

They explained that Likert-type with three to seven response categories can be used. Responses take the form of “strongly agree” to “strongly disagree,” “very well prepared” to “very poorly prepared,” “extremely useful” to “extremely useless,” and “unsatisfactory” to “excellent. However, scholars have stated that the effectiveness of a curriculum cannot be measured using a single evaluation method because no one tool can capture all the information required. Several methods and groups of observers are needed to provide a more global perspective on the entire curriculum. Hence, this study will make use of participants' perception scale and observers' rating scale to evaluate the effectiveness of this curriculum and to minimize the use of financial resources.

2.3 Empirical Review

2.3.1 Studies on Curriculum Development and Design

Curriculum design and development has a large and complex scope. According to Kolawole (2015), curriculum development involves making decisions aimed at designing learning activities that enable students to reach their maximum potential. Babalola (2019) also stated that building a curriculum is a process that integrates educational ambitions as well as values in the construction, application, and evaluation of tangible outputs.

Babalola went on to say that a model is the greatest way to understand the process and ideas of curriculum development. A model in curriculum development, on the other hand, is the framework utilized in establishing standards for the components of the proposed curriculum. Stenhouse (1975) defined a curriculum as an endeavor to express the key concepts and features of an educational proposal in such a form that it is subject to critical scrutiny and capable of effective translation into practice, according to Kolawole, Amosun, and Babalola (2014). One of the process model's key assumptions is that learning is obtained through work and life experience (experiential learning).

This style of learning consists of open-ended student activities that foster the development of tendencies and capacities. It focuses on the quality of learning as it occurs rather than on predefined results. The aim of this technique is to improve students' ability to look at experience in new ways outside of the classroom. Nwokocha (2019) also defined curriculum development as a process that engages essential stakeholders in the creation of a well-conceived tool to curb vices and enlighten society on values. He went further to say that building a successful curriculum is a methodical process that should engage all essential stakeholders and end-users. This is done to gather feedback from those whose lives will be directly impacted by the curriculum. As a result, UNESCO (2005) recommends that bodies and authorities tasked with establishing school curricula ensure that the process is as participatory as feasible.

2.3.2 Studies on Competencies Expected in Service-Learning Curriculum

A study on "Student Professional Competencies as Perceived by Community Service-Learning Partners" was conducted by Maureen Snow, Andrade Jonathan, Westover A., and Westover Utah (2017). The study looked into community partners' assessments of students' professional competencies and their influence. The descriptive survey design was used for the investigation. Bivariate and multivariate analyses, including correlations, ANOVA and ANCOVA techniques, and cross-tabulations, were used to analyze the data. The study also used Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression to test three models examining the impact of student professional competencies on the community partner's perceived quality of the project, the community partner's perceived value of the student project, and the community partner's perceived likelihood to work on

future projects with students. Professional competencies were found to have a substantial impact on partner perceptions of project quality and value, while the overall predictability of the model to analyze partners' perceived propensity to work on future projects with students was poor due to their ineptitude. As a result, the study recommended that students be permitted to engage in experiential learning in order to become more competent.

Ejiwale (2013) also conducted research as well on how leadership skills can be developed through service-learning. The research looked at the forms, assessment, and importance of service-learning in STEM programs, as well as how it might help participants develop their leadership skills. The study's findings revealed that involving students in service-learning has a higher payback than previously thought. Students in STEM programs who participated in service-learning increased their leadership qualities, as evidenced by company comments. Students can gain problem solving, critical thinking, public speaking, and interpersonal skills by participating in service-learning. Through effective feedback, the establishment of learning communities in service-learning helped to develop communication, team building, and leadership skills.

2.3.3 Studies on the Need for Service-Learning Curriculum to Enhance Students' Employability and Entrepreneurship Skills

Orlando, and Costa (2019) did research on "Service-learning: Benefits of a Different Learning Pedagogy." The paper considers the significance of teaching learning approach based on Service-learning and explores the importance of including it in the academic curriculum. The study used a qualitative data gathering and analysis approach, specifically group interviews with Subject Matter analysis. The group interviews were performed utilizing a semi structured interview script, with two Focus Groups, one with six elements and the other with five. The study's findings revealed that, because the university plays a key role in a nation's economic and social growth. It might be the connecting point between institutions and the community, and service-learning is a critical tool for achieving this goal. As a result, the study stated that service-learning is a global pedagogy that should be disseminated and applied to all areas of knowledge. With

service-learning, information spreads and excels in ongoing and dynamic interpersonal relationships among all participants in the teaching learning process and the community.

"Using Service-Learning to Enhance Employability Skills in Graduate Business Capstones: A Dissertation Overview," by Wickam (2012), was a study. The study's goal was to see if including service-learning into capstone courses improves students' development of employability skills. A nonexperimental, mixed-methods comparative research was used in this research. The top three employability skills improved by service-learning were decision-making processes, presentation skills, and collaboration; only presentation skills differed significantly between students whose capstone included service-learning and those who did not. The study's findings reveal an alignment between collaborative learning skills required by employers and those increased through service-learning, as well as that the instructor's participation in project structuring is critical to learning, establishing a demand for service-learning inclusion in university curricula.

2.3.4 Studies on Level of Awareness of Employability and Entrepreneurship Skills

Ugwu and Ezeani (2012) carried out a study on the evaluation of entrepreneurial awareness and skills among library and information science students in South East Nigerian universities. The objective of this research was to investigate the level of entrepreneurship awareness of skills and characteristics of an entrepreneur, LIS entrepreneurship opportunities created by information and communications technology (ICT), LIS modern and entrepreneurship skills, problems associated with entrepreneurship and skills in LIS, and strategies for improving entrepreneurship awareness and skills in Library and Information Sciences. The descriptive survey design was used, and one hundred and ten (110) final year and master's students from the departments of library and information science at the two universities were sampled on purpose with a researcher-structured questionnaire. Data was analyzed using frequency tables, means, and simple percentages. According to the study's findings, up to 70% of students were unaware of the entrepreneurship skills and prospects available in Library and Information Science. Furthermore, due to insufficient education and training, these kids have yet to build a culture and mindset toward entrepreneurship. As a result, the

study suggested that entrepreneurial courses and practical training in many parts of ICT be added to the Library and Information Science curriculum.

Nwabueze, Ifeanyichukwu, Nwankpa, and Lawrence (2021) carried out a study in rivers state, Nigeria, on undergraduate students' awareness and exploitation of entrepreneurial abilities and opportunities in business education. The study investigated undergraduate students in Rivers State's understanding and exploitation of entrepreneurial skills and opportunities in business education. To steer the study, two research questions and two matching null hypotheses aligned with two objectives were posed. The theoretical perspective was founded on Cantillon and Mill's (1814) "Risk Taking Theory" and Becker's (1964) "Human Capital Theory." A descriptive survey design was used in the study, using a population of Business Education students recruited from three universities in Rivers State, Nigeria.

The study employed a stratified random sampling technique. The population yielded a sample size of 259 pupils. The data collection tool was a 10-item questionnaire titled "Undergraduate Students' Awareness and Utilization of Entrepreneurship Skills and Opportunities in Business Education in Rivers State, Nigeria Questionnaire (USAUEOBEQ)". The test-retest technique was utilized to determine the instrument's reliability, yielding a coefficient index of 0.85 using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (r). In order to answer the study questions, mean and rank order were used, while z-test statistics were used to evaluate the hypotheses at the 0.05 alpha level. Among the findings were that undergraduate students are aware of entrepreneurship skills and opportunities through university entrepreneurship internship programs, occupational training, and the media. Furthermore, due to their low usage, undergraduate students do not take advantage of entrepreneurship skills opportunities for self-employment and wealth development. Based on the findings, it was advised, among other things, that entrepreneurial instruction be embedded and made mandatory at all levels of education, not just at the university level.

2.4 Literature Review Appraisal

Evidence from literature has also shown that despite the introduction of entrepreneurship education to higher education, the rate of unemployment in Nigeria still increases, although there are numerous factors affecting unemployment, which the quality of labour supply is among. Therefore, to give a direction to efforts towards the reduction of unemployment, higher education should embrace more of an experiential model in teaching employability and entrepreneurship skills to improve the quality of labour supply. In line with the literature review, service-learning has been successful in various higher institution across several developed countries. They have designated educational bodies across different levels to educate students on personal development, acquisition of skills, civic engagements, and overall community development through either pure service-learning, capstone courses, disciplined-based courses among others.

However, Nigerian universities are yet to adopt or develop a suitable service-learning curriculum to educate their students on how experiential learning can facilitate personal development and promote acquisition of skills. Even though Nigeria is a developing country, she cannot be left behind. As a result, it is critical that the Nigerian higher education system implement a service-learning curriculum to improve employability and entrepreneurship skills and to educate undergraduates on the importance of 21st century skills in improving the quality of labour supply in the Nigerian job market. This is the void that this study seeks to fulfil.

CHAPTER THREE METHODOLOGY

This chapter presented an intricate explanation of the methodology employed in this study.

3.1 Research Design

This study adopted explanatory sequential mixed methods design (Quan-qual). The researcher used quantitative data to explicitly support the qualitative data that was collected. The quantitative aspect involved collection of data through administration of questionnaires, while the qualitative aspect involved collection of data through key informant interviews.

3.2 Components Examined in the Study

The study categorized its variables following the IPO (Input, Process and Output) pattern. This approach is an analysis of performance and processing systems that assumes raw materials (inputs) are transformed by internal system processes to generate results (output).

Input Variables: These are the 21st-century skills by UNESCO (Employability and Entrepreneurship) which formed the basis on which the curriculum Subject Matters were hinged on.

Process Variables: These were the stages involved in the curriculum development process.

Output Variables: This is the Service-Learning Curriculum to enhance employability and entrepreneurship skills which was the end-product of all other variables involved in this study.

Figure 3.1: Variables of the study using the IPO model

Source: Adapted the model design from Babalola (2019)

Table 3.1: Some selected 21st century skills from UNESCO and the Brookings institution, (2020)

Relevant 21st Century Skills for Employability and Entrepreneurship	
1.	Conflict Resolution and Decision Making
2.	Self-Management and Business Management
3.	Financial Analysis and Strategic Thinking
4.	Information Technology and Media Literacy
5.	Presentation and Communication Skills
6.	Work and Social Media Ethics
7.	Critical-thinking and Problem Solving
8.	Capacity for Life-Long Learning
9.	Emotional Intelligence
10.	Networking and Marketing Skills
11.	Creativity and Innovation
12.	Leadership Skills

3.3 Surveyed Participants of the Study

The study's population encompassed university undergraduates and some stakeholders (human resource managers, entrepreneurs, service-learning experts, and curriculum experts) in southwestern Nigeria.

3.4 Study Sample and Sampling Procedure

The multistage sampling techniques were utilized in this research. The focus of the study was on the Southwestern part of Nigeria, and this comprises six (6) states namely, Oyo, Ogun, Osun, Lagos, Ekiti and Ondo.

The first stage employed the purposive sampling technique to select three (3) states from the six southwestern states. Osun, Lagos, and Ogun that have both federal and state universities. The universities in the selected three (3) states were Obafemi Awolowo University Ile Ife, Osun State (federal), Osun State University, Osogbo, Osun State (state), University of Lagos (federal), Lagos State University, Ojoo, Lagos (state), Federal University of Agriculture Abeokuta (federal), Olabisi Onabanjo University, Ago-Iwoye (state). Then, simple random sampling technique was used to select two state universities and two federal universities from the above-listed universities.

Then to conduct the need assessment, purposive sampling was used to select four common faculties each from the selected universities. Then the selection of 269 undergraduates from the 300 levels in each of the chosen faculties (total of 1076) was accomplished using the purposive sampling technique because they would have been exposed to entrepreneurship education as a general studies course as stated by National Universities Commission (NUC). Data was collected here by investigating the perceived skills needed upon graduation. Also, 20 stakeholders were interviewed to know their opinion on the need for the service-learning curriculum.

In the second stage, stakeholders were selected using the purposive sampling technique in validating the curriculum Subject Matters. Twenty (20) experts (HRs and Entrepreneurs, curriculum experts from NUC's curriculum development and planning division and service-learning local and international experts) were selected here using the Equi proportional approach to maintain a uniform standard across. Also, they were

selected taking into consideration their educational relevance, qualifications and vast experience related to the curriculum to be developed.

Furthermore, during the third stage, universities where the curriculum was trial tested were selected using the purposive sampling technique. University of Ibadan was intentionally selected for the try-out of the designed curriculum since University of Ibadan, Nigeria was not part of the schools used for the need assessment and it is the oldest university in the southwest. Hence, to ascertain the curriculum product being able to thrive in any higher institution, a different university was selected for the try-out stage. Furthermore, the intact GES 301 class was used for trial testing stage in the University of Ibadan. 168 participants were selected using the random sampling technique during the curriculum try out.

3.5 Research Instruments

Six self-developed and one adapted instrument were used in this study:

- i. Key Informant Interview Guide for Human Resource Managers (KIIGHRM)
- ii. Key Informant Interview Guide for Entrepreneurs (KIIGE)
- iii. Service-learning Curriculum for Employability and Entrepreneurship Skills Need Assessment Questionnaire (SLCEESNAQ)
- iv. Service-learning Curriculum for Employability and Entrepreneurship Skills Validation Rating Guide (SLCEESVRG)
- v. Service-learning Curriculum for Employability and Entrepreneurship Skills Participants' Perception Scale (SLCEESPPS)
- vi. Service-learning Curriculum for Employability and Entrepreneurship Skills Participants' Learning Outcome Interview Guide (SLCEESPLOIG)
- vii. Service-learning Curriculum Observers Rating Scale (SLCORS)

3.5.1 Key Informant Interview Guide for Human Resource Managers (KIIGHRM)

This was designed by the researcher to obtain first-hand information on the view of human resource managers in positioning a service-learning curriculum to address the problem of graduates' inability to display sufficient employability skills in the job

market. Precisely, the instrument addressed the relevance and suitability of this curriculum in addressing employable skills needed through a service-learning curriculum. Several experts in service learning and curriculum assessed the instrument's credibility and relevance by reviewing, analysing and evaluating it.

3.5.2 Key Informant Interview Guide for Entrepreneurs (KIIGE)

This interview guide was designed by the researcher. It elicited information from entrepreneurs on how a service-learning curriculum can address the problem of graduates' inability to display sufficient entrepreneurial skills in the job market. Several experts assessed the instrument's credibility and relevance by reviewing, analysing and evaluating it.

3.5.3 Service-learning Curriculum for Employability and Entrepreneurship Skills Need Assessment Questionnaire (SLCEESNAQ)

This was self-designed and structured by the researcher. This comprises four sections. First section gathered participants details, while second section gathered information regarding students' responsiveness of the service-learning approach, the 21st century skills and relevant employability and entrepreneurship skills needed by Nigerian graduates while third section elicited information through an unstructured test to determine participants knowledge on these skills, willingness to take the course if introduced and investigated, which of the skills they possess before the study. The reliability produced coefficients of 0.93 following the application of Cronbach Alpha analysis.

3.5.4 Service-learning Curriculum for Employability and Entrepreneurship Skills Validation Rating Guide (SLCEEESVRG)

This was designed by the researcher to investigate that the curriculum Subject Matter and objectives stated in the proposed service-learning curriculum will be relevant, valuable, and adequate to meet and achieve the goals the curriculum sets out to achieve. This validation was done by the stakeholders in which they went through the curriculum Subject Matters and also indicated by ticking; Not at all, A little, Quite a bit and A great

deal. This instrument gave a clearer view of how the curriculum should be shaped. The reliability yielded 0.91 coefficient after undergoing Cronbach Alpha analysis.

3.5.5 Service-learning Curriculum for Employability and Entrepreneurship Skills Participants' Perception Scale (SLCEESPPS)

This was designed by the researcher to obtain information on undergraduates' perception of the Subject Matter, objectives, use of service-learning approach and evaluation techniques of the curriculum to enhance employability and entrepreneurship skills. Undergraduates indicated whether they agree or disagree by ticking Excellent (E) - 4; Satisfactory (S)-3; Needs Improvement (NI)-2; and Very Weak (VW)-1. Subject Matter and face validity of the instrument was done by giving it to some lecturers in the Arts and Social Sciences Department, Institute of Education and Science and Technology Education Department in the University of Ibadan. The reliability yielded 0.84 coefficient after undergoing Cronbach Alpha analysis.

3.5.6 Service-learning Curriculum for Employability and Entrepreneurship Skills Participants' Learning Outcome Interview Guide (SLCEESPLOIG)

The researcher designed this instrument to gather information from undergraduates who took part in the trial testing, aiming to capture their understanding of the service-learning curriculum before and after the training, also to describe their present state of knowledge. Experts were involved in assessing the face and Subject Matter validity of this instrument.

3.5.7 Service-learning Curriculum Observers Rating Scale (SLCORS)

This was designed by the researcher to hear the view of the curriculum observers on the effectiveness (efficacy) of the curriculum in promoting employability and entrepreneurship traits among the undergraduates during and after the curriculum try-out. The instrument was shown to my supervisor and lecturers in the Department of Arts and Social Sciences Education for their input and suggestions. The Cronbach Alpha analysis resulted in a reliability coefficient of 0.84.

3.6 Procedure for Data Collection

After collection of an introduction letter from the department, both quantitative and qualitative data were collected sequentially in four phases namely, during the need assessment, the validation process, the curriculum try-out, and after the curriculum has been trial tested.

Stage One: In this stage, in-depth literature synthesis was done to source relevant 21st century skills and then need assessment was done to investigate skills students lack before proceeding to the design stage.

Stage Two: In this stage, the subject matters gathered from stage one was organised using the Kerr (1968) curriculum design model to arrange the needed skills into a functional service-learning curriculum.

Stage Three: In this stage, the designed service-learning curriculum was presented to relevant stakeholders for validation. They contributed to the adequacy of the curriculum objectives, Subject Matters, relevance, and suitability through this validation process. These validators were Human Resource Managers, Entrepreneurs, Curriculum Experts, and Service-Learning Experts.

Stage Four: This stage was the presentation of the designed curriculum for a try-out and reflection to know if the curriculum was adequate and relevant in equipping graduates with employability and entrepreneurship skills using the service-learning approach during trial testing.

The first phase was the identification of appropriate 21st century skills from multiple literature sources and then carry out a need assessment to know which of the skills the undergraduates currently possess. This stage lasted for about 3-4 weeks.

The second phase was the validation stage. In this stage, stakeholders were consulted to authenticate the Subject Matter of the curriculum before embarking on the try-out and reflection stage. In this stage, stakeholders investigated that the curriculum subject matter and objectives stated in the proposed service-learning curriculum will be relevant, valuable, and adequate to meet and achieve the goals the curriculum sets out to achieve. These validators utilized the (SLCEESVRG) to thoroughly assess the validity of the curriculum intended for the trial. The data gathered from the validation process underwent analysis to evaluate how realistic the designed curriculum's objectives, subject

matter, activities, and practical experiences will enhance undergraduates' employability and entrepreneurship skills. This stage lasted for 2 weeks.

The third stage was the try-out and reflection stage; in this stage, students were given orientation and training on how to embark on service-learning activities, the curriculum was trial tested and then students reflected on the activities they carried out. Hence, data was gathered while students were on their service projects considering students' level of involvement, attitude, and participation in the service-learning activities. Also, in this phase, the newly developed curriculum was subjected to classroom try-out using trained facilitators. Here, participants were exposed to the service-learning curriculum, how beneficiaries could benefit, how service projects could enhance employability and entrepreneurship and other activities embedded in the service-learning curriculum.

At the end of this phase, data was collected using Service-learning Curriculum for Employability and Entrepreneurship Skills Participants' Perception Scale (SLCEESPPS) and Service-learning Curriculum for Employability and Entrepreneurship Skills Participants' Learning Outcome Interview Guide (SLCEESPLOIG). Then, the service-learning Curriculum Observers Rating Scale (SLCORS) was used to hear the view of the curriculum observers on the effectiveness of the curriculum in promoting employability and entrepreneurship skills of the undergraduates during and after the curriculum try-out. Also, students engaged in critical reflection on what has been done and how they have benefitted immensely.

Four (4) research assistants underwent training on administering questionnaires and conducting interview sessions. Hence, both validation process and try-out stage lasted for 11-12 weeks.

Figure 3.6: The adapted 4-stages involved in the design of a service-learning curriculum.

Source: Bender (2005)

3.6.1 Service-Learning Curriculum Validation for Higher Education

Experts specializing in curriculum design, service-learning, and pertinent stakeholders involved in this study validated the curriculum. Also, the validation was done using the Service-learning Curriculum for Employability and Entrepreneurship Validation Rating Guide (SLCEESVRG) to collect data on the curriculum objective, curriculum Subject Matters, and the service-learning project experience involved in enhancing undergraduates' employability and entrepreneurship skills. Information obtained through the (SLCEEESVRG) was analysed and the feedback was used in strengthening the elements of the curriculum to be designed. This stage lasted for 2 weeks.

3.7 Methods of Data Analysis

The quantitative data collected was analysed using descriptive statistics of frequency counts, percentage score, mean and standard deviation. The qualitative data collected was transcribed and analysed using ATLAS.ti and Subject Matter analysis.

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Analysis and discussion of the collected study data are presented in the following chapter.

4.1 Demographic Data of Participants

This section includes the demographic details of all participants involved in each stage of the study, with a specific focus on displaying the demographic information gathered during the need assessment phase of the research

X

Figure 4.1: Needs assessment participants: Name of institution

Y

Figure 4.1 presents the name of participants' institution during the need assessment of the research. It reveals that, 279 (26%) are from Osun State University, 290(27%) are from University of Lagos, while 240(22.3%) are from Lagos State University, and 268(24.7) are from Obafemi Awolowo University.

Figure 4.2: Faculty of respondents during needs assessment

Figure 4.2 illustrates the demographic details of all partakers during the need assessment phase of the research, categorized based on faculties. The figure shows that 257(23.9%) of the respondents are from faculty of science, 224(20.8%) are from Management of Science, while 291(27.1%) are from Social Sciences, and 303(28.2%) are from faculty of Education.

X

Y

Figure 4.3: Gender of respondents

Figure 4.3 illustrates the demographic details of all partakers during the need assessment phase of this research, categorized by gender. The data shows that 398 (37%) are male, while 677 (63%) are female. Indicating that, female participated in the need assessment study more than their male counterparts.

4.1.2 Overview of validator demographics

Table 4.1 Summary of validator data

S/N	Gender	Frequency	Percentage
1	Male	11	55%
	Female	9	45%
	Total	20	100%
Highest Qualification			
2	PhD	12	60%
	Masters	8	40%
	Total	20	100%
Areas of Specialization			
3	Curriculum and Instruction	5	25%
	Service-Learning	5	25%
	Human Resources	5	25%
	Entrepreneurship	5	25%

The table indicates that 55% of the validators were male, while 45% were female. Moreover, 60% of the validators held a Ph.D., whereas 40% had a master's degree. Additionally, the validators represented various areas of specialization, including curriculum and instruction, service-learning, human resources, and entrepreneurship, respectively.

4.1.2 Participants' demographics during the trial stage

Table 4.2 Summary of participants' data throughout the trial stage.

S/N	Gender	Frequency	Percentage
1	Male	91	54.7%
	Female	77	45.3%
	Total	168	100%
Participants Faculty			
2	Social Sciences	42	25%
	Arts	42	25%
	Education	42	25%
	Sciences	42	25%
	Total	168	100%

4.2 Research Questions Analysis

Research Question 1: What is the level of undergraduates' awareness of employability skills?

Table 4.3: Mean response of the undergraduates' awareness of employability skills

Sn	Items	Very Much Aware	Aware	Less Aware	Not Aware	\bar{x}	Std
1	UNESCO's 21 st century skills are needed to be employable in Nigeria.	266 (24.7%)	341 (31.7%)	243 (22.6%)	225 (20.9%)	2.60	1.07
2	21 st century job vacancies require the ability to display knowledge on Information Technology (ICT)	553 (51.4%)	391 (36.4%)	93 (8.7%)	38 (3.5)	3.36	.784
3	Employers check your social media profile before being recruited	273 (25.3%)	380 (35.3%)	278 (25.9%)	144 (13.4%)	2.73	.987
4	Undergoing a personality test is part of the recruitment exercise in the work place	401 (37.3%)	434 (40.4%)	178 (16.6%)	62 (5.8%)	3.09	.873
5	To get 21 st century jobs, you should be able to work in a team.	534 (49.7%)	376 (35.0%)	125 (11.6%)	40 (3.7%)	3.31	.818
6	Getting recommendations in the workplace requires avoiding conflicts	459 (42.7%)	423 (39.3%)	145 (13.5%)	48 (4.5%)	3.20	.837
7	21 st century jobs require frequent collaboration with colleagues	474 (44.1%)	464 (43.2%)	107 (10.0%)	30 (2.8%)	3.29	.756
8	21 st century job roles require ability to proffer solution to workplace challenges	565 (52.6%)	389 (36.2%)	92 (8.6%)	29 (2.7%)	3.39	.755
9	Before securing a job, you should be able to think critically on how to solve problems	620 (57.7%)	362 (33.7%)	75 (7.0%)	18 (1.7%)	3.47	.700
10	21 st century jobs require the ability to lead a team	497 (46.2%)	437 (40.7%)	118 (11.0%)	23 (2.1%)	3.31	.750
	Weighted mean					3.17	

Note: Percentages are in parenthesis

Table 4.3 shows the level of undergraduates' awareness of employability skills. It was observed that items 2, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, and 10 have mean scores higher or equal to the weighted mean of ($\bar{x} = 3.17$) in favour of undergraduates' awareness of employability skills. While items 1, 3, and 4 successively have mean scores below the weighted mean. Judging from items with mean above the weighted mean the result implies that undergraduates are aware that the employability skills needed to secure good jobs in this 21st century is high. This means they know the meaning of employability skills.

Research Question 2: What is the level of undergraduates' awareness of entrepreneurship skills?

Table 4.4: Mean response of the undergraduates' awareness of entrepreneurship skills

Sn	ITEMS	Very Much Aware	Aware	Less Aware	Not Aware	\bar{x}	Sd
1	Entrepreneurs should be able to make good use of available opportunities	722 (67.2%)	298 (27.7%)	36 (3.3%)	19 (1.8%)	3.60	.643
2	While creating a job you should have the ability to take risks	721 (67.1%)	303 (28.2%)	34 (3.2%)	17 (1.6)	3.61	.630
3	A job creator should have the capacity to think strategically	768 (71.4%)	261 (24.3%)	30 (2.8%)	16 (1.5%)	3.66	.609
4	An employer should be able to make good employment decisions	740 (68.8%)	307 (28.6%)	21 (2.0%)	7 (0.7%)	3.66	.581
5	An employer should be able to make good business decisions	665 (61.9%)	356 (33.1%)	44 (4.1%)	10 (0.9%)	3.66	.551
6	An entrepreneur should be able to convey ideas in a clear term to prospective investors	702 (65.3%)	323 (30.0%)	43 (4.0%)	7 (0.7%)	3.56	.620
7	Entrepreneurs should be to recognize opportunities	668 (62.1%)	330 (30.7%)	67 (6.2%)	10 (0.9%)	3.60	.600
8	A job creator should have the ability to lead a team	641 (59.6%)	343 (31.9%)	73 (6.8%)	18 (1.7%)	3.54	.655
9	Entrepreneurs should have the ability to resolve conflicts among workers	641 (59.6%)	343 (31.9%)	73 (6.8%)	18 (1.7%)	3.49	.698
10	Entrepreneurs should be able to draw timelines to meet their targets.	650 (60.5%)	363 (33.8%)	51 (4.7%)	11 (1.0%)	3.54	.637
Weighted Mean: 3.59		Threshold: 2.5					

Note: Percentages are in parenthesis

Table 4.4 shows the level of undergraduates' awareness of entrepreneurship skills. From the table, it was observed that, items 1,2,3,4,5, and 7 have mean scores higher or equal to the weighted mean of ($\bar{x} = 3.59$) which is in favour of undergraduates' awareness of entrepreneurship skills. While items 6, 8, 9, and 10 successively have mean scores below the weighted mean. Judging from items with mean above the weighted mean, the result implies that, undergraduates' level of awareness of entrepreneurship skills needed to fit-in, in today's workplace is high. Which implies they know the meaning of entrepreneurship skills.

4.2.3 Research Question 3: To what extent would the opinion of stakeholders (human resource managers and entrepreneurs) on graduates' possession of employability skills justify the need for a service-learning curriculum?

Unemployment is a global concern for both developed and developing countries, and its rate has increased worldwide, particularly after the recent global economic crisis. The rapid pace of change in technology and the economy during the latter half of the 20th century and beyond has had a significant impact on the workplace, necessitating changes in the educational system to prepare students adequately for the workforce. In response, major employers have issued reports outlining key skills and strategies required to meet the changing demands of the workplace and society. However, many employers have observed that graduates lack the necessary skills to perform effectively during job interviews and contribute meaningfully to the workplace's development and advancement. This suggests that stakeholders, including the government, schools, and other interested parties, should prioritize the development of students' skills to meet the standards required in the real world, rather than focusing solely on obtaining certificates. To illustrate this need, the perspectives of entrepreneurs and human resources professionals on the importance of a service-learning curriculum in universities are presented graphically in Figure 4.3.

Figure 4.3. Entrepreneurs’ view on the need for a service-learning curriculum in universities

Focus on Being Employers: An employer is a person or organization that employs people- pays them for work. Respondent 3 was of the opinion that, *“It will assist them to stand on their own after graduation”* She was supported by Respondent 4 who also said *“after graduation they can focus on being an employer of labour rather than being employees”*. Mindset is probably the major determinant of success in pretty much every walk of life. In other words, the thinking patterns you habitually adopt largely govern the results you achieve. Therefore, employers have a mastermind mentality while employees have a pay for performance mentality. This means that, service-learning curriculum will work on student’s mindset to help them think more creative in being self-reliance other than hoping and waiting on the government to provide jobs for them.

- 1. Address Business Challenges:** In every aspect of life, there are challenges. Managers and owners of businesses face some of these challenges. Respondent 5 was of the view that, service-learning curriculum will help address such issues by saying *“it would help them to address the problems or challenges practically”*. He was supported by respondent 1 who also said, *“graduates would have learnt to be more critical thinkers and will develop strategies to solve any problem”*. People who are good at problem solving are of the most valuable and respected people in every area. In fact, success is often defined as *“the ability to solve problems.”* Most people value it even more than book smart and the best employers always look at for those that have both.
- 2. Fully prepared for the outside world:** The outside world is the world of opportunities. Respondent 4 was of the view that, service-learning curriculum will help the students in so many ways when he said, *“the exposure will aid work experience to prepare graduates for the outside world”*. The outside world is full of opportunities especially for those that possess most of the 21st century skills, service-learning curriculum will prepare these students to be more effective and ready for such opportunities.

- 3. Skill Modification:** skill modification is the use of extrinsic feedback to modify a client's existing skill, increasing the occurrence of a correct performance, and decreasing the occurrence of errors. Respondent 6 was of the view that, service-learning will help and modify the skills in the students. He said, "*early exposure to business skills will help mold their minds*" This will prepare the students to be self-reliant and develop skills that will enable them to survive even without a job after their studies.

- 4. Exposure to practical learning:** Practical learning is a task in which students observe and do things by themselves. It can be different from reading and listening for students. It helps them get hands-on experience in the learning activities thereby making them very confident and competent. Respondent 3 was of the view that service-learning curriculum will help the students in so many ways. According to him "*practical learning is better than book learning*" he was supported by respondent 6 who said, "*because what has been put in practice will always remain in the brain*". Practical learning allows students to learn quick adaptations needed for daily challenges and scenarios and allows them to build upon existing skills.

Figure 4.4: Human Resource's view on the need for a service-learning curriculum

- 5. Lack of Adequate Preparation:** Respondent 6 believed most graduates are not adequately prepared to face the workplace, she said, “*They aren’t prepared by the education system*”. He was supported by respondent 6 who stated that “*I feel that the curriculum of our schools from primary to university are designed to produce learners who just regurgitate Subject Matter*”.

Adequate preparation makes one feel more comfortable and more effective hence service-learning curriculum will open more doors for the students to learn and practice skills that will enable them fit in the workplace after their studies.

- 6. Lack of Skills:** Skills are very important. They help us improve our way of thinking, problem-solving, and the quality of our lives. Respondent 2 was of the view that “*there’s a huge gap between the needs of employers and graduates’ skill acquisition*”. Skills are activities which are developed by people with time and becomes automatic in terms of performance. A certain skill can be considered acquired when a person can perform it without thinking about the technique of performing this action or dividing a process into conventional parts. They help one to adjust to the realities of the employment market and serve as basis for adjusting for the future.

Research Question 4: To what extent do the formulated objectives in the service-learning curriculum dedicated to Employability and Entrepreneurship (EES) foster the acquisition of vital skills among undergraduates??

Table 4.5: Mean responses of service-learning curriculum to enhancing entrepreneurship skills validation

S/N	Items	AGD	QAB	AL	NAA	\bar{x}	Std
1	The stated curriculum objectives cover relevant experiences needed in enhancing undergraduates' entrepreneurship skills	6 60.0	4 40.0	0 0	0 0	3.85	.366
2	The objectives reveal the competencies undergraduates will acquire while exposed to the curriculum	7 70.0	3 30.0	1 5.0	0 0	3.70	.571
3	Service-learning approach to be used in this curriculum will facilitate relevant entrepreneurship skills needed by undergraduates upon graduation	8 80.0	2 20.0	0 0	1 5.0	3.75	.716
4	The objectives of the curriculum cover relevant competencies needed to promote entrepreneurship	6 60.0	3 30.0	1 10.0	0 0	3.75	.550
5	The Subject Matter of the service-learning curriculum takes into consideration the development of undergraduates 21st century entrepreneurship skills	6 60.0	4 40.0	0 0	0 0	3.65	.489
6	The Subject Matter of service-learning curriculum considers the personal development of undergraduates	7 70.0	3 30.0	0 0	0 0	3.70	.470
7	The Subject Matter of service-learning curriculum considers the social development of undergraduates	7 70.0	3 30.0	0 0	0 0	3.70	.470
8	The Subject Matter of service-learning curriculum considers the intellectual development of undergraduates	5 50.0	4 40.0	1 10.0	0 0	3.65	.587
9	The learners' response to the curriculum suggests that the Subject Matter is suitable in enlightening undergraduates on the essential entrepreneurship skills required upon graduation.	5 50.0	4 40.0	1 10.0	0 0	3.50	.607
10	Will undergraduates be able to acquire entrepreneurship skills through exposure to the service-learning curriculum?	5 50.0	5 50.0	0 0	0 0	3.50	.513
11	The Subject Matter of service-learning curriculum will give undergraduates better enlightenment in understanding realities of job creation	8 80.0	2 20.0	0 0	0 0	3.80	.410
12	The Subject Matter of service-learning curriculum will achieve stated learners' outcome	50 50.0	4 40.0	1 10.0	0 0	3.50	.607
13	Service activities specified in the curriculum will be adequate in enhancing entrepreneurship skills	8 80.0	2 20.0	1 10.0	0 0	3.75	.716
14	The Subject Matter of service-learning curriculum will expose students to required factors involved in creating jobs	6 60.0	4 40.0	0 0	0 0	3.55	.510
15	The Subject Matters of this curriculum address how undergraduates can identify and pursue their career interests	8 80.0	2 20.0	0 0	0 0	3.80	.410
16	The Subject Matter of this curriculum gives undergraduates the opportunity to gather experience from multiple sources to aid their entrepreneurship skills	6 60.0	4 40.0	0 0	0 0	3.60	.503
17	The Subject Matter of this curriculum emphasises on how service commitments can enhance undergraduates' entrepreneurship skills?	8 80.0	2 20.0	0 0	0 0	3.85	.366
18	The Subject Matter of this curriculum covers the important connections between career interests and acquisition of 21st century entrepreneurship skills?	3 30.0	7 70.0	0 0	0 0	3.70	.470
	Weighted Average: 3.68 Threshold: 2.5						

Key: AGD: A Great Deal; QAB: Quite A Bit; AL: A Little NAA: Not at All

Table 4.5 shows the responses of Service-Learning Curriculum to Enhancing Entrepreneurship Skills Validation. It reveals a weighted average of 3.68 which is higher than the threshold of 2.5. This implies that service-learning curriculum to enhancing entrepreneurship skills validation was good and positive.

Research Question 5: To what extent do the formulated objectives in the service-learning curriculum dedicated to Employability foster the acquisition of vital skills among undergraduates?

Table 4.6: Mean response of service-learning curriculum to enhance employability skills validation

S/N	Items on Curriculum Objectives	AGD	QAB	ALB	N	\bar{x}	Std
1	The stated curriculum objectives cover relevant experiences needed in enhancing undergraduates' employability skills	4 40.0	5 50.0	1 10.0	0 0	3.30	.675
2	The curriculum objectives will reveal the competencies undergraduates will acquire while exposed to this curriculum	5 50.0	5 50.0	0 0	0 0	3.50	.527
3	Service-learning approach will be useful in facilitating relevant employability skills undergraduates need upon graduation	2 20.0	7 70.0	1 10.0	0 0	3.10	.568
4	The objectives of the service-learning curriculum cover relevant competencies needed in gaining employment opportunities	4 40.0	6 60.0	0 0	0 0	3.40	.516
Items on Curriculum Subject Matter							
5	The Subject Matter of the service-learning curriculum takes into consideration the development of undergraduates 21st century employability skills	4 40.0	6 60.0	0 0	0 0	3.40	.516
6	The Subject Matter of service-learning curriculum considers the personal development of undergraduates	6 60.0	4 40.0	0 0	0 0	3.60	.516
7	The Subject Matter of service-learning curriculum considers the social development of undergraduates	3 30.0	7 70.0	0 0	0 0	3.30	.483
8	The Subject Matter of service-learning curriculum considers the intellectual development of undergraduates	7 70.0	3 30.0	0 0	0 0	3.70	.483
9	The learners' response to the curriculum suggests that the Subject Matter is suitable in enlightening undergraduates on the essential entrepreneurship skills required upon graduation.	4 40.0	6 60.0	0 0	0 0	3.40	.516
10	Will undergraduates be able to acquire employability skills through the service-learning curriculum?	4 40.0	6 60.0	0 0	0 0	3.40	.516
11	The Subject Matter of service-learning curriculum will give undergraduates better enlightenment in understanding realities of the workplace	3 30.0	7 70.0	0 0	0 0	3.30	.483
12	The Subject Matter of service-learning curriculum will achieve stated learners' outcome	4 40.0	6 60.0	0 0	0 0	3.40	.516
13	Service activities specified in the curriculum will be adequate in enhancing employability skills	5 50.0	5 50.0	0 0	0 0	3.50	.527
14	The Subject Matter of service-learning curriculum will expose students to the preparation for the world of work	6 60.0	4 40.0	0 0	0 0	3.60	.516
15	The Subject Matters of this curriculum address how undergraduates can identify and pursue their career interests	3 30.0	7 70.0	0 0	0 0	3.30	.483
16	The Subject Matter of this curriculum gives undergraduates the opportunity to gather experience from multiple sources to aid their employability skills	7 70.0	3 30.0	0 0	0 0	3.70	.483
17	The Subject Matter of this curriculum emphasises on how service commitments can enhance undergraduates' employability skills	4 40.0	6 60.0	0 0	0 0	3.40	.516
18	The Subject Matter of this curriculum covers the important connections between career interests and acquisition of 21st century employability skills?	5 50.0	5 50.0	0 0	0 0	3.50	.527
Weighted Average: 3.43 Threshold: 2.5							

Key: AGD: A Great Deal; QAB: Quite A Bit; AL: A Little NAA: Not at All

Table 4.6 shows the mean response of service-learning curriculum to enhance employability skills validation. It reveals a weighted average of 3.43 which is higher than the threshold of 2.5. This implies that service-learning curriculum capacity to enhance employability skills was adjudged high.

Research Question 6: What is the perception of stakeholders on the Subject Matter of the service-learning curriculum to enhance EES?

Table 4.7: Mean responses of observers' rating of service-learning curriculum subject matter adequacy, suitability and relevance

Sn	Items	Adequacy				Suitability				Relevance			
		Yes	NO	\bar{x}	Std.	Yes	NO	\bar{x}	Std	Yes	NO	\bar{x}	Std.
1	Curriculum Objectives	20 100	0 0	1.00	.00 0	15 75.0	5 25.0	1.2 5	.444	17 85.0	3 15.0	1.15	.366
2	Curriculum Subject Matter	16 80.0	4 20.0	1.20	.41 0	19 95.0	1 5.0	1.0 5	.224	20 100	0 0	1.00	.000
3	Service-Learning Activities	19 95.0	1 5.0	1.05	.22 4	17 85.0	3 15.0	1.1 5	.366	19 95.0	1 5.0	1.05	.224
4	Learning Outcomes	17 85.0	3 15.0	1.15	.36 6	20 100.0	0 0	1.0 0	.000	20 100	0 0	1.00	.000
5	Reflection Activities	18 90.0	2 10.0	1.20	.69 6	15 75.0	5 25.0	1.4 0	.940	18 90.0	2 10.0	1.10	.308
6	Style of Evaluation	16 80.0	4 20.0	1.20	.41 0	18 90.0	2 10.0	1.1 0	.308	16 80.0	4 20.0	1.20	.410
Weighted Average				1.13				1.16				1.08	

The Table 4.7 revealed that stakeholders had positive perception of the Subject Matter adequacy, suitability, and relevance of the service-learning curriculum for enhancing undergraduates' employability and entrepreneurship skills. It revealed a weighted average of Subject Matter adequacy (\bar{x} : 1.13), suitability (\bar{x} : 1.16), and relevance (\bar{x} : 1.08) as against the threshold of 1.0 respectively.

Research Question 6: What is the perception of undergraduates on the extent to which the objectives of the service-learning curriculum promote EES?

Table 4.8: Mean responses of participants' perception of service-learning curriculum

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{x}	Std
1	The service-learning curriculum is actively engaging	158 92.9	12 7.1	0 0	0 0	3.93	.257
2	The skills I have learnt are needed upon graduation	30 17.6	135 79.4	2 1.2	3 1/8	3.13	.493
3	The objectives of the curriculum are realisable	114 67.1	24 14.1	15 8.8	17 10.0	3.38	1.009
4	The teaching and learning activities involved in this curriculum is relevant in the 21st century	88 51.8	55 32.4	20 11.8	7 4.1	3.32	.839
5	What I have learnt exposes me to the elements of 21st century skills needed as stated by UNESCO	52 30.6	86 50.6	25 14.7	7 4.1	3.08	.784
6	Topics presented in this curriculum are logically arranged	128 75.3	40 23.5	2 1.2	0 0	3.74	.465
7	What I was taught addresses the employability and entrepreneurship skills needed upon graduation	40 23.5	112 65.9	5 2.9	13 7.6	3.05	.756
8	Exposure to this curriculum is sufficient in developing my skills in securing a job	106 62.4	43 25.3	13 7.6	8 4.7	3.45	.829
9	Participation in this curriculum try-out has exposed me to the acquisition of EES	67 39.4	68 40.0	23 13.5	12 7.1	3.12	.896
10	Participation in acquisition of EES will equip me in giving out the best in the work place	76 44.7	63 37.1	20 11.8	11 6.5	3.20	.888
11	Participation in this curriculum has exposed me to the rudiment and practical knowledge needed in the creation of jobs	67 39.4	71 41.8	22 12.9	10 5.9	3.15	.861
12	The curriculum has detailed the skills and competencies needed upon university graduation?	64 37.6	66 38.8	33 19.4	7 4.1	3.10	.854
13	This curriculum lay more emphasis on actively engaging in service commitments and projects?	63 37.1	73 42.9	28 16.5	6 3.5	3.14	.814
14	This curriculum enlightens me on connections between career development and acquisition skills?	66 38.8	72 42.4	16 9.4	16 9.4	3.11	.923
Weighted Average: 3.28 Threshold: 2.5							

Table 4.8 shows the responses of participants perception of the service-learning curriculum. It reveals a weighted average of 3.28 which is higher than the threshold of 2.5. This implies that participants' perception of service-learning curriculum was positive.

Research Question 7: What is observers' assessment of the efficacy of service-learning curriculum to promote EES among undergraduates?

Table 4.9: Mean responses of observers' rating of service-learning curriculum

S/N	Items	VE	E	LE	NE	\bar{x}	Std
1	Do you think this curriculum has aided participants' skills in securing employment opportunities upon graduation?	11 55.0	6 30.0	3 15.0	0 0	3.40	.754
2	Do you consider the curriculum to have aided participants' ability to do new things?	16 80.0	3 15.0	0 0	1 5.0	3.70	.733
3	Do you think the curriculum has aided participant's ability to collaborate in a team?	9 45.0	10 50.0	5 5.0	0 0	3.40	.598
4	The Subject Matters of this curriculum have exposed participants adequately to information needed to keep a job?	8 40.0	9 45.0	0 0	3 15.0	3.10	1.021
5	The Subject Matters of this curriculum have exposed participants adequately to information needed to create a job?	14 70.0	5 25.0	0 0	1 5.0	3.60	.754
6	The learning outcome of the curriculum has shaped participants view in addressing workplace challenges?	7 35.0	11 55.0	2 10.0	0 0	3.25	.639
7	Do you consider the curriculum experiences useful in exposing participants to hands-on experience?	12 60.0	5 25.0	2 10.0	1 5.0	3.40	.883
8	Do you think this curriculum has exposed participants to have various perspectives to teamwork issues?	6 30.0	11 55.0	2 10.0	1 5.0	3.10	.788
9	Do you think this curriculum has exposed participants to make decisions successfully?	11 55.0	6 30.0	3 15.0	0 0	3.40	.754
10	Do you think this curriculum have aided participants ability to identify problems and proffer solutions?	7 35.0	10 50.0	1 5.0	2 10.0	3.10	.912
Weighted Average: 3.35 Threshold: 2.5							

Table 4.2.7 shows the responses of the Observers' Rating of Service-Learning Curriculum. It reveals a weighted average of 3.35 which is higher than the threshold of 2.5. This implies that the service-learning curriculum as rated by observers was positive.

4.2.8 Research Question 8: What is the perception of undergraduates on their learning outcomes in the service-learning curriculum after trial testing?

a. Participants' Experiences in the Service-Learning Activities

The participants in the in-depth interview conducted was the need for service-learning curriculum. They extolled the virtues of service-learning curriculum that it equips them with employability and entrepreneurship skills of the 21st century. They are also of the view that the service-learning curriculum exposed them to real-world life situations. Part of their experiences is that learning was made practical and interactive. As reported by the undergraduates who participated, *I have to be a better version of myself. I have gained both theoretical and real-life experience of issues on entrepreneurship and employability in the 21st century during this programme. (Participant A; Female; UI, 5/11/2022).*

Another participant gave her experiences as follows:

I had a wonderful and interesting experience because the teaching was fun and almost everyone in the class had something to talk about. It was not a boring class. The class was very interactive and lively. **(Participant B; Female; UI, 5/11/2022).**

Other responses from the interview are as follows:

I have gained and acquired a lot from the course. I like having a business of my own in the future. So, I now understand that a lot of things is behind being an entrepreneur. You have to know both employability and entrepreneurship skills very well to succeed in a business. Also, as a businessperson, I have to always put community service at heart too. **(Participants C: male; UI; 6/11/2022).**

Further still, another participant buttressed this theme:

I have benefitted a lot because service-learning has been exposing me to real-world situations. Especially the service projects we conducted gave me insights of what I can establish when I graduate. Surely, I will recommend this curriculum because I like to

practicalize what was been taught and this curriculum also exposes people to good decision making which is key to success for any graduate. **(Participants D: male; UI; 6/11/2022).**

Other participants gave their experiences hereunder:

I have been able to acquire some skills like being able to think critically to solve any challenge or problem that comes my way after graduation on either how to secure a job or start my own business. I have had a wide range of experiences from learning needed skills to be successful after university graduation. **(Participants E: Female; UI; 6/11/2022).**

It can be concluded from all the excerpts that participants have learnt a lot through service-learning curriculum. They adjudged the curriculum as really good in exposing graduates to a better future in entrepreneurship and grooming employable graduates. Many of them had awesome experiences. Also, the curriculum is seen as helping in the development of valuable skills needed useful after graduation. Service-learning always promote individual participation in the class and also among team members. Most of the skills they have not been exposed to like conflict resolution are part of the Subject Matters in the service-learning curriculum. It afforded the students opportunity to take charge of some topics through presentations and groupings.

b. On the benefits of service-learning curriculum and whether or not they would recommend it for use.

The participants said that most of the skills they have not been exposed to like conflict resolution were part of the Subject Matters in this curriculum. They also said that they were able to identify their weaknesses and so, they will be able to carefully select suitable career options after graduation instead of hunting for jobs that are not available. They have also been able to gather a lot of knowledge that instead of roaming on the streets looking for jobs, the skills embedded in this curriculum has equipped them with capacity to run business and run it successfully. Excerpts from the interview point to this: I can now comprehend the major skills needed in the labour market so that one can successfully get a job or start a business with the knowledge gained. Absolutely, I will recommend this curriculum over 100% to all universities either public or private any day

anytime because it will aid the nation's development in the long run. **(Participant F: Male; UI, 8/11/2022).**

Similarly, this is participant B responses:

I benefited greatly. I have been able to learn new things and also, I now have a clearer vision of my goals after school. I can now think strategically on how to accomplish these visions successfully. **(Participant B: Female; UI, 8/11/2022).**

Furthermore, another respondent said:

I have learnt a lot of self-independence tactics which will help anyone that undergoes it. This curriculum gives one the ability to think deep, associate with other class members to carry out projects and also understand what is expected of you in the society as a graduate. Of course, I will recommend this curriculum 100% because it is embedded with a lot of skills needed by the youths of today. **(Participant G: Male; UI, 10/11/2022).**

In conclusion, they agreed that service-learning curriculum is very needed because it will change their orientation about seeking for jobs after graduation on what their expectations should be and what they should display in the labour market. The curriculum really benefits undergraduates in many ways as they now have the vision to accomplish objectives that addresses doing good in the community. Also, they deeply understand the logic behind not only being an entrepreneur but something more and always being able to give back to the society. They all agreed to recommend that this curriculum should be made available to undergraduates to learn how to develop and secure their future. They will also not be blaming the government on unemployable and unemployed graduates. The Service-learning curriculum has equipped them with skills that will make me able good employees or employers of labour because they learnt a lot during the course of teaching. Some of the skills mentioned in this curriculum are not in the present entrepreneurship curriculum they are using in the university currently.

c. Why Nigeria Undergraduates Need Service-Learning Curriculum

The reasons adduced by participants for claiming that Nigeria undergraduates need the service-learning curriculum are manifold. For example, respondents opined that Nigerian undergraduate need this curriculum because it will make them independent,

confident and also have the ability to think on the spot. It will also make them to be self-reliant because service-learning encourages everyone's participation. So, the curriculum will boost undergraduates' confidence to take up responsibilities. Nigeria undergraduates also need service-learning curriculum so that they can think deeply beyond entrepreneurship after school. The curriculum could make them employable by acquiring 21st century skills. It is also needed because it will change their orientation about seeking for jobs after graduation on what their expectations should be and what they should display in the labour market. So, respondents agreed that this curriculum is necessary for all undergraduates because it comprises of the 21st century skills needed by any job seeker or business owner that wants to be successful.

The respondents opined as follows:

If undergraduates have knowledge of this curriculum, they won't be ignorant of the skills they need in being a good employee and a successful entrepreneur when they graduate. **(Participant B: Female; UI, 8/11/2022).**

I believe they need it to be a successful employer of labour or a good employee after their graduation which will improve the growth of Nigerian Economy' **(Participant G: Male; UI, 9/11/2022).**

Another undergraduate said: *'Undergraduates need this curriculum because future generations need to be action takers instead of waiting to be spoon-fed.* **(Participant E: Female; UI, 9/11/2022).**

Yet another respondent claim that:

I am of the opinion that undergraduate's orientation will change on either getting a job or starting either a sole proprietorship or partnership business. **(Participant D: Male; UI, 9/11/2022).**

The conclusion that can be drawn from these excerpts is that all undergraduates need this curriculum because it will aid them in exploring the world of labour market and help them navigate labour market smoothly. It is also good for their personal career growth and also professional development. All tertiary institutions not just universities need it because it will really motivate them to learn employable skills.

d. Challenges Observed During the Curriculum Try-out

Among the challenges identified are reluctance of undergraduates to take some of the events specified in the curriculum seriously because they saw it as time consuming. For instance, when they were to have a debate program, most participants were too lazy to research on good responses to contribute during the debate. Also, there is no cooperation among some of the team members and despite that this curriculum preaches teamwork. Individual responses of the participants on this are given below:

People were not ready to work. Most people were showing nonchalant attitude during the teaching of the curriculum (Participant F: Male; UI, 8/11/2022).

Another challenge experienced is:

That there is no teamwork during some of the projects as a result of conflict due to financial constraints' **Participant A: Female; UI, 10/11/2022.**

It can be concluded from these excerpts that the challenges faced during the try-out of service curriculum were lack of team spirit among participants, financial constraints, and lackadaisical attitude to the programme on the part of the undergraduates.

Suggestions for Improvement on Identified Challenges.

The following suggestions were made for improvements on the challenges identified. They suggest that the grouping and teamwork should be used in other courses so that class members would have gotten more used to each other, and they will be able to cooperate better in future projects assigned to them. It was also suggested that there should be enough motivation and reward for all participants involved in this curriculum because this curriculum involves more practical work. Financial support should also be provided when trying out this curriculum because this curriculum involves more practical scenarios. So, this curriculum will need more sponsors for some of the programs or events.

For example, participant A said:

'There should be a form of motivation to the participants and researchers' (**Participant A: Female; UI, 10/11/2022**).

I did not observe any challenge, but I suggest that something like this curriculum should be available to all Nigerian universities' (**Participant C: Female; UI, 12/11/2022**).

The only suggestion I have is that undergraduates should take this curriculum seriously because if everyone of us is enlightened and we can be able to think critically, the easier it will be to correct the notion that graduates are unemployable. (**Participant F; male; UI, 12/11/2022**).

In conclusion, the participants suggested that this curriculum should be incorporated into general curriculum in all tertiary institutions because if this curriculum is being adopted into the university curriculum, students will take it more seriously because they know that aside marks will be awarded to them for participating in the projects, they will also acquire life-long learning. Integrating the service-learning program into Nigerian universities curriculum will make graduates self-dependent and independent after graduation.

4.3 Discussion of Results

4.3.1 Analysis of Undergraduates' Awareness of Employability Skills

The result revealed that undergraduates are aware of employability skills. By implication, it means that the undergraduates that were part of the study revealed that they know that there are certain skills which are called employability skills some of which are financial, communication, interpersonal skills, technology, problem-solving and several others. At times, these skills are referred to as transferable skills. The findings of this study align with those of Binkley, Erstad, Herman, Raizen, Ripley, Miller-Ricci, and Rumble (2012), indicating that approximately 80% of the undergraduates, nearly two-thirds of the entire sample, acknowledged their familiarity with employability skills. On the contrary, the study of Care and Anderson (2016) as well as Cherniss and Goleman (2001) affirmed that employability skills such as emotional intelligence, self-management, teamwork, and several others can be domiciled in an individual without them having the capacity to identify it.

To buttress, it has been found to be critical to students' development even when they are not aware of the existence of these skills in their respective lives. The study is in line with the research of Akinbode, and Oyelude (2020); Akinyemi, Aimm, Igot and

Ikuenomore (2012); Damoah, Peprah and Brefo (2021); Okolie, Nwosu and Mlanga (2019); Pitan (2017) and Tomlinson (2017) which found that no student can claim ignorant of employability skills. This is because several of the skills are student-driven and have been directly or indirectly embedded into the school curriculum. However, the studies of Evans, Gbadamosi, Wells and Scott (2012) found that there is high level of awareness among students due to the interconnected clustered of the use and deployment of the internet for several purposes, but it is the application of some of these skills that are the main challenges for most of these students.

This was corroborated by the studies of Dagenais, Hawley and Lund (2003) and Carvalho and Yeoman (2018) whose findings affirmed that several companies lament that graduates lack some critical employability skills which are necessary for them to perform well and efficiently during job recruitment and placement exercise. For instance, several business owners whose opinions were canvassed felt that graduates who are expected to make significant contributions to the growth and improvement of the workplace lack the necessary abilities and fortitude to do so. This submission of the study was not at variance with the assertion above, especially while considering the study of Clevenger and Ozbek (2013) which stated service-learning depicts sustainability competencies in the construction of several educational activities but some of the practical roles are not deployed by some teachers at nearly all levels of education which can help galvanise awareness among students. It is to be noted that several other factors could trigger students' awareness of employability skills.

This is because at all levels of education, irrespective of the degree and level, students gain hands-on experience doing service projects to tackle community issues and make positive changes. The beauty of service-learning is that something real and concrete is occurring. Learning takes on a new dimension. When students are engaged intellectually and emotionally with a topic, they can light up with a revelation or make a connection between two previously separate ideas. What they have learned in school suddenly matters and engages their minds and their hearts. By inference, they have a tendency to be aware.

4.3.2 Undergraduates Level of Awareness of Entrepreneurship Skills

The result revealed that undergraduates are aware of entrepreneurship skills. By implication, it means that the undergraduates that were part of the study revealed that they know that there are certain skills which are called entrepreneurship skills some of which are customer care, critical thinking, listening, and communicating, strategic thinking and leadership skills, among others. The finding is in line with that of Chang and Wyszomirski (2015); Croci (2016) and Silva (2008) which studies affirmed several students of the higher institutions are aware of skills to galvanize entrepreneurship activities. In the same vein, the study by Cooper, Orrell and Bowden (2010) was also not at variance with the finding of the study.

The study's findings align with the viewpoints expressed by Gbadamosi, Jacob and Pillay, (2022) and Abiodun-Oyebanji (2020) who also reported a high degree of awareness of entrepreneurship skills. These authors submit that a larger percentage of undergraduates are fully aware of entrepreneurship skills due to the issues of breaks in academic calendar occasioned by strikes in the nation's ivory towers as well as the advent of covid-19 pandemic which led to the shutdown of several socio-economic activities including academic engagements in Nigeria institutions. Due to these, several of the students had in one way or the other subscribed to one form of economic engagement in order to cover for lost grounds during these shutdowns while they were waiting for normalcy in university education as well as the society at large.

4.3.3 Stakeholders' Views on Graduates' Possession of Employability Skills and the Need for Service-learning Curriculum

The study revealed that stakeholders (human resource managers and entrepreneurs) had a negative view on graduates' possession of employability skills which justified the need for a service-learning curriculum to expose them to growth and development. By implication, there was a need for service-learning to drive graduates' employability skills. To corroborate this, it was found out that a lot of graduates do not have the required skills to survive the harrowing days of graduate unemployment. Also, the spate of unemployment also drives several graduates to gain knowledge about the professional world, and how to deal with them, especially years after graduating. This is

one of the critical reasons for the utilisation of the service-learning curriculum because it has various hand-on skills which can help graduates build the capacity they need in themselves. The rate of unemployment had made lots of people involved in work that are demeaning or illicit in the society, therefore, the need for service-learning curriculum is of paramount importance as it will benefit people especially graduates who have been exposed to its programme and philosophy to grow, explore, innovate, and produce efficiently. Hence, graduate unemployment (supply of labour) is the social problem which needs to be solved and analysed through an experiential package using the service-learning way.

4.3.4 Service-learning Curriculum for Enhancing Employability Skills Validation

The result shows that the service-learning curriculum for enhancing employability skills was judged good. This implies that the service-learning curriculum was found to be good in building and developing students' employability skills. This is in line with the studies of Fry, Ketteridge and Marshall (2009). Cooper, Orrell and Bowden (2010) and Enos and Troppe (1996). It is sacrosanct that the world is growing increasingly complex at an increasingly rapid pace. The software revolution is reshaping the economy, with 50% of existing jobs expected to be replaced by software and automation. This shift is bifurcating the labour pool. Hence, there is a need for an academic programme that could help spur students' instructions as well as help build capacity in them to create jobs in this global village occasioned by technology. This study was in line with the works of Clayton and Radcliffe (1996) but at variance with the study from Campus Compact (2013). This could be so because making a culture of assessment after the deployment of the curriculum may be difficult. The study also agrees with that of Cantor (1997) whose finding revealed the experiential learning in higher education helps to drive employability skills such as money management, identification of problems, and associated linkages between classroom and community.

4.3.5 Service-learning Curriculum for Enhancing Entrepreneurship Skills Validation

The result shows that the service-learning curriculum for enhancing entrepreneurship skills was adjudged good. This implies that the service-learning curriculum was found to be good in building and developing students' entrepreneurship skills. This is in line with the studies of Silva (2008); Sousa (2014) and Kivunja (2014a) which findings revealed that any programme, learning Subject Matter or curriculum that is experiential can build students' skill sets which is responsible for entrepreneurship engagement. Consequently, the service-learning curriculum can achieve this. As a result of its experiential activities and the synergies among the community, organisations, and the school system in bringing students to bear the necessary experience to triumph in the world of work. The result of this research was also in line with the studies of Abiodun (2010) and Akinbode and Oyelude (2020) whose studies affirmed the need for 21st century skills which are of paramount importance for graduates' employability in several countries of the world including Nigeria.

It is to be noted that with some of these skills, students are likely to engage in activities that will make them productive or self-employed. The submission was corroborated by Barot (2015) who found out that the world of work currently requires a transformative learning which can make students, employers of labour. This means that the type of education students should be exposed to are the ones that can help them function and develop their interest in creating something meaningful for themselves. The submission of Chang and Wyszomirski, (2015) was at variance with the submission of the study. The authors affirmed that with or without the service-learning curriculum, several students at all levels are exposed to several skills such as presentation, problem solving, negotiation, debating system, money management for enhancing their capacity. Though it was not a packaged idea, it finds its way among techniques used in delivering the curriculum experiences to students, especially in the tertiary institutions. This and several other means are what indirectly builds students' entrepreneurship skills.

4.3.6 Stakeholders' Perception of the Subject Matter Adequacy, Suitability and Relevance of the Service-learning Curriculum in Enhancing Employability and Entrepreneurship Skills

The result revealed that stakeholders had a positive perception of the Subject Matter adequacy, suitability, and relevance of the service-learning curriculum in enhancing employability and entrepreneurship skills. This means that stakeholders were satisfied with the curriculum Subject Matter and its objectives as it was tailored to drive undergraduates' employability and entrepreneurship skills. The finding of the study was in line with that of Bringle, Hatcher, and Games (1997); Celio, Durlak, and Dymnicki (2011); Checkoway (2001); Dagenais, Hawley, and Lund (2003); Folgueiras, Luna, and Puig (2013); Babalola (2019).

4.3.7 Undergraduates' Perception of the Service-Learning Curriculum in Promoting Employability and Entrepreneurship Skills

The outcome showed that participants had positive perception of the service-learning curriculum. This implies that participants are predisposed positively to the service-learning curriculum. This may be due to its experiential engagement students are exposed to in building capacity for growth and development. The finding of the study was in line with the works of Okolie, Igwe, and Elom (2019). The studies of Okolie, Igwe and Eneje (2019a); Sharifi, McCombs and Kattelus (2003) and Yorke and Knight (2006) agree with the result of the findings which states that there is positive perception of the service-learning curriculum. It is to be noted that in service-learning, teachers or any significant others use service-learning to make a better change for themselves, the students and the people in general. This is because the school setting today is a mini society where students learn and practice all their life and social skills. Hence, they can easily develop effective service-learning habits to benefit themselves and their own community.

The result of this finding revealed that participants showed positive interest in the service-learning curriculum as agreed with by the works of Bender, Daniels, Lazarus, Naude and Sattar (2006); Berasategi, Alonso and Roman (2016); Cruisinger, Pookulangara, Tran and Kim (2004); Bonar, Buchanan, Fisher and Wechsler (1996)

whose submissions likens service-learning to deep learning which has become one of the most recent growing philosophies and strategies in the last decade. It is now being used in various industrial sectors to make tasks simpler and grow in business as well build necessary synergy with the world of jobs. By implication, the designed service-learning curriculum is not a personalised learning but symbiotic learning and gaining mechanism to a wide and diverse variety of educational programmes, schedules, learning experiences, learning techniques and instructional approaches that can cater for each and every students learning needs, interest and aspirations from diverse backgrounds, age groups, etc. while the host community and the employers of labour can benefit from these services as they learn and provide assistance in addressing socio-economic challenges.

4.3.8 Observers' Assessment of the Efficacy of Service-Learning Curriculum in Promoting Employability and Entrepreneurship Skills Among Undergraduates

The finding revealed that observers' assessment of the efficacy of service-learning curriculum in promoting employability and entrepreneurship skills (EES) among undergraduates was positive. Hence, the observers' rating revealed that service-learning curriculum for promoting employability and entrepreneurship skills (EES) among undergraduates is critical for their functionality in the workplace. This was in line with the studies of Folguez Luna and Puig (2013); Heffernan (2001); Hessels and Naudé (2019); Kolb and Kolb (2011b) and Kezar (2002). For a very long time, the efficacy of service-learning has been called to order as it provides a triangular arrangement. Thus, service-learning is an educational method that combines academic goals with community service. This is because lessons about relevant community issues are combined with existing course Subject Matter to optimize the academic experience are presented before the students.

In line with the result of this study, Kendall (1990); Kolb and Kolb (2005a) and Kolb and Kolb (2009a) also explained that the efficacy of service-learning tends to develop positive concern in students through enhanced metacognitive competences, ability to see, plan and proffer solution to personal and societal problems. This is because it offers students the capability to learn from a classroom arrangement as well as in a wider society. Students could relate with giants in industries as well as acquire new ideas

into their daily activities. The result of this study was also in line with Franklin (2021); Godfrey and Grasso (2000) and Jackson (2012)

The studies by Manring (2012) added to the narration on the efficacy of service-learning in promoting employability and entrepreneurship skills among undergraduates. Stating that teachers will be able to provide real-world examples of the curriculum that they teach. Also, students are given a fresh perspective on what they are learning and can apply it to the projects they will be working on. This is because the entire classrooms make positive changes to the community, and everyone reaps the rewards. Moreso, service-learning is more of a student-centered approach than other forms of community service, such as volunteering. The focus is on student experiences, and the entire service project is designed around providing as much education as possible every step of the way.

4.3.9 Undergraduates' Perception of their Learning Outcomes in the Service-Learning Curriculum after Trial Testing

The result revealed that undergraduates had positive perception of their learning outcomes in the service-learning curriculum after trial testing. This implies that the result on the perception of undergraduates on their learning outcomes in the service-learning curriculum after trial testing came out positive. Because students sampled for the study had positive perception of the learning experiences embedded in the service-learning curriculum. The finding was not at variance with the finding of Buchanan, Baldwin and Rudisill (2002) who discovered that lots of postgraduate students celebrate service-learning programme when it was introduced to them. By inference, they had positive interest in discovering that service-learning is essential for students' academic growth and career development. This could be so as students love to hands-on activities which make them learn at a very fast pace. Service-learning curriculum would provide students with global best practices in terms of solid academic Subject Matter that can be traced to students' productivity, strong self-efficacy, service commitment as well as communication and leadership qualities which are the prerequisites for job security, community development as well as productivity in day-to-day engagements.

The result of this study was also in line with Crutsinger, Pookulangara, Tran and Kim, (2004); Franklin (2021); Binkley, Erstad, Herman, Raizen, Ripley, Miller-Ricci and Rumble (2012); Jackson (2012); Keating, Rishel and Byles (2005) but it was at variance with the research of Ambrose, Bridges, DiPietro, Lovett and Norman (2010) who came up with certain principles of how learning works irrespective of any programme or connectivity with the public sphere. To corroborate, the work done by Bamber and Hankin (2011), who is a firm believer of service-learning, affirmed that the curriculum largely depends on service rendering and the acquisition of requisite contacts, networks and collaboration necessary for the world of jobs. This assertion means performing duty, and that whatever duty one has, it is critical that one needs to serve and learn in that role. The result was inconsistent with the submission of Okolie, Igwe and Elom (2019) that service-learning is not about giving back, but developing oneself as a community member, developing one's intellectual, cultural, or social habits through service and learning. However, this is to benefit, change oneself and the society.

4.3.10 Undergraduates' Perception of the Benefits of Service-learning Curriculum after Trial Testing

The result of the study revealed that undergraduates' perception of the benefits of service-learning curriculum after trial testing was positive. This means that several undergraduates that participated in the study were predisposed positively to the benefit attributed to the deployment of service-learning curriculum during the trial testing. This could be so because students were able to activate their core interest in practical activities embedded in the programme as well as expository arrangements with the workplace, job industries and society. Authors like Sousa (2014); Pitan (2016); Okunuga and Ajeyalemi (2018); Nwankwo (2012); and Jacoby (1996) were also in support of the findings of the study. This could be so due to the current realities as all curriculum experiences are geared towards making significant meaning and impacts in the life of the students. In the global society, the nature of experience for students is driven by the core mandate of self-reliance, self-sufficiency, and interest in proffering solutions to critical issues in the society.

Additionally, the study's findings were consistent with the research conducted by Idaka (2013) which affirmed the need for re-engineering university education for employability in Nigeria. However, studies from Hessels and Naudé (2019) were not also at variance with the findings of the study. This is because the intersection of the fields of entrepreneurship and development is necessary for building capacity in students for the 21st century lives and livelihood.

4.3.11 Undergraduates' Perception of the Need for Service-learning Curriculum after Trial Testing

The result of these findings revealed that undergraduates' perception of the need for service-learning curriculum after trial testing was great. Nearly 95% of undergraduates that participated in the study were really keen on pushing for the inclusion of this curriculum in the school's general program. Critically looking at the findings, it was in line with the studies of Kenworthy-U'ren (2008); Manring (2012); Kuh (2008) and Kolb and Kolb (2011a) whose findings also push for the need for service-learning curriculum as a critical part of higher education. Because these researchers believed that the effectiveness of service-learning curriculum involves suitable implementation of resources to produce desired outcomes. Meanwhile, its effectiveness ensures a process whereby people are well educated, exposed to first-hand industrial experiences and have the opportunity to identify and address the problems in the community. Thus, to produce desired results, one presumes that ineffective service-learning is simply not learning; effective service-learning is a demonstrable engagement that ensures success in not only education but to meet the realities of the people and market experience.

4.3.12 Undergraduates' Perception of the Challenges Observed during Service-learning Curriculum Trial Testing

Looking at the trends of the results of this study, it was revealed that undergraduates encountered some challenges during service-learning curriculum trial testing. This means that there were some issues that popped up during the trying -out stage of the service-learning curriculum. They were poor attitude of participants, weak

understanding of the programme during the initial stage, congested classroom during the implementation and several others. This was in line with the research of Steiner and Watson (2006); Alsubaie (2016); Ambrose, Bridges, DiPietro, Lovett and Norman (2010); Urevbu (1985) and Tomlinson (2017) whose studies affirmed that no programme of this nature deployed that would not face some measure of resistance in terms the logistics, human, materials as well as attitudinal issues.

4.3.13 Undergraduates' Suggestions on the Trial-tested Service-learning Curriculum

The findings revealed that participants suggested that the trial-tested service-learning curriculum should be introduced into all tertiary institutions' undergraduate programs. This implies that the effectiveness of the curriculum in achieving its objectives led to participants' personal, societal, and professional development. Hence, it is important to fully expose Nigerian undergraduates to this curriculum. This submission was in line with Huang and Yang (2004); Gibson, Hauf, Long and Sampson (2011); Bender (2005); Akinyemi, Aimm, Igot, and Ikuenomore (2012); Onuoha and Okam (2011); Skilbeck and Connell (2004) and Akinbode and Oyelude (2020) but was at variance with Yorke and Knight (2006) whose take was that students should not be taken through the rigours of learning by doing and capacity to drive.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter encapsulates a concise overview of the study's findings, conclusions drawn from these findings, and recommendations. Additionally, it highlights the study's contribution to knowledge and suggests potential areas for further research.

5.1 Summary

This study examined the development of a service-learning curriculum for enhancing employability and entrepreneurship skills of university undergraduates in southwestern Nigeria. This study adopted explanatory sequential mixed methods design (Quan-qual). The researcher used quantitative data to explicitly support the qualitative data that were collected. The quantitative aspect involved the collection of data through administration of questionnaires, while the qualitative aspect involved the collection of data through key informant interviews. Eight research questions were raised and answered. The experiential learning theory: human capital theory and John Kerr's model of curriculum design provided the framework for the study.

In this study, a multistage sampling procedure was utilized. The initial stage involved the use of the purposive sampling technique to select three (3) states from the total of six southwestern states. These are Osun, Lagos, and Ogun that have both federal and state universities. Then, a simple random sampling technique was used to select two state universities and two federal universities from the listed states. Also, in conducting the need assessment, simple random sampling was used to select two (2) common faculties each from the selected universities. Then the purposive sampling technique was used to select 1076 undergraduates in 300level in each of the selected faculties because they would have been exposed to entrepreneurship education as a general studies course as stated by National Universities Commission (NUC).

Also, twenty stakeholders; human resources, curriculum experts, service-learning experts and entrepreneurs were interviewed. Additionally, the following are key in the summary of findings:

1. The study found that undergraduates are aware of employability skills, indicating a foundational knowledge base in this area.
2. Results showed that undergraduates are also aware of entrepreneurship skills, demonstrating their understanding of key entrepreneurial concepts.
3. Stakeholders, including human resource managers and entrepreneurs, had a negative view of graduates' possession of employability skills. This justified the need for implementing a service-learning curriculum to bridge this gap.
4. The objectives of the developed service-learning curriculum significantly promoted the acquisition of employability and entrepreneurship skills among undergraduates, validating the curriculum's efficacy.
5. Stakeholders had a positive perception of the adequacy, suitability, and relevance of the service-learning curriculum, supporting its role in enhancing employability and entrepreneurship skills.
6. Undergraduates perceived the objectives of the service-learning curriculum as highly effective in promoting employability and entrepreneurship skills, reflecting their positive reception and engagement.
7. Observers positively assessed the efficacy of the service-learning curriculum in promoting employability and entrepreneurship skills, further endorsing its effectiveness.
8. Undergraduates reported a positive experience and significant benefits from the service-learning curriculum, recommended its adoption, and identified implementation challenges for improvement.

5.2 Conclusion

The study examined the development of a service-learning curriculum in enhancing employability and entrepreneurship skills of university undergraduates in southwestern Nigeria. Thus, it can be deduced that the target audience of the service-learning curriculum is the Nigerian youths because they are the great resource and

cherishable asset that will increase the quality of Nigeria's supply of labour. Hence, this study aimed to incorporate service-learning into tertiary education curriculum in order to avail students, host community, employers of labour, and other interested parties into a new horizon for addressing socio-economic challenges from innovative perspectives in a real-life context. The current reality revealed that graduate employability and self-employment is really essential in turning the tide around the alarming rate of unemployment ravaging the global space. Hence, it can be concluded that the set of competences and character of an individual that enables him or her to perform a certain role which could lead to creation of new ideas for being a great problem solver in tackling societal issues is of top priority.

Furthermore, various researchers and educational administrators have made frantic efforts at addressing some of these challenges, but the results have not been effective. However, the development of a service-learning curriculum in enhancing employability and entrepreneurship skills of university undergraduates in southwestern Nigeria could help tailor students mind towards global best practices where there is socio-economic synergy between and among critical stakeholders in address students' functionality, productivity, and innovation capacity beyond then four walls of the school system. The service-learning curriculum has the capacity to drive undergraduate employability and entrepreneurship competence beyond educational qualification to the acquisition of technical skills, soft skills, attitude, and ambition which are the major drivers of societal change in terms of quality growth and development.

Additionally, many graduates assume that one can be employable simply by possessing the qualification without having one or two requisite learning and organisational experiences as well as competence to drive creativity or innovation. Many graduates also assume that having a degree or diploma is just sufficient for them to be employable which is not so. In today's industry and corporate setting, one must perform job roles by applying technology (technical skills) and have the ability to work with people (which requires soft skills) and basic intelligence quotient (education) with the perfect personality and intelligence. Hence, service-learning curriculum exposes students to critical templates necessary to be used in harnessing potentials needed in the workplace through learning and active service.

5.3 Implications of Findings

1. The adoption of the service-learning curriculum will help stimulate entrepreneurship and employability competences. This is because it will be the tool and philosophy upon which current realities and educational ideas will rest in tertiary institutions.
2. The acceptance and utilisation of service-learning curriculum will also assist in the actualisation of the objectives of yet to be introduced core curriculum minimum acceptable standard (CCMAS) required by the Nigerian Universities Commission. (NUC)
3. The study would provide a critical benchmark to eradicate the old-age mentality of graduates seeking jobs when they would have been exposed to the rudiments of job creation, problem identification and solution.
4. Upon adoption of the service-learning curriculum, the university setting would re-activate its core mandate of producing problem-solvers, thinkers, collaborators as well as innovators and not consumers of archaic ideas who are driven by white collar engagements.
5. Exposing undergraduates to the service-learning curriculum early in their career, will make them embrace the multidisciplinary approach in either taking up the ownership of a business, accept the challenges of the business or display valuable 21st century employability skills needed in the workplace.

5.4 Limitations to the Study

This study is not without some constraints. The study was limited to only southwestern states in Nigeria. The limited number of states, agencies, participants used for the study limited the extent to which the result of this study could be generalized especially when the issues of education and unemployment is global issues. In the same

vein, out of the several agencies associated with issues bothering on education and employment generation, only the NUC was investigated in this study. Some constraints were experienced from respondents, in terms of their poor attitude to responding to questionnaires as well as provision of time to be interviewed. Some participants were not cooperative. Some GES lecturers were also reluctant to spare some time, hence there was insufficient time to cover almost all the topics during the trial testing. However, notwithstanding these limitations and restraints, the findings of the study was able to provide important landmark in the bid to sensitize, teach and give reasons why the service-learning curriculum was able to instil valuable 21st century employability and entrepreneurship skills in Nigerian undergraduates.

5.5 Recommendations

The following recommendations were made.

1. There is a need for the adoption of service-learning curriculum in tertiary institutions in order to enhance undergraduates' employability and entrepreneurship skills.
2. There is a need for adequate collaboration between the triumvirate of school, community, and the world of work.
3. The efficacy of service-learning curriculum rests on adequate provision of human materials, and networks for adoption of its experiential programmes for students. Hence, lecturers need to be sensitised and trained on how to promote and encourage service-learning programmes.
4. Universities and other tertiary institutions should be ready to encourage students in combining both learning and rendering of services to their immediate community while the curriculum is being adopted to instil some valuable skills.
5. Modern mechanisms should be put in place to stimulate students' interest in the world of service-learning, civic participation, gaining valuable employability and entrepreneurship skills.
6. In making efforts to push for the adoption of the service-learning curriculum, teachers and students' sense of social responsibility and citizenship skills would be spurred.

7. The National Universities Commission should further consider the promotion of service-learning curriculum to enhance both employability and entrepreneurship not just the existing entrepreneurship curriculum presently used in Nigerian universities.

5.6 Contributions and Impact of the Research to Advancing Knowledge

The research contributes to knowledge by creating a service-learning curriculum designed to enhance the employability and entrepreneurship skills of university undergraduates in southwestern Nigeria. It provides insights into the effectiveness of such a curriculum in meeting the needs of this demographic and its potential impact on their skill development and future prospects. The study highlights the importance of driving students' employability and entrepreneurship engagement through service-learning and reveals critical mechanisms for effectively utilizing talents and potentials to address personal, professional, and societal problems. Additionally, it bridges the gap between academic learning and practical business linkages, offering a holistic approach to enhancing university students' skills. The curriculum serves as a guide for curriculum developers and policymakers in developing and implementing a service-learning curriculum in a developing nation, addressing unemployment and improving the quality of labor supply.

5.7 Suggestions for Further Research

Future studies could focus on broadening the scope and arrangement of the curriculum. This could involve testing the curriculum with larger sample sizes and in different geographical and cultural contexts to enhance the generalizability of the findings. Additionally, empirical research could be conducted to evaluate the impact of the curriculum on graduates' employability and entrepreneurship skills. Further research might also explore the attitudes of undergraduates towards the service-learning curriculum and how it has influenced their career aspirations and goals.

REFERENCES

- Abiodun, S. O. 2010. Analysis of Mismatch Between Demand and Supply of Skills and University Graduate Unemployment in Nigeria. Unpublished M.Ed Dissertation, Lagos State University.
- Abiodun-Oyebanji O. J., 2015. Employability of Nigerian Graduates, the Role of Stakeholders. *African Higher Education Review (AHER)*, Vol. 9 (1and2), ISSN; 2141-1905
- Akinbode, J. O. and Oyelude O. O. 2020. 21st Century Skills and Fresh Graduates' Employability in Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Management Studies* 20:1, 172-179
- Akinyemi S., Aimm O., Igot B., and Ikuenomore S. 2012. Graduate Turnout and Graduate Employment in Nigeria., *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*. 2. 14
- Alsubaie M. A. 2016. Curriculum Development: Teacher Involvement in Curriculum Development. *Journal of Education and Practice* 7:9
- Ambrose, S., Bridges, M., DiPietro, M., Lovett, M., and Norman, M. 2010. How learning works: 7 research-based principles for smart teaching. San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass.
- Andrews, C. P. 2007. Service-learning: Applications and Research in Business. *Journal of Education for Business*, 83(1), 19-26.
- Babalola S. O. 2019. Application of 4DS of Curriculum Model as Paradigm for Sustainable Development Goals in Nigeria. Ph.D. Thesis, University of Ibadan.
- Babalola S. O., Amosun P. A., and Kolawole C. O. O. 2014. Developing and Validating Political Education Curriculum for Senior Secondary Schools in *Africa Journal of Education*. 18:1
- Bamber, P., and Hankin, L. 2011. Transformative Learning Through Service-Learning: No Passport Required. *Education and Training*, 53 2:3, 190-206
- Barot, H. 2015. Entrepreneurship - A Key to Success. *The International Journal of Business and Management*, 3:1; 163-165.
- Bender, C. J. 2005. How Teacher Educators Can Integrate Service-Learning in The Curriculum. Paper and Workshop presented at the 50th World Assembly of the International Council for the Education of Teaching (ICET), 12-15 July 2005 at the University of Pretoria.
- Bender, C. J. G. 2005. Institutionalization of Service-Learning in Higher Education: how faculties in South Africa find their way. Paper presented at the 5t h Annual

International K-H Service-Learning Research Conference, 13-15 November 2005, East Lansing, Michigan, USA.

- Bender, C. J. G., Daniels, P, Lazarus, J, Naude, L. and Sattar, K. 2006. Service-Learning in the Curriculum: A Resource for Higher Education Institutions. Pretoria, South Africa: Council on Higher Education
- Berasategi, N., Alonso, I., and Roman, G. 2016. Service-learning and Higher Education: Evaluating Students Learning Process from Their Own Perspective. *Procedia Social and Behavioural Sciences*, 228, 424-429.
- Binkley, M., Erstad, O., Herman, J., Raizen, S., Ripley, M., Miller-Ricci, M., and Rumble, M., 2012. "Defining Twenty First Century Skills." In *Assessment and Teaching of 21st Century Skills*, edited by P. Griffin, B. McGaw, and E. Care, 17-66. London: Springer, 2012.
- Boateng K. and Ofori-Sarpong E. 2002. An Analytical Study of the Labour Market for Tertiary Graduates in Ghana. A World Bank/National Council for Tertiary Education and the National Accreditation Board Project. Accra, Ghana.
- Bringle G. R. and Hatcher J. A. 2000. Institutionalization of Service-learning in Higher Education. *The Journal of Higher Education*, 71: 3, 273-290
- Buchanan, A. M., Baldwin, S. C., and Rudisill, M. E. 2002. Service-learning as Scholarship in Teacher Education. *Educational Researcher*, 31:8, 30-36.
- Campus Compact. 2013. Creating a Culture of Assessment: 2012 Campus Compact Annual Member Survey. Boston, MA: Campus Compact.
- Care, E., and Anderson, K. 2016. Skills for a Changing World: How Education Systems Approach Breadth of Skills. Washington, DC: Brookings Institution.
- Carvalho L. and Yeoman P. 2018. Framing Learning Entanglement in Innovative Learning Spaces: Connecting Theory, Design and Practice. *British Educational Research Journal* 44:6, 1120–1137
- Celio, C. I., Durlak, J., and Dymnicki, A. 2011. A Metanalysis of the Impact of Service-Learning on Students. *Journal of Experiential Education*, 34:2, 164- 181
- Chang, W. J., and Wyszomirski, M., 2015. What is Arts Entrepreneurship? Tracking the Development of its Definition in Scholarly Journals. *Journal of Entrepreneurship in the Arts*, 4:2; 11-3
- Checkoway, G. 2001. Renewing the Civic Mission of the American Research University. *Journal of Higher Education*, 72:2, 125.

- Cherniss, C., and Goleman D., Eds. 2001. *The Emotionally Intelligent Workplace: How to Select for, Measure, and Improve Emotional Intelligence in Individuals, Groups, and Organisations* (p. 28). New York, NY: Jossey-bass.
- Clevenger, C. M., and Ozbek, M. E. 2013. Service-Learning Assessment: Sustainability competencies in construction education. *Journal of Construction Engineering and Management*, 139:12
- Cooper, L., Orrell J., and Bowden, M. 2010. *Work Integrated Learning: A guide to Effective practice*. New York, NY: Routledge.
- Croci, C. L. 2016. "Is Entrepreneurship a Discipline?". Honors Theses and Capstones. 296. Cited from <https://scholars.unh.edu/honors/296>. University of New Hampshire Scholar's Repository.
- Crutsinger, C. A., Pookulangara, S., Tran, G., and Kim, D. 2004. Collaborative Service-learning: A Winning Proposition for Industry and Education. *Journal of Family and Consumer Sciences*, 96:3, 46.
- Damoah, Pephrah and Brefo . 2021. Does Higher Education Equip Graduate Students with the Employability Skills Employers Require? The Perceptions of Employers in Ghana *Journal of Further and Higher Education*.
- Dagenais, M., Hawley, D., and Lund J. 2003. Assessing the Effectiveness of a New Curriculum. *Journal of Dental Education*.
- Deakin C. R., Goldspink, C., and Foster, M. 2013. Telling Identities: Learning as Script or Design? Learning Emergency Discussion Paper. Retrieved from: <http://learningemergence.net/events/lasi-dla-wkshp>
- Evans C., Gbadamosi G., Wells J., and Scott I. 2012. Balancing the Yin and Yang: The Role of Universities in Developing Softer Skills in Accountancy. *Industry and Higher Education* 26:1, 63–70.
- Folgueiras B. P., Luna G. E., and Puig L. G. 2013. Service-learning: Study of the Degree of Satisfaction of University Students. *Revista de Educación*, 362, 159-185.
- Franklin, K. E. 2021. Service-learning, Sustainable Development, and the Tourism Sector in Conflict-Affected Bamyan, Afghanistan. Graduate Student Theses, Dissertations, and Professional Papers. Retrieved from 11786. <https://scholarworks.umt.edu/etd/11786>
- Fry, H., Ketteridge, S., and Marshall, S. 2009. *A Handbook for Teaching and Learning in Higher Education: Enhancing Academic Practice* 3rd ed. New York, USA: Routledge

- Furco, A. 2001. Advancing service-learning at research universities. *New Directions for Higher Education*, 2001. 114, 67-78.
- Gbadamosi, T. V. 2018. Where are we? Lecturers' Receptivity of Service-Learning in Nigeria. *People: International Journal of Social Sciences*, 4:2, 466-476.
- Gibson, M., Hauf, P., Long, B., and Sampson, G. 2011. Reflective Practice in Service-learning: Possibilities and Limitations. *Education and Training*, 53:4, 284-296.
- Godfrey, P. C., and Grasso, E. T. 2000. Working for the Common Good: Concepts and Models for Service-Learning in Management. Washington, D. C.: American Association for Higher Education
- Heffernan, K. 2001. Fundamentals of Service-Learning Course Construction. RI: Campus Compact. 2-7, 9. <https://sl.engagement.uconn.edu/sixmodels>
- Hessels, J. and Naudé, W. 2019. The Intersection of the Fields of Entrepreneurship and Development Economics: A Review towards a New View. *Journal of Economic Surveys*, 33: 2; 389-403.
- Honnet, E. P., and Poulson, S. J. 1989. Principles of Good Practice for Combining Service and Learning Wingspread Report Racine Wis: The Johnson Foundation, Inc.
- Hsi Ta Shu Yuan. Huang, T. 2000. Evaluation of Curriculum. Taipei; His Ta Shu Yuan.
- Huang, G. H., and Yang, L. L. 2004. Curriculum Development and Design: Concept and Practice.
- Idaka, I. 2013. Re-engineering University Education for Employability in Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 4;11
- Jackson, D. 2012. Business Undergraduates' Perceptions of their Capabilities in Employability Skills: Implications for Industry and Higher Education. *Industry and Higher Education* 26:5, 345–356.
- Joy, S., and Kolb, D. A. 2009. Are there Cultural Differences in Learning Style? *International Journal of Intercultural Relations*; 33:1, 69-85. Doi: 10.1016/j.ijintrel.2008.11.002
- Keating, R. J., Rishel, T. D., and Byles, C. M, 2005. Mission Impossible? The Challenges of Incorporating Emotional Intelligence and Emotional Competence into an Undergraduate Business Curriculum. *Journal of the Academy of Business Education*, 6,

- Kenworthy-U'ren, A. L. 2008. A Decade of Service-Learning: A Review of the Field Ten Years After JOBE's Seminal Special Issue. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 81(4), 811-822.
- Kezar, A. (2002). Assessing Community Service-learning: Are We Identifying the Right Outcomes? *About Campus*, 7:2, 14-20.
- Kezar, A., and Rhoads, R. A. 2001. The Dynamic Tensions of Service-Learning in Higher Education. *Journal of Higher Education*, 72:2, 148-171.
- Kivunja, C. 2014a. Do You Want Your Students to Be Job-ready with 21st Century Skills? Change Pedagogies: A Paradigm Shift from Vygotskyian Social Constructivism to Critical-thinking, Problem Solving and Siemens' Digital Connectivism. *International Journal of Higher Education*, 3:3, 81 – 91. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5430/ijhe.v3n3p81>
- Kivunja, C. 2014b. Innovative Pedagogies in Higher Education to Become Effective Teachers of 21st Century Skills: Unpacking the Learning and Innovations Skills Domain Of The New Learning Paradigm, *International Journal of Higher Education*, 3:4, 37 – 48. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5430/ijhe.v3n4p37>
- Kolawole, C. O. O. 2015. Curriculum design, Implementation, and Innovation. Ibadan: Ibadan University Press
- Kolb, A. Y. and Kolb, D. A. 2005a. Learning Styles and Learning Spaces: Enhancing Experiential Learning in Higher Education. *Academy of Management Learning and Education*. 4:2, 193-212.
- Kolb, A. Y. and Kolb, D. A. 2006a. Learning Style and Learning Spaces: A Review of the Multidisciplinary Application of Experiential Learning Theory in Higher Education. In Sims, R., and Sims, S. (Eds.). *Learning Styles and Learning: A Key to Meeting the Accountability Demands in Education*. Hauppauge, NY: Nova Publishers.
- Kolb, A. Y. and Kolb, D. A. 2009a. The Learning Way: Méta-Cognitive Aspects of Experiential Learning. Simulation and Gaming: *An Interdisciplinary Journal*. 40:3, 297-327.
- Kolb, A. Y. and Kolb, D. A. 2009b. On Becoming a Learner: The Concept of Learning Identity. In Bamford-Rees *et. al.* (Eds.), *Learning Never Ends: Essays on Adult Learning Inspired by the Life and Work of David O. Justice* Chicago, IL: CAEL Forum and News
- Kolb, A. Y. and Kolb, D. A. 2011a. *The Teaching Role Profile*. Boston, MA: Hay Resources Direct. Retrieved from www.learningfromexperience.com

- Kolb, A.Y., and Kolb, D. A. 2011b. *Experiential Learning Theory Bibliography: Volume 1 1971-2005*. Experience Based Learning Systems, Inc. Cleveland, OH. Retrieved from www.learningfromexperience.com
- Kolb, A.Y., and Kolb, D. A. 2011c. *Experiential Learning Theory Bibliography: 2, 2006-2011*. Experience Based Learning Systems, Inc. Cleveland, OH. Retrieved from www.learningfromexperience.com
- Kolb, D. A. 2007. *The Kolb Learning Style Inventory Version 3.1: LSI Workbook*. Boston, MA: Hay Learning Transformations
- Kuh, G. D. 2008. *High-Impact Educational Practices: What They Are, Who Has Access to Them, and Why They Matter*. Washington, DC: Association of American Colleges and Universities.
- Lester, S. W., Tomkovick, C., Wells, T., and Flunker, L. 2005. Does service-learning add value? Examining the perspectives of multiple stakeholders. *Academy of Management Learning and Education*, 4:3; 278-294.
- Manring, L.S. 2012. *Tapping and Fostering Students' Emotional Intelligence through Service-learning Experiences* Institute of Behavioural and Applied Management
Elon University
- Mattern, D. 2016. An Appraisal of the Importance of Graduates' Language Skills and ERASMUS Experiences. *Industry and Higher Education* 30:5, 355–365.
- McLarty, R. 2005. The Dimensions of Graduate Skills Following SME Employment Experience. *Industry and Higher Education* 19:1, 35–43.
- McNiff, J. 2002. *Action research: Principles and Practice*. New York, NY: Routledge-Falmer.
- Mysore, N., 2003. *Assessment in Higher Education: Partnerships in Learning*. Oxford, Ohio Miami University: 23rd Annual Lilly Conference on College Teaching.
- National Bureau of Statistics 2010. *Labour Force Survey March 2009*. Statistical News: Labour Force Statistics in Nigeria, ISSN 0794 – 1954, 476
- Nwankwo, B.O. 2003. *Institutional Designs and Functionality of African Democracies*, Berlin: Teena
- Nwankwo, O. B. C. 2012. The Challenges of Political Education in Contemporary Nigeria: Re-thinking Mission and Re-planning Strategies. *Education Research Journal*, 2:12, 392-399,

- Okolie, U. C. , Nwosu H. E., Eneje B. C., 2019c. Reclaiming Education: Rising Above Examination Malpractices, and its Contextual Factors on Study Progress in Nigeria. *International Journal of Educational Development* 65: 44–56.
- Okolie, U. C., Igwe P. A. and Elom E. N. 2019. Improving Graduate Outcomes for Technical Colleges in Nigeria. *Australian Journal of Career Development* 28:1, 21–30.
- Okolie, U. C., Igwe P. A., and Eneje B. C., 2019a. Enhancing Graduate Employability: Why Do Higher Education Institutions Have Problems with Teaching Generic Skills? *Policy Futures in Education*. Retrieved from DOI:10.1177/1478210319864824
- Okolie, U. C., Nwosu H. E. and Mlanga S. 2019. Graduate Employability: How the Higher Education Institutions Can Meet the Demand of the Labour Market. *Higher Education, Skills and Work-Based Learning* 9:4,620–636 Retrieved from DOI: 10.1108/HESWBL-09-2018-0089
- Okunuga R. O. and Ajeyalemi D. 2018. Relationship Between Knowledge and Skills in the Nigerian Undergraduate Chemistry Curriculum and Graduate Employability in Chemical-Based Industries. *Industry and Higher Education* 32:3, 183–191
- Olagoke-Oladokun, L. I., Mokhtar, M., Gbadamosi, T. V., and Dugguh, S. I. 2020. Impact Of Service-Learning Among University Students in Nigeria. *PalArch's Journal of Archaeology of Egypt/Egyptology*, 17:7, 4947-4958.
- Onuoha, J. C. and Okam, C. C. 2011. Repositioning Social Studies Education in Nigeria: Issues and Challenges. *Nigerian Journal of Social Studies and Civic Education*. 1:1
- Papamarcos, S. D. 2005. Giving Traction to Management Theory: Today's Service-Learning. *Academy of Management Learning and Education*, 4(3), 325-335.
- Passarelli, A. M., and Kolb, D. A. 2012. Using Experiential Learning Theory to Promote Student Learning and Development in Programs of Education Abroad. In M. Vande Berg, M. Page, and K. Lou (Eds.), *Sterling, VA: Stylus. Student Learning Abroad*. 137-161.
- Pitan O. S. 2016. Towards Enhancing University Graduate Employability in Nigeria. *Journal of Sociology and Social Anthropology* 7:1, 1–11.
- Pitan O. S. 2017. Graduate Employees' Generic Skills and Training Needs. *Higher Education, Skills and Work-Based Learning* 7:3, 290–303.
- Pitan O. S. and Adedeji S. O. 2012. Skills Mismatch Among University Graduates in the Nigeria Labor Market. *US-China Education Review*. *US-China Education Review*, ISSN 1548-6613. A:1 90-98.

- Salimbene, F. P., Buono, A. F., LaFarge, V. S., and Nurick, A. J. 2005. Service-Learning and Management Education: The Bentley Experience. *Academy of Management Learning and Education*, 4:3, 336-344.
- Sharifi, M., McCombs, G. B., and Kattelus, S. C. 2003. Using Service-Learning to Develop Competencies in a Capstone Accounting Course. *Journal of the Academy of Business Education*, 89-100.
- Silva, E. 2008. Measuring skills for the 21st century. Washington, DC: Education Sector. Available: www.educationsector.org/usr_doc/MeasuringSkills.pdf
- Skilbeck and Connell 2004. Teachers for the Future - The Changing Nature of Society and Related Issues for the Teaching Workforce.
- Sousa, M. 2014. Entrepreneurial Skills Development. *Recent Advances in Applied Economics* 135-139
- Steiner, S. D., and Watson, M. A. 2006. The Service-Learning Component in Business Education: The Values Linkage Void. *Academy of Management Learning and Education*, 5:4, 422-434
- Tomlinson, M. 2017. Forms of Graduate Capital and Their Relationship to Graduate Employability. *Education Training* 59:4, 338–352.
- Yorke, M. and Knight, P. 2006. Learning and Employability. The Higher Education Academy. http://www.employability.ed.ac.uk/documents/staff/heabriefings/esect-3_embedding_employability_into_curriculum.pdf

APPENDIX I
Service-Learning Curriculum For Employability And Entrepreneurship Skills Need
Assessment Questionnaire

Instruction: Please rate statement by putting a tick (√) appropriately in the space provided

S/N	ITEM	Very Much Aware	Aware	Less Aware	Not Aware
	Employability Skills To what extent:				
1	Are you aware that 21st century skills by UNESCO are elements needed to be employable?				
2	Are you aware that 21st century job vacancies require the ability to display knowledge on information communication technology?				
3	Do you know that employers check your social media profile before being recruited?				
4	Are you aware that going through a personality test is part of recruitment processes in the workplace?				
5	Are you aware that to get 21st century jobs, you should be able to work in a team?				
6	Do you know that to get recommendations in the workplace, you should avoid conflicts?				
7	Do you know that 21st century jobs require frequent collaboration with colleagues?				
8	Are you aware that recent job vacancies require the ability to proffer solutions to workplace challenges?				
9	Do you know that before securing a job, you must be able to think critically before solving issues?				

	Entrepreneurship Skills				
	To what extent:				
10	Do you know that creation of jobs requires the ability to take risks?				
11	Are you aware that to be a job creator, you should have the capacity to think strategically?				
12	Are you aware that entrepreneurs should be able to make good use of opportunities?				
13	Are you aware that an employer should be able to make good decisions?				
14	Do you know that an entrepreneur should be able to convey ideas in a clear term?				
15	Do you know that entrepreneurs should be able to recognise opportunities?				
16	Do you know that a job creator should be able to lead a team?				
17	Are you aware that entrepreneurs should have the ability to resolve conflicts among people?				
18	Do you know that entrepreneurs draw a timeline to meet their targets?				

Section C: Undergraduates Skill Possession Rating Scale

Instruction: Please rate the statement by putting a tick (√) appropriately in the space.

S/N	ITEMS	Great Extent	An Extent	Little Extent	Not at All
	To what extent				
1	Do you proffer possible solutions to problems?				
2	Do you make good decisions?				
3	Do you have the ability to lead a				

	team?				
4	Do you make good use of opportunities?				
5	Do you like to introduce new and unique ideas to people?				
6	Can you resolve conflicts among people?				
7	Do you engage in systemic thinking?				
8	Do you have the ability to think strategically?				
9	Do you like to think critically when you have an issue at hand?				
10	Do you listen to people's opinion before you react?				
11	Do you have the ability to present your ideas to an audience?				
12	Are you good with calculation of figures?				
13	Do you believe in ethical standards at work place?				
14	Do you have the ability to network among people?				
15	Do you like to take business risks				
16	Do you have the ability to manage a business				
17	Do you get tired of learning				
18	Do you have the ability to assess situations				
19	Do you like to sustain relationships				

20	Are you open to learn new ideas				
21	Are you good with the use of information technology				
22	Do you have the ability to convince people to buy my ideas				

APPENDIX IIA
HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGERS INTERVIEW GUIDE

Overview

Precisely, this instrument will encompass the opinions and issues identified by stakeholders, along with the strategies to address these problems through a service-learning curriculum.

Section A: Demographic Information

The Interviewer politely asks for the Interviewee to give a brief introduction of him/herself. The Interviewer fills in the following demographic information.

Name of Interviewee	
Status	
Name of Organisation	
Place of Interview	
Date of Interview	

Section B: The Interviewer politely and appropriately probes further to elicit more information to the under-listed questions.

Questions

- 1) What is your view on graduates' unemployability these days?
- 2) Do you think there is a need for a curriculum to capture 21st-century skills stated by UNESCO?
- 3) What are the skills set employers expect from a university graduate?
- 4) In your opinion, what do you consider to be the challenges of graduates' unemployability?
- 5) Can you please suggest possible solutions to these problems?

Appendix IIB
ENTREPRENEURS INTERVIEW GUIDE

Overview

This instrument will address the opinions and issues identified by stakeholders, outlining the methods by which these problems should be tackled through a service-learning curriculum.

Section A: Demographic Information

The Interviewer politely asks for the Interviewee to give a brief introduction of him/herself. The Interviewer fills in the following demographic information.

Name of Interviewee	
Status	
Department	
Name of Organisation	
Place of Interview	
Date of Interview	

Section B: The Interviewer politely and appropriately probes further to elicit more information to the under listed questions.

Questions

- 1) Do you think graduates understand the elements of entrepreneurship skills?
- 2) What are the skills set an entrepreneur should be exposed to?
- 3) Do you think that if graduates are exposed to experiential learning during university education, they will solve business problems using new approaches?
- 4) In your opinion, what do you consider to be the challenges of an entrepreneur?
- 5) Can you please suggest possible solutions to these problems?

APPENDIX III

Service-Learning Curriculum to Enhance Employability Skills Validation Rating Scale

Dear Stakeholder,

This tool was created to evaluate the sufficiency and pertinence of the goals and substance of the recently formulated service-learning curriculum aimed at improving employability skills. Please evaluate the feasibility of the curriculum using the rating scale provided. Thank you.

Section A: Participant Details

Instruction: Kindly supply the information

Name of Institution:.....

Gender: Male () Female()

Qualification:.....

Area of Specialization:.....

Section B: Skills Validation Rating Scale

Instruction: Please rate the statements by putting a tick (✓) appropriately in the space provided.

S/N	ITEM	Not at All	A Little	Quite a Bit	A Great Deal
Curriculum Objectives					
Does:					
1	The stated curriculum objectives cover relevant experiences needed in enhancing undergraduates' employability skills				
2	The curriculum objectives will reveal the competencies undergraduates will acquire while exposed to this curriculum				

3	Service-learning approach will be useful in facilitating relevant employability skills undergraduates need upon graduation				
4	The goals outlined within the service-learning curriculum encompass pertinent competencies crucial for acquiring employment opportunities				
Curriculum Subject Matters					
5	The service-learning curriculum Subject Matter is structured to address the cultivation of employability skills pertinent to the 21st century for undergraduates				
6	The Subject Matter of service-learning curriculum considers the personal development of undergraduates				
7	The Subject Matter of service-learning curriculum considers the social development of undergraduates				
8	The Subject Matter of service-learning curriculum considers the intellectual development of undergraduates				
9	The learners' response to the curriculum suggests that the Subject Matter is suitable in enlightening undergraduates on the essential entrepreneurship skills required upon graduation.				
10	Will undergraduates be able to acquire employability skills through the service-learning curriculum?				
11	The Subject Matter of service-learning curriculum will give undergraduates better enlightenment in understanding realities of the workplace				
12	The Subject Matter of service-learning curriculum will achieve stated learners' outcome				
13	Service activities specified in the curriculum will be adequate in enhancing employability skills				
14	The Subject Matter of service-learning curriculum will				

	expose students to the preparation for the world of work				
15	The Subject Matters of this curriculum address how undergraduates can identify and pursue their career interests				
16	The Subject Matter of this curriculum gives undergraduates the opportunity to gather experience from multiple sources to aid their employability skills				
17	The Subject Matter of this curriculum emphasises on how service commitments can enhance undergraduates' employability skills				
18	The Subject Matter of this curriculum covers the important connections between career interests and acquisition of 21st century employability skills?				

APPENDIX IV

**Service-Learning Curriculum to Enhance Entrepreneurship Skills Validation
Rating Scale**

Dear Stakeholder,

This tool is developed to assess the sufficiency and relevance of the goals and Subject Matters within the recently created service-learning curriculum aimed at improving entrepreneurship skills. Please evaluate the feasibility of the curriculum using the rating scale provided. Thank you.

Section A: Demographic Details

Instruction: Kindly supply the information

Name of Institution:.....

Gender: Male () Female()

Qualification:.....

Area of Specialization:.....

Section B: Skills Validation Rating Scale

Instruction: Please rate statements by putting a tick (✓) appropriately in the space provided.

S/N	ITEM	Not at All	A Little	Quite a Bit	A Great Deal
Curriculum Objectives					
Does:					
1	The stated curriculum objectives cover relevant experiences needed in enhancing undergraduates' entrepreneurship skills				
2	The objectives reveal the competencies undergraduates will acquire while exposed to the curriculum				
3	Service-learning approach to be used in this curriculum will facilitate relevant entrepreneurship skills needed by undergraduates upon graduation				

4	The objectives of the curriculum cover relevant competencies needed to promote entrepreneurship				
Curriculum Subject Matters					
5	The service-learning curriculum Subject Matter focuses on nurturing 21st-century entrepreneurship skills among undergraduates.				
6	The service-learning curriculum Subject Matter emphasizes the personal development of undergraduates				
7	The service-learning curriculum Subject Matter highlights the social development of undergraduates.				
8	The service-learning curriculum Subject Matter promotes the intellectual development of undergraduates.				
9	Feedback from learners indicates that the curriculum Subject Matter effectively enlightens undergraduates on essential entrepreneurship skills required post-graduation.				
10	Is the service-learning curriculum conducive for undergraduates to acquire entrepreneurship skills through exposure?				
11	The Subject Matter of service-learning curriculum will give undergraduates better enlightenment in understanding realities of job creation				
12	The Subject Matter of service-learning curriculum will achieve stated learners' outcome				
13	Service activities specified in the curriculum will be adequate in enhancing entrepreneurship skills				
14	The Subject Matter of service-learning curriculum will expose students to required factors involved in creating jobs				
15	The Subject Matters of this curriculum address how				

	undergraduates can identify and pursue their career interests				
16	The Subject Matter of this curriculum gives undergraduates the opportunity to gather experience from multiple sources to aid their entrepreneurship skills				
17	The Subject Matter of this curriculum emphasises on how service commitments can enhance undergraduates' entrepreneurship skills?				
18	The Subject Matter of this curriculum covers the important connections between career interests and acquisition of 21st century entrepreneurship skills?				

APPENDIX V

Service-Learning Curriculum for Employability and Entrepreneurship Skills Participants' Perception Scale

Dear Participant,

This survey will gather your viewpoints regarding the comprehensiveness and specific elements of the newly devised service-learning curriculum aimed at enhancing employability and entrepreneurship skills. Your unbiased responses will aid the researcher in refining the curriculum's practicality and functionality. Please utilize the provided rating guide. Your input is greatly appreciated. Thank you for your participation.

Section A: Demographic Data

Instruction: Kindly supply the information

Name of Institution:.....

Gender: Male () Female()

Department:.....

Faculty:.....

Section B: Participants Perception of the Service-Learning Curriculum

Instruction: Please rate the statement by putting a tick (✓) appropriately in the space provided

S/N	ITEM	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1	The service-learning curriculum is actively engaging				
2	The skills I have learnt are needed upon graduation				
3	The objectives of the curriculum are realisable				
4	The teaching and learning activities involved in this curriculum is relevant in the				

	21st century				
5	What I have learnt exposes me to the elements of 21st century skills needed as stated by UNESCO				
6	Topics presented in this curriculum are logically arranged				
7	What I was taught addresses the employability and entrepreneurship skills needed upon graduation				
8	Exposure to this curriculum is sufficient in developing my skills in securing a job				
9	Participation in this curriculum try-out has exposed me to the acquisition of EES				
10	Participation in acquisition of EES will equip me in giving out the best in the workplace				
11	Participation in this curriculum has exposed me to the rudiment and practical knowledge needed in the creation of jobs				
12	The curriculum has detailed the skills and competencies needed upon university graduation?				
13	This curriculum lay more emphasis on actively engaging in service commitments and projects?				
14	This curriculum enlightens me on connections between career development and acquisition skills?				

APPENDIX VI

Service-Learning Curriculum for Employability and Entrepreneurship Skills Participants' Learning Outcome Interview Guide

1. What are your experiences in the service-learning activities?
2. In what ways have you benefited from this curriculum?
3. Why do you think Nigeria undergraduates need this curriculum?
4. How will you summarise the challenges you observed during the curriculum try out?
5. What are your suggestions on improving these challenges?

APPENDIX VII

Service-Learning Curriculum Observers Rating Scale

Dear Observer,

This tool is specifically crafted to evaluate the sufficiency and effectiveness of the curriculum in fostering the enhancement of employability and entrepreneurship skills among undergraduates, both during and after the trial period. Your evaluation of the curriculum's efficacy using the rating guide provided is highly valued. Thank you for your participation and input.

Section A: Participant Data

Instruction: Kindly supply the information

Name of Observer (optional):.....

Gender: Male () Female()

Qualification:.....

Area of Specialization:.....

Section B: Service-Learning Curriculum Observers Rating Scale

Instruction: Please rate statement by putting a tick (✓) appropriately in the space provided

S/N	ITEM	Very Effective	Effective	Less Effective	Not Effective
	How effective:				
1	Do you think this curriculum has aided participants' skills in securing employment opportunities upon graduation?				
2	Do you consider the curriculum to have aided participants' ability to do new things?				
3	Do you think the curriculum has aided participant's ability to collaborate in a team?				
4	Does the Subject Matters of this curriculum have exposed				

	participants adequately to information needed to keep a job?				
5	Does the Subject Matters of this curriculum have exposed participants adequately to information needed to create a job?				
6	Has the learning outcome of the curriculum has shaped participants' view in addressing workplace challenges?				
7	Do you consider the curriculum experiences useful in exposing participants to hands-on experience?				
8	Do you think this curriculum has exposed participants to have various perspectives to teamwork issues?				
9	Do you think this curriculum has exposed participants to make decisions successfully?				
10	Do you think this curriculum has aided participants' ability to identify problems and proffer solutions?				

Section B: Observers, please tick as appropriate.

S/N	Concept	Adequate		Suitable		Relevance	
		Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No
1	Curriculum Objectives						
2	Curriculum Subject Matter						
3	Service-Learning Activities						
4	Learning Outcomes						
5	Reflection Activities						
6	Style of Evaluation						

APPENDIX VIII
Service-Learning Curriculum in Enhancing Employability and Entrepreneurship
Skills of University Undergraduates

Introduction

Service-learning is an educational approach that merges academic learning with career goals and pathways, engaging students in service-oriented activities. These students participate in projects with a defined timeframe that contribute positively to both the community and the students involved. This curriculum is based on the principles of equipping students with skills required in being employable, being business oriented, ability to create jobs and adequately prepare them with skills required of an employee or an employer. This course should be taught as a required course during the first and second semesters to 300 level university undergraduates.

Course Component Development

Ololade Serifat Omosunlade crafted this course Subject Matter as part of the requirements for the attainment of a Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D.) degree at University of Ibadan. The developed curriculum's objective is to enrich students' learning experiences through practical, experiential learning methods, offering a comprehensive educational journey that readies students for successful entry into the workforce and fosters a promising career path.

Philosophy of the Course

The philosophy of this curriculum is to present service-learning as a course that has relevance in empowering undergraduates with adequate employability and entrepreneurship skills which can prepare them for a bright career future, world of work and community development.

Objectives of the Course

The objectives of the service-learning curriculum include to enable students:

1. Acquire entrepreneurship and employability skills.
2. Define a professional interest area and research career options by taking on service initiatives.
3. Leverage academic expertise and critical-thinking abilities to address actual community needs.

4. Identify service-learning possibilities for entrepreneurial and professional development.
5. Develop strong work ethics.
6. Make a thoughtful contribution to community improvement.
7. Create a shared vision to accomplish objectives with others.

Teaching Pedagogy

In this curriculum, the service-learning approach is the key pedagogy to be used. Service-learning is a teaching and learning strategy that is basically centred on the learners. It is an experiential form of learning; it focuses on their experience, interest, and opinions because they learn by doing. It is a hands-on approach whereby learners can learn and develop valuable skills through active participation in a service that is conducted in their communities or immediate environment.

Assessment Techniques

Service-learning utilises a flexible outlook in teaching and learning, it blends academic learning and real-world experiences. Therefore, the assessment methods should be diverse and tailored to differentiate based on students' grasp of Subject Matter knowledge, their capacity to comprehend, and mastery of the subject matter. Based on these, interest inventories, journal entries, meetings with partners, blog posts, partnership agreements, electronic and written communication, community presentation, podcasts, slideshow presentation etc. are some of the assessment techniques applicable to this curriculum.

Learning Outcomes

On the successful completion of this curriculum, service-learning courses will help students:

1. Use academic expertise and critical-thinking techniques to address actual community issues.
2. Exhibit a deeper comprehension of the course's unique learning objectives that is appropriate for the situation.

3. Critically consider the connections between theory and practice, learning within and outside of the classroom, and other aspects of their experience.
4. Understand how each students' discipline can provide for the needs of the community.
5. Understand how service commitments can enhance employment and entrepreneurship skills.
6. Comprehend and appreciate the value of being a responsive member of the society.
7. Recognise the importance of universities mission and vision to address the needs of their respective community.

Service-Learning Experience

1. The teacher will specify one or more learning goals for the course that the students will strive toward by performing community service or service-learning.
2. The faculty member and community partner will collaborate to identify community needs and then construct a service-learning opportunity to meet those needs.
3. To achieve the specific service-learning course objective, service-learning activities will be incorporated into course work and used as the pedagogical strategy (s). As a result, all course participants will take part in the service-learning activities.
4. The service-learning experience will be significant, ongoing, and involve active student participation throughout the semester.

Cognitive Development

- **Discipline Specific Knowledge:** Service-learning activities give students the chance to apply their classroom learning to real-world situations. Through practical work with non-profit community organizations, students have the chance to apply their discipline-specific expertise. Engaged experiential learning helps students remember more material, participate more actively in class discussions, and develop their confidence in their ability to apply what they have learned in real-world situations.
- **Epistemological growth:** By giving students a larger social context in which to comprehend the structural concerns that members of society face, service-learning opportunities push students to deepen their grasp of social justice issues. Students are encouraged to think about numerous perspectives of the same subject through

varied social interactions, dialogues, and critical reflection exercises, which strengthens their cognitive abilities and epistemic growth.

- **Moral judgement:** Students get a deeper understanding of themselves in connection to others through service-learning activities. They are obliged to re-evaluate their beliefs and personal values, as well as how they judge other people, as a result of the conversations and activities they partake in. Students frequently acquire a care ethic and a feeling of citizenship that permeate all facets of their lives as a result of their interactions with people who are in need of assistance.

Psychosocial Development

- **Sense of Purpose:** Students can explore academic majors and/or get practical experience for their career ambitions through service-learning initiatives. Often, taking part in service-learning and engaging in critical reflection exercises together with students enables them to better understand their own identities, values, and potential career interests. Many students claim that these pursuits have aided them in discovering their "calling in life."
- **Cultural Identity Development:** Students will have the chance to interact with persons who are different from themselves in terms of values, lifestyle, religion, race/ethnicity, and sexual orientation by taking part in service-learning activities. These experiences help students become more aware of their own cultural identities and inspire them to cultivate a conscious appreciation for diversity when accompanied with the right critical reflection exercises.
- **Sense of Interdependence:** Students learn more about their individual abilities and how they may help a group or community achieve its objectives by taking part in group activities. Students learn the value of community cooperation and their place in society by working side-by-side with some non-profit agency professionals and their clients.

Curriculum Subject Matters

1. Decision Making
2. Financial Analysis
3. Communication
4. Presentation

5. Risk Management
6. Critical Thinking
7. Networking
8. Conflict Resolution
9. Systematic Thinking
10. Leadership
11. Innovation
12. Creativity
13. Business Management
14. Strategic Thinking
15. Problem Solving
16. Social Media Ethics
17. Self-Management
18. Information Communication Technology
19. Resources Management
20. Work Ethics
21. Emotional Intelligence
22. Marketing
23. Time Management
24. Interpersonal
25. Capacity for lifelong Learning
26. Teamwork or Collaboration

Week One - Lecture

The Concept of Decision Making

Explicit objectives

- Elucidate the idea of decision making.
- Provide the elements involved in decision making processes (positive/negative)
- Identify strategies to make good decisions and avoid bad decision making.
- Explain extensively.
- Explain the use of decision trees.

- Psychological biases that affect decision

Subject Matter

This lesson offers a diverse array of knowledge essential to empower learners in attaining the established objectives.

- Elaborating on the concept of decision making
- Components of making decisions
- The benefits of making decision trees

Instructional Approach

Enhancing decision-making skills through service-learning by conducting a thorough analysis of critical issues.

Learning Activities

- Engage the learners in identifying the problem to be solved.
- Make learners gather relevant information amongst themselves.
- Let learners brainstorm possible solutions.
- Let learners identify potential consequences.
- Engage the learners in making a choice.
- Make learners take action for the choice made.

Materials/Resources

Decision making worksheets, Flash cards, Video clips e.t.c.

Assessment

- Observation of students' participation, interaction, and interconnection to issues raised while in the classroom.
- Brainstorming sessions to raise solutions to classroom issues.

Service-learning project

Activities can be organised among students on

- a. Social Justice Project: Develop a social justice project that challenges students to make decisions about how to address a social issue in their community. Students can learn about decision making frameworks, such as ethical decision making and the cost-benefit analysis and apply these frameworks to make informed decisions.

- b. Community Service Project: Develop a community service project that challenges students to make decisions about how to best serve their community. Students can learn about decision making models, such as the rational decision-making model and the incremental decision-making model and use these models to make effective decisions.
- c. Environmental Sustainability Project: Develop an environmental sustainability project that challenges students to make decisions about how to promote sustainability in their community. Students can learn about decision making strategies, such as group decision making and brainstorming, and use these strategies to make informed decisions.
- d. Business Ethics Project: Develop a business ethics project that challenges students to make decisions about ethical issues faced by businesses. Students can learn about decision making processes, such as the normative decision-making model and the intuitive decision-making model and apply these processes to make ethical decisions.
- e. Political Advocacy Project: Develop a political advocacy project that challenges students to make decisions about political issues facing their community. Students can learn about decision making tools, such as decision trees and scenario analysis, and use these tools to make informed decisions about political issues.

Week Two - Lecture

The Concept of Financial Analysis

Explicit Objectives

- Explain the components of financial analysis.
- Give the proper analysis of financial modelling and financial management.
- Identify how to compute financial statements and financial reports.

Subject Matter

This lesson offers a diverse array of knowledge essential to empower learners in attaining the established objectives.

- The concept of financial analysis
- Components of financial analysis
- Financial modelling and financial management

- Computation of financial statements and financial reports

Instructional Approach

Learning financial analysis skills using the service-learning approach where students are taught in the class, and they also learn by practising what has been learnt.

Learning Activities

- Engage the learners in identify the industry characteristics.
- Make learners gather information about the company's strategies.
- Let learners analyse the profit and risk involved.
- Let learners identify potential consequences.
- Let learners value the firm.

Materials/Resources

Flash cards, Video clips e.t.c.

Assessment

- Observation of students' participation, interaction, and interconnection to issues raised on financial analysis.
- Brainstorming sessions to raise solutions to classroom issues.

Service-learning project

Activities can be organised among students on

- a. **Financial Literacy Program:** Develop a financial literacy program that teaches students about personal finance, including budgeting, saving, investing, and managing debt. The program can include workshops on financial analysis, such as how to read financial statements and calculate financial ratios.
- b. **Investment Club:** Develop an investment club that teaches students about investment strategies and financial analysis. Students can research different investment options, analyze financial statements, and make investment decisions as a group.
- c. **Business Plan Competition:** Develop a business plan competition that challenges students to create a business plan and pitch it to a panel of judges.

Students can learn about financial analysis, including forecasting revenues and expenses, and using financial ratios to assess the financial health of a business.

- d. Entrepreneurship Project: Develop an entrepreneurship project that challenges students to start a business. Students can learn about financial analysis, including how to calculate break-even points, perform sensitivity analysis, and evaluate the profitability of a business.
- e. Financial Consulting Project: Develop a financial consulting project that pairs students with local businesses or non-profit organizations to provide financial analysis and recommendations. Students can learn about financial analysis, including how to analyse financial statements, evaluate financial performance, and develop recommendations for improvement.

Week Three - Lecture

Communication and Presentation

Explicit Objectives

- Explain the components involved in displaying good communication and presentation skills.
- Explain how to communicate effectively.
- Identify the relationship between communication and presentation.

Subject Matter

This lesson offers a diverse array of knowledge essential to empower learners in attaining the established objectives.

- The concept of communicating effectively
- Components involved while presenting.
- Presentation skills
- Communication skills

Instructional Approach

Classroom discussions, group interaction, teamwork,

Learning Activities

Teacher

- Division of class into groups to interact with each other.
- Give class an exercise that will involve presenting to the entire class.

Students

- Engage in class interactions and discussions.
- Contribute actively while preparing for the class presentation.

Materials/Resources

Relevant books, online resources, flash cards, video clips e.t.c.

Assessment

- Observation of students' participation, interaction, and interconnection to issues raised during class presentation.
- Brainstorming sessions and active involvement to raise solutions to issues raised after the presentation.

Service-learning project

In collaboration with media experts, resources will be made available to support.

- a. **Public Speaking Program:** Develop a public speaking program that teaches students how to create and deliver effective speeches. The program can include workshops on speechwriting, delivery techniques, and overcoming nervousness.
- b. **Community Outreach Campaign:** Develop a community outreach campaign that challenges students to create a persuasive message and deliver it to the community. Students can learn how to craft a compelling message, deliver it in different formats such as a public speech or presentation, and evaluate the effectiveness of their campaign.
- c. **Video Production Project:** Develop a video production project that challenges students to create a video to communicate an important message. The project can include workshops on scriptwriting, storyboarding, filming, and editing.
- d. **Social Media Campaign:** Develop a social media campaign that teaches students how to create and deliver effective messages using social media platforms. The project can include workshops on social media strategy, writing effective social media posts, and creating visual Subject Matter.
- e. **Journalism Project:** Develop a journalism project that teaches students how to conduct interviews and write news stories. Students can learn how to ask effective

questions, research topics, and write compelling stories. They can then share their work through a school newspaper or website.

Week Four - Lecture

Risk Management

Explicit Objectives

- Explain the components involved in systematic risk management process.
- Identify and analyse the risk.
- Monitor and review the risk.

Subject Matter

This lesson offers a diverse array of knowledge essential to empower learners in attaining the established objectives.

- The concept of risk management cycle
- Categorization of risks
- Risk Assessment

Instructional Approach

Brainstorming sessions,

Learning Activities

Teacher

- Division of class into groups to interact with each other.
- Give class an exercise that will involve presenting to the entire class.

Students

- Engage in class interactions and discussions.
- Contribute actively while preparing for the class presentation.

Materials/Resources

Relevant books, online resources, flash cards, video clips e.t.c.

Assessment

- Observation of students' participation, interaction, and interconnection to issues raised during class presentation.
- Brainstorming sessions and active involvement to raise solutions to issues raised after the presentation.

Service-learning project

In collaboration with risk analysts, resources will be made available to support.

- a. Disaster Preparedness Project: Develop a disaster preparedness project that helps students assess and mitigate the risks associated with natural disasters or other emergencies. Students can research potential hazards in their community, develop an emergency response plan, and identify ways to minimize the risks to individuals and the community.
- b. Environmental Restoration Project: Develop an environmental restoration project that helps students assess and mitigate the risks associated with pollution or other environmental hazards. Students can research the impact of pollution on the environment and public health, develop a plan to restore an affected area, and identify ways to prevent future pollution.
- c. Financial Planning Workshop: Develop a financial planning workshop that helps students assess and manage financial risks. Students can learn about budgeting, investing, and managing debt, and develop strategies for financial risk management.
- d. Health and Safety Training: Develop a health and safety training program that helps students assess and manage risks associated with physical and mental health. Students can learn about topics such as first aid, mental health, and substance abuse, and develop strategies for risk management.
- e. Sports Safety Project: Develop a sports safety project that helps students assess and manage the risks associated with sports participation. Students can learn about topics such as concussion prevention, injury prevention, and equipment safety, and develop strategies for risk management.

Week Five - Lecture

Critical Thinking

Explicit Objectives

- Explain the importance of being open minded.
- Encourage students to give their assumptions on issues.
- Encourage students to think and give reasons for their answers.
- Encourage students to be open to conflicting views.
- Ask students questions on “why”.

Subject Matter

This lesson offers a diverse array of knowledge essential to empower learners in attaining the established objectives.

- Open mindedness
- Giving out intelligent assumption on issues
- Ability to give meaningful answers to questions.

Instructional Approach

Brainstorming sessions, Debate, quizzes

Learning Activities

Teacher

- Questioning the students and encourage them to be open minded in giving out answers.
- Give an exercise to the class that will make them think and contribute to issues.

Students

- Engage the class in thinking about their own assumption.
- Engage the class in contributing actively.

Materials/Resources

Relevant books on bloom’s taxonomy, website debates

Assessment

- Observation of students’ participation, interaction, and interconnection to issues raised during class.

- Brainstorming sessions and active involvement to raise solutions to issues raised in class.

Service-learning project

Activities can be organised among students through:

- a. **Community Problem-Solving:** Develop a project that challenges students to identify and solve a problem in their community. This project can involve researching the problem, developing and evaluating potential solutions, and implementing the chosen solution. Students will need to use critical thinking skills to analyze the problem, evaluate potential solutions, and make decisions based on evidence and reasoning.
- b. **Debate Club:** Develop a debate club that encourages students to research and analyze complex issues from multiple perspectives. Students will need to use critical thinking skills to evaluate evidence, make logical arguments, and defend their position in a debate.
- c. **Current Events Discussion Group:** Develop a current events discussion group that encourages students to read and analyze news articles from a variety of sources. Students will need to use critical thinking skills to evaluate the credibility of sources, identify bias, and analyze the implications of current events.
- d. **Service-Learning Reflections:** Develop reflection prompts that encourage students to critically analyze their service-learning experiences. Students can reflect on the impact of their service on the community, identify areas for improvement, and develop action plans for future service projects.
- e. **Ethics in Action:** Develop a project that challenges students to consider ethical dilemmas and develop solutions. Students can explore ethical frameworks, analyze case studies, and develop their own ethical guidelines for decision making.

Week Six - Lecture

Networking

Explicit Objectives

- The ability to communicate.
- Having the ability to speak publicly.
- Having the ability to communicate with others.

- Being Empathetic.

Subject Matter

This lesson offers a diverse array of knowledge essential to empower learners in attaining the established objectives.

- Listening actively to issues.
- Being able to stay positive in all situations.
- Ability to display social skills.

Instructional Approach

Brainstorming sessions, Debate, quizzes

Learning Activities

Teacher

- Make students practise on improving their communication habits.
- Ask students the right questions that can help them build trust and open lines of communication. Keep the questions positive and focused on the issues at hand.

Students

- Engage the class in paying attention to the body language of people they speak to
- Engage the class in attending events that will be beneficial to their growth.
- Students should have the ability to follow up on new friends made.

Materials/Resources

Relevant books on networking and attending events.

Assessment

- Observation of students that listen and engage in active participation in class discussions.
- Observation of students who genuinely compliment other colleagues on their positive attribute and also have the ability to mingle with them.

Service-learning project

Activities can be organised among students on

- a. Mentorship Program: Develop a mentorship program that pairs students with professionals in their field of interest. This program can include workshops on

networking skills, such as how to introduce oneself, how to initiate and maintain a conversation, and how to follow up with contacts.

- b. **Networking Event:** Plan and organize a networking event for students to attend. This event can include guest speakers, workshops on networking skills, and opportunities for students to connect with professionals in their field of interest.
- c. **Alumni Database:** Create a database of alumni from your school or university who are willing to network with current students. This database can include contact information, job titles, and industry information. Students can use this database to reach out to alumni for advice and networking opportunities.
- d. **Professional Development Workshops:** Develop workshops on professional development skills, such as networking, interviewing, and resume writing. These workshops can be held in collaboration with local professionals or alumni.
- e. **Placement Program:** Develop a placement program that includes networking opportunities for students. Students can attend networking events, meet with professionals in their field, and receive training on networking skills. This program can help students build their professional networks while gaining valuable work experience.

Week Seven - Lecture

Conflict Resolution

Explicit Objectives

- Have the ability to define the problem.
- Summon courage to come together and communicate.
- Be willing to establish relationships.
- Get ready to develop an action plan.
- Be willing to gain commitment.
- Ensure to provide feedback.

Subject Matter

This lesson offers a diverse array of knowledge essential to empower learners in attaining the established objectives.

- Pay close attention to issues causing problem.

- Being able to understand everyone's interests.
- List and evaluate possible solutions in addressing the issue.
- Document the options agreed upon.

Instructional Approach

Brainstorming sessions for solutions, role playing, group discussions.

Learning Activities

Teacher

- Make students take responsibility for their own actions.
- Encourage students to keep their emotions under control.

Students

- Engage the class in paying attention to the body language of people they speak to
- Engage the class in attending events that will be beneficial to their growth.
- Students should have the ability to follow up on new friends made.

Materials/Resources

Relevant books on community building and restorative justice

Assessment

- Observation of students that are responsible for their actions.
- Observation of students who follow up on the welfare of others.

Service-learning project

Activities can be organised among students on

- a. Mediation Program: Develop a mediation program that trains students to be mediators and resolve conflicts between their peers. The program can include workshops on active listening, effective communication, and conflict resolution techniques.
- b. Restorative Justice Program: Develop a restorative justice program that helps students understand the impact of their actions on others, take responsibility for their behaviour, and make amends. The program can involve group discussions, role-playing exercises, and community service projects.

- c. Peer Counselling Program: Develop a peer counselling program that trains students to be effective listeners and provide emotional support to their peers. The program can include workshops on active listening, empathy, and communication skills.
- d. Community Building Activities: Develop community-building activities that promote collaboration and positive relationships between students. For example, students can work together to organize a community service project, plan a school event, or create a mural or art project that celebrates diversity.
- e. Conflict Resolution Workshops: Develop workshops on conflict resolution that are tailored to specific groups or communities. For example, workshops can be developed for teachers, parents, or community members who work with youth to teach them effective conflict resolution techniques.

Week Eight - Lecture

Systematic Thinking

Explicit Objectives

- Have the ability to ask questions.
- Encourage making good decisions.
- Have the ability to work in a team and connect different ideas.
- Being able to incorporate different points of view to inspire creativity.

Subject Matter

This lesson offers a diverse array of knowledge essential to empower learners in attaining the established objectives.

- Pay attention to issues causing problem.
- Focus on the solution of complex problems through pragmatic application of laws, principles, and concepts.
- Make informed decisions, as an individual or as a society, which requires an understanding of the complexity of the issue.

Instructional Approach

Brainstorming sessions for solutions, role playing, webinar

Learning Activities

Teacher

- Make students analyse the problem before jumping into action.
- Make students formulate multiple options.
- Encourage students to define and establish a selection criterion.
- Encourage students to be bold in making a final decision.

Students

- Engage the class in paying attention to problems before jumping into action.
- Engage the class in being confident in making decisions.
- Students should have the ability analyse solutions to problems.

Materials/Resources

Relevant books on networking and attending events.

Assessment

- Observation of students that are responsible for their actions.
- Observation of students who are confident in making decisions.

Service-learning project

Activities can be organised among students on

- a. Community Development Project: Develop a community development project that challenges students to think systematically about how to improve their community. Students can learn about systems thinking, including how to identify interrelationships and feedback loops, and use this approach to identify and address complex community issues.
- b. Sustainable Development Project: Develop a sustainable development project that challenges students to think systematically about how to promote sustainability in their community. Students can learn about sustainability principles, such as the triple bottom line and the circular economy and apply these principles to create sustainable solutions.
- c. Health and Wellness Project: Develop a health and wellness project that challenges students to think systematically about how to improve the health and well-being of their community. Students can learn about systems thinking tools, such as causal

loop diagrams and stock and flow diagrams and use these tools to identify and address the underlying causes of health issues.

- d. Education Reform Project: Develop an education reform project that challenges students to think systematically about how to improve the education system. Students can learn about systems thinking concepts, such as leverage points and systems archetypes, and use these concepts to identify and address the root causes of education issues.
- e. Climate Change Project: Develop a climate change project that challenges students to think systematically about how to address climate change. Students can learn about systems thinking methods, such as system mapping and boundary analysis, and use these methods to identify and address the underlying causes of climate change.

Week Nine - Lecture

Leadership

Explicit Objectives

- Have the ability to lead a group of diverse people.
- Have the ability to make good decisions for the team.
- Have the ability to work with diverse group of people.
- Hard working and confident in taking responsibility for the team.

Subject Matter

This lesson offers a diverse array of knowledge essential to empower learners in attaining the established objectives.

- Pay attention to how to plan a project and how to delegate duties.
- Motivating and encouraging team members and colleagues on how to reach their highest potential.
- Display of effective communication skills
- Resolving of conflicts among team members amicably to increase productivity.

Instructional Approach

Leadership talks, school clubs, role playing, webinar.

Learning Activities

Teacher

- Make students analyse the problem before jumping into action.
- Make students formulate multiple options.
- Encourage students to define and establish a selection criterion.
- Encourage students to be bold in making a final decision.

Students

- Engage the class in paying attention to problems before jumping into action.
- Engage the class in being confident in making decisions.
- Students should have the ability analyse solutions to problems.

Materials/Resources

Relevant books on networking and attending events.

Assessment

- Observation of students that are responsible for their actions.
- Observation of students who are confident in making decisions.

Service-learning project

Activities can be organised among students on

- a. Youth Empowerment Project: Develop a youth empowerment project that challenges students to develop leadership skills and empower their peers. Students can learn about leadership styles and traits, such as transformational leadership and emotional intelligence, and use these skills to inspire and motivate their peers.
- b. Community Engagement Project: Develop a community engagement project that challenges students to take a leadership role in improving their community. Students can learn about leadership principles, such as servant leadership and adaptive leadership, and apply these principles to engage community members and address community issues.
- c. Non-profit Management Project: Develop a non-profit management project that challenges students to lead a non-profit organization. Students can learn about leadership strategies, such as strategic planning and organizational change management, and apply these strategies to effectively manage a non-profit organization.

- d. Global Citizenship Project: Develop a global citizenship project that challenges students to develop leadership skills to address global issues. Students can learn about leadership practices, such as cross-cultural communication and collaboration, and use these practices to work with others to address global challenges.
- e. Entrepreneurship Project: Develop an entrepreneurship project that challenges students to lead a business venture. Students can learn about leadership skills, such as risk-taking and decision-making, and apply these skills to develop and lead a successful business.

Week Ten - Lecture

Creativity and Innovation

Explicit Objectives

- Engage in having an open mind and self-reflect on issues.
- Have the ability to ask open ended questions and get to know the problem at hand.
- Have the ability to network with invited entrepreneurs or human resource managers.

Subject Matter

This lesson offers a diverse array of knowledge essential to empower learners in attaining the established objectives.

- Make self-reflection part of the class activities.
- Engage students in innovative activities and reward the active students.
- Engage students in problem solving issues.

Instructional Approach

Game show, brainstorming, giving feedback and positive reinforcement.

Learning Activities

Teacher

- Make students think outside the box for possible solutions to issues.
- Make students engage in competitive activities.
- Encourage students to collaborate and put in strong efforts.
- Teachers should encourage students to be autonomous.

Students

- Students should be ready to seek creative solutions to problems.
- Students should be confident in innovating unique ideas.
- Students should have the ability to creatively analyse solutions to problems.

Materials/Resources

Relevant books on creativity and attending unique events to generate innovative ideas.

Assessment

- Observation of students that are responsible for their actions.
- Observation of students who are confident in making decisions.

Service-learning project

Activities can be organised among students on

- a. Social Entrepreneurship Project: Develop a social entrepreneurship project that challenges students to think creatively and innovatively about how to address a social issue in their community. Students can learn about design thinking, creativity techniques, and innovation frameworks, such as the lean startup approach, and use these tools to develop innovative and sustainable solutions to social challenges.
- b. Environmental Sustainability Project: Develop an environmental sustainability project that challenges students to think creatively and innovatively about how to promote sustainability in their community. Students can learn about sustainable design principles, such as cradle-to-cradle and biomimicry, and apply these principles to develop innovative solutions to environmental challenges.
- c. Maker Space Project: Develop a maker space project that challenges students to think creatively and innovatively about how to create something new. Students can learn about maker skills, such as 3D printing and robotics, and use these skills to design and create prototypes for new products or solutions to real-world problems.
- d. Arts and Culture Project: Develop an arts and culture project that challenges students to think creatively and innovatively about how to express themselves and engage their community through the arts. Students can learn about creative thinking techniques, such as brainstorming and mind mapping, and use these techniques to develop innovative and engaging arts and culture projects.

- e. Technology Project: Develop a technology project that challenges students to think creatively and innovatively about how to use technology to solve real-world problems. Students can learn about emerging technologies, such as artificial intelligence and the internet of things, and use these technologies to develop innovative solutions to complex problems.

Week Eleven - Lecture

Business Management

Explicit Objectives

- Initiate plans in knowing how to communicate business ideas, manage, analyse and translate the ideas into actions.
- Discuss and interact with entrepreneurs to refine students in improving their business plan or prepare for business plan competitions.
- Discover ways on how to face business continuity challenges and also give out best management and governance practices of a business.

Subject Matter

This lesson offers a diverse array of knowledge essential to empower learners in attaining the established objectives.

- Ways on how to make decisions on managing and analysing business challenges.
- Practical activities on engaging students in understanding how to overcome business challenges.
- The impact of interacting with existing business owners and employers of labour.

Instructional Approach

Game show, brainstorming, giving feedback and positive reinforcement from resource persons.

Learning Activities

Teacher

- Make students think outside the box for possible solutions to issues.
- Make students engage in competitive activities.
- Encourage students to collaborate and put in strong efforts.

- Teachers should encourage students to be autonomous.

Students

- Students should be ready to seek creative solutions to problems.
- Students should be confident in innovating unique ideas.
- Students should have the ability to creatively analyse solutions to problems.

Materials/Resources

Relevant books on creativity and attending unique events to generate innovative ideas.

Assessment

- Observation of students that are responsible for their actions.
- Observation of students who are confident in making decisions.

Service-learning project

Activities can be organised among students on

- a. Business Incubator Project: Develop a business incubator project that challenges students to think like entrepreneurs and develop new business ideas. Students can learn about business planning, market research, and financial analysis, and use these skills to develop a business plan and launch a new venture.
- b. Non-profit Management Project: Develop a non-profit management project that challenges students to learn about the unique challenges of managing a non-profit organization. Students can learn about non-profit fundraising, volunteer management, and program development, and use these skills to manage a non-profit organization and make a positive impact in their community.
- c. Marketing and Communications Project: Develop a marketing and communications project that challenges students to learn about marketing principles and how to effectively communicate with different stakeholders. Students can learn about branding, advertising, and public relations, and use these skills to promote a product, service, or cause.
- d. Operations Management Project: Develop an operations management project that challenges students to learn about the principles of operations management and how to manage a production process. Students can learn about supply chain management,

quality control, and process improvement, and use these skills to manage a production process and increase efficiency.

- e. Financial Management Project: Develop a financial management project that challenges students to learn about financial principles and how to manage a budget. Students can learn about financial analysis, budgeting, and forecasting, and use these skills to manage a budget for a non-profit organization or small business.

Week Twelve - Lecture

Problem solving and Strategic thinking.

Explicit Objectives

- Discover the impact of the problem and think in a strategic way to tackle it.
- Take time to analyse and articulate likely solutions to the problem.
- Discuss and interact with colleagues to understand the problem and make suggestions for solution.
- Discover ways on how to use the solution and reflect if the problem has been truly resolved.

Subject Matter

This lesson offers a diverse array of knowledge essential to empower learners in attaining the established objectives.

- Necessary actions in being a problem solver.
- Practical activities in engaging in problem solving and strategic thinking.
- Ways and methods to engage students in strategically initiating solution to problems.
- The importance of problem solving and strategic thinking.

Instructional Approach

Game show, brainstorming, giving feedback and positive reinforcement from resource persons.

Learning Activities

Teacher

- Make students think outside the box for possible solutions to issues.

- Make students engage in competitive activities.
- Encourage students to collaborate and put in strong efforts.
- Teachers should encourage students to be autonomous.

Students

- Students should be ready to seek creative solutions to problems.
- Students should be confident in innovating unique ideas.
- Students should have the ability to creatively analyse solutions to problems.

Materials/Resources

Relevant books on creativity and attending unique events to generate innovative ideas.

Assessment

- Observation of students that are responsible for their actions.
- Observation of students who are confident in making decisions.

Service-learning project

Activities should be organised among students on

- a. **Community Problem-Solving Project:** Develop a community problem-solving project that challenges students to identify and address a specific community issue. Students can learn about problem-solving methodologies, such as root cause analysis and brainstorming, and use these skills to develop innovative and sustainable solutions to the problem.
- b. **Business Strategy Project:** Develop a business strategy project that challenges students to think strategically about a business. Students can learn about strategic planning, market analysis, and competitive analysis, and use these skills to develop a comprehensive business strategy for a real or hypothetical business.
- c. **Social Innovation Project:** Develop a social innovation project that challenges students to use their problem-solving and strategic thinking skills to address a social issue. Students can learn about social entrepreneurship, design thinking, and innovation frameworks, and use these skills to develop and launch a social innovation initiative.
- d. **Environmental Sustainability Project:** Develop an environmental sustainability project that challenges students to think strategically about how to promote

sustainability in their community. Students can learn about sustainability planning, stakeholder engagement, and sustainable development, and use these skills to develop a comprehensive sustainability strategy for a real or hypothetical community.

- e. Crisis Management Project: Develop a crisis management project that challenges students to think strategically about how to manage a crisis. Students can learn about crisis management planning, risk assessment, and communication strategies, and use these skills to develop a crisis management plan for a real or hypothetical crisis situation.

Week Thirteen - Lecture

Work Ethics and Social Media Ethics

Explicit Objectives

- Explain the impact and importance of work and social media ethics.
- Connect the importance of work and social media ethics to being a good entrepreneur and employer.
- Recognize the importance and embark on an awareness campaign among colleagues.
- Acquire necessary information on issues that could affect work and social media ethics of an entrepreneur and employer.

Subject Matter

This lesson offers a diverse array of knowledge essential to empower learners in attaining the established objectives.

- Relevant information on work ethics and social media ethics.
- The importance of good work ethics and social media ethics.
- Principles involved in displaying good work and social media ethics.

Instructional Approach

The simulation technique will be employed to facilitate the generation, sharing, and application of knowledge.

Learning Activities

Teacher

- Lead discussions on various ways of promoting good work ethics and social media ethics.
- Guide students in understanding the importance and impact of work ethics and social media ethics to being a good entrepreneur and human resource manager.
- Guide the students in recognizing the merits of exhibiting good work ethics and social media ethics.

Students

- Students should be ready to participate in discussions regarding work ethics and social media ethics.
- Discover the benefits of maintaining good work ethics and social media ethics.
- Students should be available to identify practical ways in displaying good work ethics and maintain good social media ethics.

Materials/Resources

Internet links, social media platforms, images, video clips

Assessment

- Observation of students' ability to demonstrate good work ethics and social media ethics.
-

Service-learning project

Activities should be organised among students on

- a. Professionalism Project: Develop a professionalism project that challenges students to learn about the importance of work ethics and professional behaviour in the workplace. Students can learn about workplace ethics, communication skills, and professional conduct, and use these skills to develop a code of conduct for a real or hypothetical workplace.
- b. Social Media Ethics Project: Develop a social media ethics project that challenges students to learn about the impact of social media on society and the importance of responsible social media use. Students can learn about online privacy, digital citizenship, and social media ethics, and use these skills to develop a social media policy for a real or hypothetical organization.

- c. Volunteer Ethics Project: Develop a volunteer ethics project that challenges students to learn about the importance of ethics and integrity in volunteer work. Students can learn about volunteer ethics, cultural competence, and community engagement, and use these skills to develop a volunteer code of conduct for a real or hypothetical volunteer organization.
- d. Workplace Diversity Project: Develop a workplace diversity project that challenges students to learn about the importance of diversity and inclusion in the workplace. Students can learn about cultural competency, diversity awareness, and workplace equity, and use these skills to develop a diversity and inclusion policy for a real or hypothetical workplace.
- e. Service-Learning Reflection Project: Develop a service-learning reflection project that challenges students to reflect on their service-learning experience and the ethical issues they encountered. Students can learn about critical reflection, ethical decision-making, and community impact, and use these skills to develop a service-learning reflection report or presentation.

Week Fourteen - Lecture

Information Communication Technology

Explicit Objectives

- Explain the impact and importance of ICT to the development of a good employee and business owner.
- Identify the benefits of ICT in promoting employability and entrepreneurship.
- Highlight the importance and limitation of ICT skills to the 21st century graduate.

Subject Matter

This lesson offers a diverse array of knowledge essential to empower learners in attaining the established objectives.

- The meaning and importance of ICT to the 21st century graduate.
- Introduction to ICT and its significance for business, economics, and society.
- The benefits of ICT to promote employability and entrepreneurship.
- The goals ICT set to achieve in the all-round development of a 21st century graduate.

Instructional Approach

Internet navigation, word processing, and computer networking will be utilized to support the generation, sharing, and application of knowledge.

Learning Activities

Teacher

- Explain the concept of ICT and its importance to the 21st century graduates.
- Guide students in understanding the benefits of ICT in promoting employability and entrepreneurship skills.
- Lead the classroom in identifying the goals students will achieve if they undergo the ICT skills.

Students

- Students should be ready to participate in discussions regarding acquisition of ICT skills.
- Students should interact on their computer networking skills in promoting their employability and entrepreneurship skills.
- Students should be able to practice what has been taught during the introduction to ICT skills.

Materials/Resources

Internet links, images, video clips, database, google sheets.

Assessment

- Observation of students' ability to demonstrate adequate understanding of ICT.

Service-learning project

Activities should be organised among students on

- a. Digital Literacy Project: Develop a digital literacy project that challenges students to learn basic computer skills, such as using word processing software, creating spreadsheets, and conducting online research. Students can learn about digital citizenship, online safety, and digital communication, and use these skills to create digital Subject Matter, such as a website or blog.
- b. Coding Project: Develop a coding project that challenges students to learn programming languages, such as HTML, CSS, or JavaScript. Students can learn

about web development, app development, and software engineering, and use these skills to create a digital product, such as a website, mobile app, or video game.

- c. **Robotics Project:** Develop a robotics project that challenges students to learn about robotics technology, such as sensors, motors, and microcontrollers. Students can learn about engineering design, programming logic, and project management, and use these skills to build a robot that performs a specific task or solves a real-world problem.
- d. **Digital Media Project:** Develop a digital media project that challenges students to learn about digital media tools, such as photo editing software, video editing software, and graphic design software. Students can learn about visual communication, storytelling, and digital media ethics, and use these skills to create a digital media project, such as a video, podcast, or infographic.
- e. **Information Management Project:** Develop an information management project that challenges students to learn about database management, data analysis, and information security. Students can learn about information architecture, data modelling, and data visualization, and use these skills to create a database, analyse data, or implement a security system for a real or hypothetical organization.

Week Fifteen - Lecture

Resource management

Explicit Objectives

- Explain the definition of resource management.
- Identify the benefits associated with managing resources.
- Highlight the importance of being a resource manager to the 21st century graduate.
- Enumerate and explain resource management components and concepts.

Subject Matter

This lesson offers a diverse array of knowledge essential to empower learners in attaining the established objectives.

- The definition of resource management and its related concepts
- The importance of resource management to employability and entrepreneurship skills.

- The resource management components in relation to resource utilisation, planning and business intelligence.
- Consequences of poor resource management strategy.

Instructional Approach

Critical analysis of issues, simulations, class brainstorming and practical classes

Learning Activities

Teacher

- Explain the concept of resource management and its importance to the 21st century graduates.
- Guide students in understanding the consequences attached to poor resource management strategy.
- Guide the classroom in identifying the concepts and components related to resource management.

Students

- Students should be ready to answer relevant questions on resource management concepts and components.
- Students should interact with their colleagues on consequences of poor management strategy.
- Students should be able to work in a team to practise.

Materials/Resources

Internet links, textbooks, and related materials

Assessment

- Observation of students' and project-based assessment

Service-learning project

Activities should be organised among students on

- a. Sustainability Project: Develop a sustainability project that challenges students to learn about resource conservation and sustainable practices. Students can learn about renewable energy, waste reduction, and sustainable agriculture, and use these skills to implement sustainable practices in their community, such as building a community garden, conducting an energy audit, or creating a recycling program.

- b. Food Security Project: Develop a food security project that challenges students to learn about food production, distribution, and access. Students can learn about sustainable agriculture, food waste reduction, and food insecurity, and use these skills to develop a food security plan for their community, such as building a community garden, conducting a food drive, or creating a food bank.
- c. Water Resource Project: Develop a water resource project that challenges students to learn about water conservation, management, and pollution. Students can learn about water quality, water scarcity, and water rights, and use these skills to implement a water resource plan for their community, such as implementing water conservation measures, conducting a water quality test, or creating a water treatment system.
- d. Energy Management Project: Develop an energy management project that challenges students to learn about energy conservation, management, and production. Students can learn about renewable energy, energy efficiency, and energy policy, and use these skills to implement an energy management plan for their community, such as conducting an energy audit, implementing energy-efficient practices, or creating a renewable energy system.
- e. Natural Resource Management Project: Develop a natural resource management project that challenges students to learn about natural resource conservation, management, and restoration. Students can learn about land use, biodiversity, and ecosystem services, and use these skills to implement a natural resource management plan for their community, such as restoring a degraded ecosystem, conducting a biodiversity assessment, or creating a natural resource management policy.

Week Sixteen - Lecture

Self - Management

Explicit Objectives

- Give the definition of self-management.
- Identify the reason why self-management is important to promotion of employability and entrepreneurship skills.

- Highlight the importance of having the ability of self-awareness to the 21st century graduate.
- Enumerate and explain self-management components.

Subject Matter

This lesson offers a diverse array of knowledge essential to empower learners in attaining the established objectives.

- The definition of self-management and its related components.
- The importance of self-management to employability and entrepreneurship skills.
- The self-management components in relation to self-care, self-awareness and priority setting.

Instructional Approach

Critical analysis of issues, role playing and class discussions

Learning Activities

Teacher

- Explain the concept of self-management and its importance to the 21st century graduates.
- Guide students in understanding and sharpening their self-management skills.
- Guide the classroom in identifying the components related to self-management.

Students

- Students should be ready to answer relevant questions on self-management components.
- Students should discuss on self- management skills.
- Get involved in a project that promote self-management skills.

Materials/Resources

Internet pages, textbooks, and related materials

Assessment

- Observation of students' and project-based assessment

Service-learning project

Activities should be organised among students on

- a. Mindfulness Project: Develop a mindfulness project that challenges students to learn about mindfulness techniques and practices. Students can learn about stress management, emotional regulation, and self-awareness, and use these skills to implement mindfulness practices in their daily lives, such as meditation, yoga, or journaling.
- b. Time Management Project: Develop a time management project that challenges students to learn about time management strategies and techniques. Students can learn about goal setting, prioritization, and scheduling, and use these skills to manage their time more effectively, such as creating a daily or weekly schedule, tracking their time usage, or using a time management app.
- c. Healthy Lifestyle Project: Develop a healthy lifestyle project that challenges students to learn about healthy habits and practices. Students can learn about nutrition, exercise, and sleep hygiene, and use these skills to implement healthy habits in their daily lives, such as creating a meal plan, starting an exercise routine, or practicing good sleep hygiene.
- d. Goal Setting Project: Develop a goal setting project that challenges students to learn about setting and achieving goals. Students can learn about SMART goals, motivation, and self-reflection, and use these skills to set and achieve their own goals, such as improving their grades, learning a new skill, or starting a personal project.
- e. Self-Assessment Project: Develop a self-assessment project that challenges students to learn about self-reflection and self-assessment. Students can learn about self-awareness, strengths and weaknesses, and personal growth, and use these skills to conduct a self-assessment and create a personal development plan, such as identifying their strengths and weaknesses, setting goals for personal growth, and tracking their progress over time.

Week Seventeen - Lecture

Emotional Intelligence

Explicit Objectives

- Give the definition of emotional intelligence.

- Identify the importance of building emotional intelligence.
- Explain why emotional intelligence is so important to 21st century graduates.

Subject Matter

This lesson offers a diverse array of knowledge essential to empower learners in attaining the established objectives.

- The definition of emotional intelligence and its related components.
- The importance of building emotional intelligence to develop graduates' employability and entrepreneurship skills.
- Emotional Intelligence components in relation to self-awareness, relationship management and social awareness.

Instructional Approach

Critical analysis of issues, simulations, role playing, brainstorming and classroom discussions

Learning Activities

Teacher

- Explain the concept of emotional intelligence and its importance to the 21st century graduates.
- Guide students in understanding and building their emotional intelligence skills.
- Guide the classroom in identifying the components related to emotional intelligence.

Students

- Students should be ready to build emotional intelligence skills.
- Students should be able to develop emotional awareness.
- Participate in a project that enhances emotional intelligence.

Materials/Resources

Video clips, textbooks, and related materials

Assessment

- Observation of students' and project-based assessment

Service-learning project

Practical events should be organised among students on

- a. Empathy Project: Develop an empathy project that challenges students to learn about empathy and perspective-taking. Students can learn about active listening, communication skills, and understanding others' emotions, and use these skills to develop empathy towards others in their community, such as volunteering at a local shelter, nursing home, or community centre.
- b. Emotional Regulation Project: Develop an emotional regulation project that challenges students to learn about emotional regulation strategies and techniques. Students can learn about identifying and managing their own emotions, coping mechanisms, and self-reflection, and use these skills to regulate their own emotions in a healthy and productive way, such as through meditation, mindfulness, or creative expression.
- c. Conflict Resolution Project: Develop a conflict resolution project that challenges students to learn about conflict resolution skills and strategies. Students can learn about communication skills, problem-solving, and compromise, and use these skills to resolve conflicts in their community, such as through peer mediation, community forums, or restorative justice programs.
- d. Self-Awareness Project: Develop a self-awareness project that challenges students to learn about self-awareness and self-reflection. Students can learn about their own emotions, strengths and weaknesses, and personal values, and use these skills to become more self-aware and improve their emotional intelligence, such as through journaling, self-assessment, or personal development plans.
- e. Mindfulness Project: Develop a mindfulness project that challenges students to learn about mindfulness techniques and practices. Students can learn about stress management, emotional regulation, and self-awareness, and use these skills to implement mindfulness practices in their daily lives, such as meditation, yoga, or deep breathing exercises. This can help students develop a greater sense of emotional intelligence and awareness.

Week Eighteen - Lecture

Marketing

Explicit Objectives

- Give the meaning of marketing.
- Identify the roles of marketing and ways of implementing marketing strategies.
- Explain the benefits of acquiring variety of marketing skills by 21st century graduates.

Subject Matter

This lesson offers a diverse array of knowledge essential to empower learners in attaining the established objectives.

- The meaning of marketing and its related concepts.
- The importance of marketing and ways of implementing variety of marketing skills.
- The concept of marketing versus product visibility in the 21st century.

Instructional Approach

Critical analysis of issues, simulations, role playing, invitation of resource persons

Learning Activities

Teacher

- Explain the concept of marketing and its importance to the 21st century graduates.
- Guide students in understanding variety of marketing strategies.
- Guide the classroom in understanding marketing and product visibility.

Students

- Students should be able to work in a group to demonstrate their understanding of marketing skills
- Students should be able to participate in class discussions on marketing strategies
- Participate in a project that enhances marketing skills

Materials/Resources

Video clips, textbooks, internet resources and related materials

Assessment

- Observation of students' and project-based assessment

Service-learning project

Practical events should be organised among students on

- a. **Social Media Marketing Project:** Develop a social media marketing project that challenges students to learn about social media marketing strategies and techniques. Students can learn about Subject Matter creation, social media management, and audience targeting, and use these skills to create a social media campaign for a local non-profit organization or small business.
- b. **Event Planning Project:** Develop an event planning project that challenges students to learn about event planning and marketing. Students can learn about event logistics, promotion, and branding, and use these skills to plan and promote a fundraising or awareness-raising event for a local non-profit organization.
- c. **Market Research Project:** Develop a market research project that challenges students to learn about market research methods and techniques. Students can learn about survey design, data analysis, and market segmentation, and use these skills to conduct a market research study for a local small business or startup.
- d. **Product Launch Project:** Develop a product launch project that challenges students to learn about product development and marketing. Students can learn about product design, branding, and marketing strategy, and use these skills to create and launch a new product or service for a local small business or startup.
- e. **Public Relations Project:** Develop a public relations project that challenges students to learn about public relations strategies and techniques. Students can learn about media relations, crisis communication, and reputation management, and use these skills to create and execute a public relations campaign for a local nonprofit organization or small business.

Week Nineteen - Lecture

Time Management

Explicit Objectives

- Explain the concept of time management.
- Identify the reasons why time management is important to developing employability and entrepreneurship skills.
- Describe the consequences of poor time management to development of 21st century graduates.

Subject Matter

This lesson offers a diverse array of knowledge essential to empower learners in attaining the established objectives.

- The meaning of time management and its related concepts
- The importance of time management and reasons for acquiring time management skills
- The consequences of procrastination

Instructional Approach

Critical analysis of issues,

Learning Activities

Teacher

- Explain the concept of time management and developing schedules.
- Guide students in keeping to schedules and time allocated for events.
- Guide the classroom in understanding how to set priorities.
- Guide the students on how to avoid procrastination.

Students

- Students should be able to work by keeping to schedules and being able to maintain a flexible schedule.
- Students should be able to participate in competitions.
- Students should be able to stick to a routine and keep track of time.
- Students should arrange tasks in logical sequences and deadlines.

Materials/Resources

Video clips, textbooks, internet resources and related materials

Assessment

- Observation of students'

Service-learning project

Practical events should be organised among students on

- a. Time Management Skills Workshop: Develop a time management skills workshop that challenges students to learn about effective time management strategies and techniques. Students can learn about time-blocking, prioritization, goal setting, and

- procrastination management, and use these skills to create a workshop to teach others in the community about time management.
- b. **Community Service Project:** Develop a community service project that challenges students to learn about time management while volunteering. Students can learn about time management skills while volunteering at local food banks, shelters, or community centers. They can apply the time management skills they have learned to make their volunteering efforts more effective and efficient.
 - c. **Personal Time Management Project:** Develop a personal time management project that challenges students to learn about time management through self-reflection and goal setting. Students can learn about time management strategies and techniques such as to-do lists, prioritization, and time-blocking, and use these skills to create a personal time management plan to meet their academic and personal goals.
 - d. **Time Tracking Project:** Develop a time tracking project that challenges students to learn about effective time management by tracking their time usage over a week or two. Students can learn about time management techniques, identify time-wasting activities, and use these skills to create a plan to improve their time management.
 - e. **Time Management App Project:** Develop a time management app project that challenges students to learn about time management while developing an app. Students can learn about time management strategies and techniques and use these skills to develop an app that helps users to manage their time more effectively. This project can help students learn about time management and gain experience with app development.

Week Twenty - Lecture

Interpersonal

Explicit Objectives

- Explain the concept of interpersonal skills.
- Identify ways on how to improve interpersonal skills in the workplace.
- Describe the essential attributes of developing good interpersonal skills of 21st century graduates.

Subject Matter

This lesson offers a diverse array of knowledge essential to empower learners in attaining the established objectives.

- The meaning of interpersonal skills.
- Ways of improving interpersonal skills in the workplace.
- The attributes of good interpersonal skills of a graduate.

Instructional Approach

Critical analysis of issues, role playing

Learning Activities

Teacher

- Explain the concept of interpersonal skills.
- Guide students on how to improve their interpersonal skills.
- Guide the classroom in understanding how to develop interpersonal awareness.
- Guide the students on how to display good attributes of interpersonal skills.

Students

- Students should be able to engage in and understand the concept of interpersonal skills.
- Students should be able to participate in team working.
- Students should be informed on interpersonal awareness.

Materials/Resources

Video clips, textbooks, internet resources and related materials

Assessment

- Observation of students' relationship with team and colleagues.

Service-learning project

Activities should be organised among students on

- a. Mentoring Program: Develop a mentoring program that challenges students to learn about interpersonal skills through mentoring younger students or peers. Students can learn about active listening, empathy, and effective communication, and use these skills to mentor and support others in their community.

- b. **Team Building Project:** Develop a team-building project that challenges students to learn about interpersonal skills through collaborative activities. Students can learn about teamwork, conflict resolution, and effective communication, and use these skills to plan and execute a team-building event for a local organization or group.
- c. **Conflict Resolution Project:** Develop a conflict resolution project that challenges students to learn about interpersonal skills through conflict resolution. Students can learn about negotiation, mediation, and effective communication, and use these skills to develop and implement a conflict resolution program for a local organization or group.
- d. **Service-Learning Trip:** Develop a service-learning trip that challenges students to learn about interpersonal skills through service work in a different culture or community. Students can learn about cultural sensitivity, effective communication, and collaboration, and use these skills to work alongside members of a different community on a service project.
- e. **Communication Skills Workshop:** Develop a communication skills workshop that challenges students to learn about interpersonal skills through role-playing and other communication exercises. Students can learn about active listening, effective communication, and nonverbal communication, and use these skills to create a workshop to teach others in the community about communication skills.

Week Twenty-One - Lecture

Capacity for Lifelong Learning

Explicit Objectives

- Explain the concept of learning, unlearning and relearning.
- Identify ways on how to evolve as a lifelong learner.
- Describe the benefits and importance of lifelong learning.
- Explain how to adopt lifelong learning as a 21st century graduate.

Subject Matter

This lesson offers a diverse array of knowledge essential to empower learners in attaining the established objectives.

- The meaning of learning, unlearning and relearning.
- Ways of evolving as a lifelong learner.

- Benefits and importance of lifelong learning.
- How to adopt lifelong learning as a graduate.

Instructional Approach

Critical analysis of issues, role playing, brainstorming, class discussions

Learning Activities

Teacher

- Explain the concept of learning, unlearning and relearning.
- Guide students on how to evolve as a lifelong learner.
- Guide the classroom in understanding the benefits and importance of lifelong learning.
- Guide the students on how to adopt lifelong learning as a graduate.

Students

- Students should be able to learn, unlearn and relearn.
- Students should be able to evolve as a lifelong learner.
- Students should be well informed on the benefits and importance of being a lifelong learner.

Materials/Resources

Video clips, textbooks, internet resources and related materials

Assessment

- Observation of students' retention skills.

Service-learning project

Activities should be organised on

- a. Learning Resource Centre: Develop a learning resource centre that challenges students to learn about lifelong learning and share their knowledge with others in the community. Students can research and collect resources on a variety of topics, such as professional development, personal growth, and creative hobbies, and use these resources to create a learning centre in a local library, community centre, or school.

- b. **Personal Development Project:** Develop a personal development project that challenges students to learn about lifelong learning through self-reflection and goal setting. Students can learn about personal growth, creativity, and lifelong learning, and use these skills to create a personal development plan to pursue their interests and passions.
- c. **Mentorship Program:** Develop a mentorship program that challenges students to learn about lifelong learning through mentoring younger students or peers. Students can learn about the benefits of mentorship, share their knowledge and experience, and use these skills to mentor and support others in their community.
- d. **Learning Exchange Program:** Develop a learning exchange program that challenges students to learn about lifelong learning through cultural exchange and collaboration. Students can connect with students from other communities, cultures, and backgrounds and learn about their experiences and interests. They can then share their own experiences and knowledge to create a mutually beneficial learning exchange program.
- e. **Lifelong Learning Workshop:** Develop a lifelong learning workshop that challenges students to learn about lifelong learning through experiential learning and skill-building activities. Students can learn about the importance of lifelong learning, explore different learning styles and strategies, and use these skills to create a workshop to teach others in the community about lifelong learning.

Week Twenty-Two - Lecture

Teamwork and Collaboration

Explicit Objectives

- Explain the concept of teamwork and collaboration.
- Identify ways on how to promote teamwork and collaboration.
- Describe the principles of achieving effective teamwork and collaboration.
- Explain how to acquire teamwork and collaboration skill as a 21st century graduate.

Subject Matter

This lesson offers a diverse array of knowledge essential to empower learners in attaining the established objectives.

- The meaning of teamwork and collaboration.
- Promoting teamwork and collaboration in the workplace.
- Principles of team working and collaboration.

Instructional Approach

Critical analysis of issues, group work, role playing, brainstorming, class discussions

Learning Activities

Teacher

- Explain the concept of teamwork and collaboration.
- Guide students on how to promote teamwork and collaborate in the workplace.
- Guide the classroom in understanding the principles of teamwork and collaboration.

Students

- Students should be able to collaborate with each other.
- Students should be able work as a team player.
- Students should be well informed on the principles guiding collaboration and teamwork.

Materials/Resources

Video clips, textbooks, internet resources and related materials

Assessment

- Observation of students' ability to work in groups, teams, cohorts and perform excellently.

Service-learning project

Activities should be organised on

- a. Community Service Project: Develop a community service project that challenges students to work together and collaborate to serve the needs of their community. Students can identify a need in their community, such as cleaning up a local park or supporting a local charity and work together to plan and execute the project.
- b. Group Project: Develop a group project that challenges students to work together and collaborate to achieve a common goal. Students can work in small groups to

complete a project, such as planning an event or creating a product, and practice effective communication, delegation, and problem-solving skills.

- c. Peer Support Program: Develop a peer support program that challenges students to work together and collaborate to support the academic and personal growth of their peers. Students can work together to create a program that provides peer support, mentorship, and academic assistance to their peers.
- d. Team-building Retreat: Develop a team-building retreat that challenges students to work together and collaborate in a new environment. Students can participate in team-building activities, such as ropes courses or trust exercises, and practice effective communication, problem-solving, and conflict resolution skills.
- e. Collaborative Learning Project: Develop a collaborative learning project that challenges students to work together and collaborate to learn a new skill or concept. Students can work in pairs or small groups to research and learn about a topic, and then share their knowledge and insights with the class through a presentation or demonstration.

APPENDIX IX
Field Work Pictures

Researcher at Lagos State University administering research instruments

Researcher and research assistants at Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile Ife

Researcher in the class giving research instruments to students to fill at Osun State University

Researcher and assistant administering questionnaires at University of Lagos

Researcher at Lagos State University, Ojoo

Researcher administering questionnaires at Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife

Researcher and assistants at Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife

Researcher at Osun State University, Ipetu Ijesa Campus